

Safe-, sUstainable- and R recyclable-by design P olymeric systems
A guidance towardS next generation of plasticS

Start date of the project: 01/06/2022
Duration 42 months

Deliverable D4.2

**Report on release and transformation mechanisms
that could lead to human and environmental
exposure**

Work Package	4	Development and use of SSRbD Assessment tools, methods and guidance
WP Leader		CEA
Lead beneficiary		LEITAT
Contributing beneficiaries		LEITAT, CEA, IPC, BASF, RIVM
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Nature of the deliverable		
R	Report, document	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
DMP	Data Management Plan	<input type="checkbox"/>

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
SEN	Sensitive, restricted to a group specified by the consortium under conditions set out in grant agreement	<input type="checkbox"/>

Quality procedure			
Contractual delivery date	28/02/2025		
Actual delivery date	28/02/2025, updated version: 31/07/2025		
Version accepted by the Steering Board	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Report uploaded via Research Participant Portal	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Acknowledgements

The SURPASS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101057901. This publication reflects only the author's views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Version history

Version	Date	Partner - Author	Email	Comments ¹
1.1	10/2024	V. Cazzagon	vcazzagon@leitat.org	Creation
1.2	11/2024	C. Delpivo; P. Pfohl; D. Tissier; B. Pellegrin; S. Motellier; H. Fontaine	cdelpivo@leitat.org patrizia-marie.pfohl@basf.com Delphine.TISSIER@ct-ipc.com bastien.pellegrin@cea.fr sylvie.motellier@cea.fr herve.fonctaine@cea.fr	Modification
2	02/2025	S. Artous	Sebastien.artous@cea.fr	Review
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4	02/2025	Y. Staal	yvonne.staal@rivm.nl	Review
4.1	02/2025	I. Mikonsaari	Irma.mikonsaari@ict.fraunhofer.de	Review
4.2	02/2025	S. Clavaguera	simon.clavaguera@cea.fr	Final

¹ Creation, modification, final version for evaluation, revised version following evaluation, final

Executive summary

Deliverable 4.2 summarizes the work performed in the context of the identification and quantification of release materials' hotspots along the lifecycle of each SURPASS case study (construction, transport and food packaging sectors).

The first part of this Deliverable presents the theoretical work done for the identification of hotspots of release taking into account guidelines and protocols for the release assessment of substances that can be released from plastics products along their life cycle, as well as potential exposed targets (e.g., workers, consumers, environment). The second part summarises the experimental work performed based on the theoretical results obtained.

All the achievements of Task 4.2 are presented in this Deliverable as part of the development and use of Safe and Sustainable and Recyclable by Design assessment tools, methods and guidance of WP4.

List of acronyms

AFD	4-aminophenyl disulphide
A/R	Aspect/Ratio
ATR-FTIR	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy in Attenuated Total Reflectance mode
AUC	Analytical ultracentrifugation
CAS	Chemical Abstracts Service
CS	Case Study
DI	Dustiness Index
DOC	Dissolved Organic Compounds / Organic Carbon
DOP	Diethyl Phthalate
DGEBA	Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether
DGEPPG	Butanediol diglycidyl ether
EoL	End of Life
EVOH	Ethylene Vinyl Alcohol
feSEM	Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy
FR	Flame Retardant
GC-MS	Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry
HEDS	2-Hydroxyethyl disulfide
HS-GC-MS	Head Space Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry
IAS	Intentionally Added Substances
ICP-MS	Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LDPE	Low-density polyethylene
mLLDPE	metallocene Linear Low-Density Polyethylene
ML	MultiLayer
MDA	4,4-methylene dianiline
MDI	methylene diphenyl diisocyanate
MNL	MultiNanoLayer
MSDS	Material Safety Data Sheet
NIAS	Non-Intentionally Added Substance
OM	Overall Migration
OPS	Optical Particle Sizer
PA	Polyamide
PA6	Polyamide 6
PE	Polyethylene
PMDI	Poly methylene diphenyl diisocyanate
PO	Polyolefin
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
PPG	Polypropylene Glycol
PTFE	Polytetrafluoroethylene
PU	Polyurethane
PSD	Particle Size Distribution

QL	Quantification Limit
RMM	Risk Management Measures
RTM	Resin Transfer Moulding
scCO ₂	supercritical CO ₂ process
SD	Standard Deviation
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SM	Specific Migration
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
SVOCs	Semi-Volatile Organic Compound
TCPP	Tris(1-chloro-2-propyl) phosphate
TD-GC-MS/FID	Thermo-Desorption Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry Flame Ionization Detector
TEDA	triethylenediamine
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscopy
THEED	N, N, N', N'-Tetrakis (2-hydroxyethyl) ethylenediamine
TGA	Thermogravimetric Analysis
TMP	Triol Trimethylolpropane
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TVOC	Total Volatile Organic Compounds
UPLC-tofMS	Ultra-Performance Liquid Chromatography with time-of-flight Mass Spectrometry detector
VOCs	Volatile Organic Compounds
WHO	World Health Organisation

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Introduction

The EU-funded SURPASS project (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101057901>, <https://www.surpass-project.eu/>) will lead by example the transition towards more Safe, Sustainable and Recyclable by Design (SSRbD) polymeric materials. The SURPASS consortium of 14 partners consisting of research and technology organizations and industries will:

1. Develop SSRbD alternatives with no potentially hazardous additives through industrially relevant case-studies (TRL3-5) targeting the three sectors representing 70% of the European plastic demand:
 - Building: bio-sourced polyurethane resins with enhanced vitrimer properties to replace insulating PVC for window frames (40% C-Footprint reduction)
 - Transport: lightweight, therefore less energy-consuming epoxy-vitrimer (30% C-Footprint reduction), as alternative to metal for the train structure, anticipating emerging use of non-recyclable composites.
 - Packaging: MultiNanoLayered films involving no compatibilizers to replace currently non-recyclable multi-layers films (60% C-Footprint reduction).
2. Optimize reprocessing technologies adapted to the new SSRbD systems to support achievement of ambitious recyclability targets.
3. Develop a scoring-based assessment that will guide material designers, formulators and recyclers to design SSRbD polymeric materials, operating over the plastic's entire life cycle, including hazard, health, environmental and economic assessment.
4. Merge all data and relevant methodologies in a digital infrastructure, offering an open-access user-friendly interface for innovators.

SURPASS activities are distributed within 7 work packages, among them WP4 is focusing on the assessment of the SSbD strategies, addressing hazard (Task 4.3), release (Task 4.2) and life cycle (Task 4.4) and life cycle costing (Task 4.5) assessment.

The main objective of this Deliverable is to present the results obtained for the release assessment conducted in Task 4.2 for the three case studies considered in SURPASS.

Task 4.2 aims to analyse the release from the materials used and the products generated in the case studies. Data and information on release are relevant for material/ product designers, because the release can be considered the first step in the exposure pathway. Therefore Task 4.2 addresses the assessment steps 2- *Safety during manufacturing* and 3- *Safety during use* required in the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) Framework developed by JRC. Specifically, a theoretical work has been firstly conducted to identify potential hotspots of release along the life cycle of each case study. Once hotspots of release were identified, specific experimental tests were performed to simulate the corresponding exposure scenarios. The beneficiaries LEITAT, CEA, IPC and BASF strongly collaborated by sharing information on the best analytical techniques to be used and experimental conditions that can represent realistic exposure scenarios using knowledge acquired in previous projects (e.g., GUIDEnano (G.A. 604387), Gracious (G.A. 760840), SAbyNA (G.A. 862419)).

Theoretical and experimental results will be then used in D5.4 ("Validation of the SURPASS digital infrastructure") to validate the infrastructure developed by the beneficiary GEONARDO through the development of a scoring system for the release assessment of substances from plastics materials as part of the implementation of the SSbD Framework.

Table 1: Involved beneficiaries in T4.2

Consortium partner	Full name	Organization type
CEA	Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et aux Énergies Alternatives	RTO
LEITAT	ACONDICIONAMIENTO TARRASENSE ASSOCIACION	RTO
IPC	CENTRE TECHNIQUE INDUSTRIEL DE LA PLASTURGIE ET DES COMPOSITES	RTO
BASF	Badische Anilin & Soda-Fabrik	Industry

Description of the tasks

LEITAT, CEA, IPC, and BASF

- 1) perform the mapping of the potential hotspot routes of release and exposure (including identification of main drivers for chemical extractability and durability) with a special focus on the use and end-of-life phases considering the product life cycle and inputs from T1.2 and
- 2) prepare a chemical inventory of potential substances (components and released forms derived from polymeric materials degradation or transformation processes with emphasis on components conferring to the product an increase of performance).

CEA (for CS#1 - building sector) and LEITAT (for CS#2 – railway sector) perform environmental weathering and mechanical solicitations after having harmonized protocols and data collection templates. Leaching and migration of contaminants assays from food packaging (CS#3) to foodstuff is covered by IPC, through an experimental design allowing to identify correlations between detected Non-Intentionally Added Substance (NIAS) and the formulation/design parameters of the films. RIVM and BASF contribute by sharing protocols, data and analytical capabilities.

CEA, LEITAT and IPC analyse released substances (released products and product alterations) in air and/or liquids via an anticipated methodological development. A common strategy is used: search of volatile and semi-volatile molecules ($100 < M_w < 600$) by GC-MS, then search of semi-volatile and / or ionic molecules ($100 < M_w < 2500$ g / mol) by qualitative UPLC / TOF-MS chromatography analysis.

BASF additionally conduct “spot check” evaluations on microplastics release. Release potential can be assessed by emerging standards based on ISO routines as described in ISO TR 22293 (2021). Specifically, BASF apply an adapted protocol (from Cefic LRI ECO59 and BMBF InnoMat.Life) to identify and quantify microplastic fragments from weathering materials, and their secondary degradation into nanoplastics and dissolved components. The physiochemical characterization of newly produced and used/weathered/degraded/disrupted plastics will feed into the toxicological assessment as performed in T4.3.

Description of the work and main achievements

The identification of hotspots of release, transformations processes and release quantification through experimental work have been planned and executed for each SURPASS case study and each assessment route identified in [Deliverable 4.1](#).

For the identification of hotspots of release along the life cycle of each case study, a questionnaire has been developed and filled in collaboration with WP2 (material) and WP3 (reprocess and recycling) partners. All the details are presented in paragraph 1.1.

To investigate potential transformation mechanisms of the substances/materials investigated and the corresponding transformed products, both release experiments and literature search have been conducted on components and released forms derived from polymeric materials degradation or transformation processes with emphasis on components conferring to the product an increase of performance.

Based on the release hotspots identified, experimental tests were planned and executed by LEITAT, IPC, CEA and BASF through a continuous collaboration between Indresmat and CIDETEC. Additional experimental results will be included in an updated version of this D4.2 until the end of the SURPASS project in November 2025. In the following paragraphs, all the experiments details and results are reported.

1.1 Release hotspot identification

To identify potential release of substances/materials along the life cycle of each case study (from the manufacturing to the end-of-life, and eventually considering re-use), an excel file was developed to organize important information related to the substances used and the activities performed at each stage of the life cycle. To do so, European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) guidelines were considered to collect and group this information in sub-categories.

More specifically, material-specific information and use-description following ECHA R12:2015 on use description, ECHA R14:2016 for occupational exposure assessment, ECHA R15:2016 for consumer exposure assessment, ECHA R18:2016 for environmental exposure estimations. Additionally, in collaboration with polymers manufacturers, specific information on the physico-chemical characteristics of their materials have been added to collect polymers-specificity that can help in the investigation of materials released or transformation processes along their life cycle.

All the information added in the excel file are listed here below considering the sub-categories previously mentioned. For some information, a free text should be included, and for other we provided a dropdown menu, which options are reported in brackets. Underlined information are key aspects that can determine a potential release or emission of material.

The first inputs are general information about the life cycle stage, exposure scenario and the SURPASS Chemical Identifier that permits to connect the information collected in the hotspot release questionnaire with the ones in the hazard questionnaire developed in T4.3 to ensure traceability of data.

General information:

- Contact person who adds the data.
- Life cycle stage.
- Activity.
- Exposure scenario/Contributing activity.

Material-specific information:

- SURPASS Chemical Identifier.
- Amount of substance used and unit.
- Substance name.
- Product type (e.g., pellets, powder, liquid).
- Composition and crystallinity (if known).
- If powder, dustiness index (*if YES, specify if: Low: pellet-like, non-friable solids. Little evidence of any dust observed during use, e.g., PVC pellets, waxes; Medium: crystalline, granular solids, e.g., when used, dust is seen, but it settles quickly, dust is seen on the surface after use; High: fine, light powders, e.g., when used, dust clouds can be seen to form and remain airborne for several minutes).*
- Moisture (<5% moisture content ; 5-10% moisture content ; >10% moisture content).
- Weight fraction (*if the weight fraction is not precisely known, pick if it is: pure material (100%); main component (50-90%); substantial (10-50%); minor (5-10%); small (1-5%); very small (0.5-1%); extremely small (0.1-1.5%); minute (0.01-0.1%).*

Activity-related information:

- Setting activities (e.g., indoor/outdoor, industry/house/public place).
- If indoor, room conditions (T, humidity, air velocity) and volume of the room.
- Energy level of process (*Choose from Zero (e.g., removal and handling of clean barrels and plastic containers); Very low (e.g., weighing small amounts of material); Low (e.g., < 5 cm drop height); Moderate (e.g., drop between 5-30 cm, mixing nanomaterials in a liquid medium); High (e.g., drop between 30-100 cm); Very high (e.g., drop from > 100 cm, dry mixing, dry cleaning with a brush).*
- Level of containment of the process (*closed, semi-enclosed (e.g., fumehood) or open-air process*).
- Level of automatization of the process (*Manual, automatic, semiautomatic*).

Worker exposure:

- Number of workers.
- Potential route of exposure and body part exposed.
- Is the task being carried out in the breathing zone of an employee? (Distance head-product < 1 meter) (YES/NO).
- Is there more than one employee carrying out the same task simultaneously? (YES/NO).
- Activity duration (min) of each work cycle.
- Time between each work cycle (hours).
- Number of repeated work cycle daily.
- Type of Local Exhausted Ventilation system (LEV).
- Ventilation rate (*the ventilation system is a Risk Management Measure (RMM) for occupational inhalation exposure but can increase the emission rate to outdoor air, which could increase exposure of the general population living in the vicinity of the site. ECHA 2008*) (No ventilation (<1 ACH), Basic (up to 3 ACH), Good (3 to 5 ACH), Enhanced (5 to 10 ACH), Specialised (10 to 30 ACH), Specialised (more than 30 ACH).
- Type of air filtration and % reduction of filter.
- Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) for inhalation route.
- PPE for dermal route.

Consumer exposure:

- Conditions of use (e.g., outdoor, indoor).
- Mode of exposure (e.g., mouthing, skin contact).
- Duration and frequency of use.
- Migration mechanism if any (e.g., for food contact materials).

Environmental release/ exposure:

- Intended release (i.e., none, low, high).
- Environmental compartment where the release occurred.
- Substance(s) released.
- Quantity of substance released.
- Frequency of substance release.
- Risk Management Measures used to reduce releases.
- Effectiveness of waste treatment.
- If recycling, type of material recycled.
- If recycling, waste of recycling process.
- Waste Treatment (*Municipal Waste; Recycling; Landfill; Incineration; Thermal treatment*).

An excel file was made for each case study where each sheet represents a different assessment route. Data were collected together with the manufacturer of the composite/plastic material (e.g., Indresmat for CS#1, CIDETEC for CS#2, and IPC for CS#3) through virtual meetings.

Hotspots of release were identified for each case study and each assessment route combining information on materials properties and on process/activity. As reference, the use of a material in

powder form with high dustiness during a high energy process, was considered a likely hotspot for release. As no guidelines are available at the moment to define whether or not a material can be released, the expert judgement and previous experiences were used to identify the hotspots also in case of data gaps. Several meetings with T4.2 partners and manufacturers were organized to identify and agree on the main hotspots of release, considering case study specificities. Results are reported in the following paragraphs for each case study.

Gender dimension

As mentioned in the SURPASS Description of Work, the project consortium is exploring whether and how the gender dimension is relevant to all the tasks and research activities conducted during the project.

In the context of task 4.2, gender dimension is an important aspect to consider because of the diversity in biological structure of the body and different types of activities performed by workers, consumers and general population of each case study along their life cycles. For this reason, once release hotspots were identified, gender-dimension considerations have been taken into account, such as the frequency, the quantity and the gender of the target(s) potentially exposed. Results are reported in the release hotspots description.

For some of the CS, exposure scenarios could consider a target population more “male-related” or “female-related” (e.g., in the building sector, consider exposure will be more important for males than females). However, for the life cycle stage linked to use, exposure scenarios could consider a target population as “male-related” as “female-related” (e.g., in the packaging sector, considering exposure will be important for males and females: all of them can eat food conditioned on plastic packaging). General considerations related to this aspect are reported for each life cycle stage.

1.2 Release estimation and transformation mechanisms

Case study 1 aims to develop an alternative PU used in building sector for windows frame manufacturing which would be recyclable and also in a second approach bio-sourced. The recyclability objective will be obtained by the vitrimerization of the current fossil-based PU (CEA) and also by newly bio-based PU (LEITAT).

1.2.1 Case study 1 (CS#1)

Polyurethane-based window frames are intended to replace those made of PVC, wood or aluminum. To select a suitable benchmark material for the SSbD assessment, we proposed focusing on various polyurethane alternatives, particularly those being developed in WP2 and WP3. Procuring PVC, wood, or aluminium-based window frames would require significant effort and pose challenges due to the wide variety of formulations available on the market. Given the resource constraints and the extensive efforts required to test multiple materials, we have decided to concentrate on the routes investigated in the SURPASS project. Therefore, four different routes are considered for the release assessment in case study #1 (windows frame manufacturing – building sector) and illustrated in Figure 1. The first route, considered as the Reference route, corresponds to the PU window frame currently commercialized by Indresmat. The second route (SSbD#0 route) refers to the route equivalent to the Reference route, but with the implementation of bio-based polyols. The third route (SSbD#1 route)

describes the integration of a recycling process (through vitrimerization) developed by CEA on End-of-Life (EoL) fossil-based PU windows frames. The last route considered (SSbD#2 route) refers to the recycling approach investigated by LEITAT, where the initial bio-based PU formulation is modified with the introduction of an exchange chemistry (di-sulfide bond) with the objective to award mechanical recyclability to the polymer upfront.

Figure 1. Routes considered for release assessment in case study 1

Hereunder is reported the information gathered on the PU formulation for each route assessed.

Reference route - Fossil-based PU

According to the information provided by Indresmat, the fossil-based PU composition used to produce the Reference PU windows frames comprises a polyol component mixed with an isocyanate component and water (used as foaming agent).

The polyol component is a formulated commercial product (BASF, Elastolit® D 8240/101). According to the Material Safety Data Sheet (MSDS), in addition to an ether-based polyol, it comprises a catalyst, a flame retardant agent and other additives. More specifically, the MSDS lists the following substances considered as hazardous ingredients according to UN GHS criteria:

- Diethylmethylbenzenediamine
 - o Content (W/W): $\geq 25\%$ - $\leq 45\%$
 - o CAS Number: 68479-98-1
- 1,1',1'',1'''-Ethylenedinitrilotetrapropan-2-ol
 - o Content (W/W): $\geq 1\%$ - $< 20\%$
 - o CAS Number: 102-60-3
- Polyetherdiamine
 - o Content (W/W): $\geq 3\%$ - $< 5\%$
 - o CAS Number: 9046-10-0

The isocyanate component is a commercial product (BASF, IsoPMDI 92140). According to the MSDS, it comprises 100 % of polymethylene diphenyl diisocyanate (PMDI, CAS Number: 9016-87-9), which is a mixture of methylene diphenyl diisocyanate (MDI) oligomers

Windows frames are manufactured through reactive injection molding process (at room temperature, slightly exothermic reaction), followed by cutting and assembly steps.

SSbD#0 route - Bio-based PU

As for its fossil counterpart, the bio-based PU formulation comprises a polyol component mixed with an isocyanate component and water (used as foaming agent). The isocyanate is unchanged (PMDI, CAS Number: 9016-87-9), whereas the polyol is replaced by a mixture of different bio-based polyols. The polyol mixture comprises ester-based castor oil derivatives, but, as part of industrial know-how, the exact References were not communicated by Indresmat.

The manufacturing process is performed through reactive injection molding, similarly to the Reference route.

SSbD#1 route – Vitrimerized fossil-based PU

The approach here consists in infusing a powder of fossil-based PU (Reference route material) with a mixture of catalyst (N,N,N',N'-Tetrakis(2-hydroxyethyl)ethylenediamine - THEED) and an organic disulfide (Cystamine) in anisole solution as solvent :

Following this impregnation step, the solvent is evaporated, and the retrieved powder may be processed at high temperature and pressure to obtain a reshaped PU. The ultimate objective is to melt process this powder via an extruder and implement an inline foaming step to obtain a similar material as the original PU, but some technical challenges remain to be overcome. At this point of the project, the infused powder is processed by thermal compression moulding to obtain dense disks (d ~ 32 mm; h ~ 1.5 mm). An illustration of the fossil-based PU reprocessing steps developed by CEA is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. PU recycling strategy developed by CEA in SSbD#1 route

In the long run, this recycling process would be intended to be implemented on EoL PU windows frames but early stage developments are conducted on a model material consisting in fresh PU foam grinded and provided by Indresmat.

SSbD#2 route - Bio-based PU vitrimer

The strategy developed by LEITAT consists in substituting part of the bio-based polyol in the initial PU formulation by an organic disulfide species with two hydroxyl groups (2-Hydroxyethyl disulfide, HEDS). The objective is to integrate the disulfide bounds in the PU backbone to take advantage of its reversibility at high temperature, theoretically enabling melted polymer reprocessability.

Similarly to SSbD#1 route, the proof of concept of the bio-based PU vitrimer reprocessing is intended to be performed by thermal compression moulding after grinding.

1.2.1.1 Hotspot identification

In this section, the conclusions of the release hotspots' identification performed on case study #1 are reported.

The objective of this analysis is to identify stages/operations along the life cycle of the product (from manufacturing to end-of-life) where significant potential for unintentional release of substances is anticipated. To conduct the analysis, interviews of the parties in charge of the material development (Indresmat, LEITAT & CEA – WP2-3) were carried out to collect relevant information regarding materials, products and processes. The collected data were organized in the template file described in paragraph 3.1 including for each route assessed:

- a chemical inventory of substances, compounds and reagents.
- a comprehensive list of the operations/steps related to each life cycle stage and the associated chemicals, parameters and/or conditions.

Based on these data and considerations such as the state of matter, the phys-chem properties of the implemented reagents, the energy level of the operation considered or the use conditions of the product, potential release hotspots have been identified as reported in Figure 3.

The hotspots can be separated into three main categories:

- Cutting/milling activities: with a high potential of particulate release due to the high mechanical energy involved and the production of powder material.

- Consumer use: with a long term implementation of the products in indoor/outdoor setting including exposure to UV, temperature and humidity potentially leading to degradation mechanisms and subsequent release of pollutants.
- Thermal compression step (during recycling): with a high potential of release (especially volatile organic compounds (VOCs)) due to the processing of powder material at high temperature.

For each category, exposure scenarios and associated characterization methods were defined to evaluate the potential release of various species. The implemented protocols are detailed in the following section.

Indresmat, LEITAT and CEA were also providing information related to the gender dimension. During the windows frame process fabrication at Indresmat facilities a percentage of 100% male are involved. During the installation of the window frame (use stage), 87%. While for the end of life, 80% of recycling activities are carried out by men.

Life Cycle Stage	Activity / Exposure Scenario	Route	Potential Hotspot of release	Potential receptor(s) of release/ exposure	Potential exposure route(s)/ Exposed environmental compartments	Experimental test	Substance of interest
Step 1 & Step 2 - Material design (Formulation & Manufacturing)	Mixing of polyol phase	All	NA (no info available)				
	Oxime addition	SSRbD#1	NO				
	Reactive injection molding	All	NO				
	Cleaning (injection part)	All	NO				
	Demolding	All	NO				
	Mold cleaning	All	NO				
	Storage	All	NO				
	Cutting	All	YES - High energy mechanical activity	Workers	Inhalation, Dermal	Powder analysis	Particulate materials (micro & nano plastics)
Assembly	All	NO					
Painting	All	NA (no info available)					
Step 3 - Use, maintenance and repair (Life & Life N)	Windows frame installation	All (Life), SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2 (Life N)	NO	Consumers	Dermal		Additives, catalysts, degradation products (e.g., VOCs, oligomers, micro & nano plastics)
	Consumer use	All (Life), SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2 (Life N)	YES - Long term use in indoor/ outdoor setting	Environment	Soil, waters	UV/ thermal aging, environmental leaching	Additives, catalysts, degradation products (e.g., VOCs, oligomers, micro & nano plastics)
	Maintenance / repair	All (Life), SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2 (Life N)	NO				
Step 4 - EoL, reprocessing	Milling	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	YES - Powder material, high energy mechanical activity	Workers	Inhalation, Dermal	Powder analysis	Particulate materials (micro & nano plastics)
	Thermal impregnation	SSRbD#1	NO				
	Solvent evaporation	SSRbD#1	TBC (depend on level of containment)				
	Thermal compression	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	YES - Powder material, high pressure and temperature process	Workers	Inhalation	Laboratory thermal treatment	Particulate materials (micro & nano plastics)
Step 5 - End of Life	Landfill	All	NA (no info available)				
	Incineration	All	NA (no info available)				

Figure 3. Identification of hotspots of release for CS#1

1.2.1.2 Experimental setup

As schematically illustrated in Figure 4, based on the activities previously identified as hotspots, realistic exposure scenarios were designed and associated characterization methods were selected.

Figure 4. Release assessment strategy for CS#1

For the activities involving powder generation or manipulation (cutting, milling, handling...) which implied potentially workers exposure, the powder materials properties were characterized to qualitatively evaluate their potential of transfer to the environment through two parameters:

- The number-based particle size distribution (PSD), obtained by automated optical microscopy acquisition and image analysis (Morphologi G3, Malvern Panalytical).
- The dustiness indexes (DI_{RN} & DI_{RM} , defined in §1.2.1.3), obtain by Vortex Shaker method, according to EN 17199-5:2019.

Additionally, scanning electron microscopy (feSEM, FEI NovaNanoSEM 200 in low vacuum mode) was performed on powder particles deposited on carbon tape to collect information on the particle morphology.

For the thermal compression step included in the recycling process, a thermal degradation study of the PU powders was implemented to assess the workers exposure. First, analysis of the thermal stability of the powders was carried out by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, TA Instruments Q600 SDT) for evaluating mass losses and behaviour of materials at the compression temperature (for SSbD#1 route, $T = 200^\circ\text{C}$). Then, the emitted volatile and semi-volatile organic compounds (VOCs & SVOCs) were characterized by direct Thermo-Desorption Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry (for identification) & Flame Ionization Detector (for quantification) (TD-GC-MS/FID; TD Ultra-xr Unity series2 from Markes and GC5975C VL MSD from Agilent Technologies). The protocol consists in inserting a low amount of powder (~5 mg) directly in a thermal desorption empty tube for subjecting to the compression temperature under flushed helium for a given time. This way, the emitted VOCs & SVOCs are then injected for GC-MS/FID analysis. These experimental tests have been conducted on the available powders provided by the WP2&3 partners, namely the pristine fossil-based PU (Reference route) and its vitrimerized counterpart (SSbD#1 route).

Regarding the consumer use phase, a release assessment study associated with environmental weathering and leaching protocols was carried out. The environmental weathering protocol consists in exposing PU specimens to UV radiation under specific temperature and humidity conditions in a weathering chamber (Q-SUN xenon arc test chamber, Q-Lab). The exposure parameters are adapted from EN ISO 4892-2 Method A: the specimens are continuously exposed to a realistic reproduction of full spectrum sunlight (including ultraviolet, visible light, and infrared radiation) with an UV irradiance of 0.51 W/m²/nm at 340 nm. Temperature and relative humidity inside the chamber are respectively fixed at 40 +/-2 °C and 50 +/-2 %. The exposure time is set at 250h, 500h and 1000h.

To evaluate the impact of UV exposure on PUs properties, a broad panel of characterization techniques were performed on pristine (prior weathering) and aged specimens, including:

- feSEM (FEI NovaNanoSEM 200 in low vacuum mode) for morphological change assessment
- Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR, BRUKER Vertex70 in Attenuated Total Reflectance mode) for surface chemical analysis
- Tensile testing (3R Syntax) and linear abrasion (TABER Linear Abraser Model 5750) for mechanical properties and wear resistance evaluation

In parallel, the potential release of pollutants in air and liquids was evaluated and compared for pristine and aged PU samples:

- VOCs and SVOCs airborne emission rates at 40°C (temperature representative of stringent use conditions) were extrapolated from release study performed at 50-90°C temperature range obtained by TD-GCMS/FID,
- Release of dissolved organic species analysis was conducted by Ultra-Performance Liquid Chromatography equipped with time-of-flight Mass Spectrometry detector (UPLC-tofMS) after extraction steps (partial extraction in water & total extraction in methanol/toluene)
- Release rates of secondary micro and nano-plastic fragments were also evaluated (results reported in following section).

Figure 5 summarizes the analysis performed on the different specimens as a function of their physical forms, the route considered, and the addressed hotspot of release.

Route	Reference			SSbD#0		SSbD#1		SSbD#2	
Material	Fossil PU			Bio PU		Vitrimerized PU (Fossil-based)		Vitrimerized PU (bio-based)	
Specimen type	Dense	Foam	Powder	Dense	Foam	Dense	Powder	Dense	Foam

Cutting/milling activities (Powder characterization)									
Vortex shaker method (Dustiness indexes)			✓				✓		
Optical analysis (PSD)			✓				✓		
feSEM (morphology)			✓				✓		
Thermal compression step (Thermal degradation study)									
TGA @200°C (Mass loss)			✓				✓		
TD-GC-MS/FID @200°C (VOCs & sVOCs emission)			✓				✓		
Consumer use (Environmental weathering & leaching)									
feSEM (surface morphology)	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
FTIR (chemical surface analysis)	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
Tensile testing (mechanical properties)	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
Linear abrasion (wear resistance)	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
TD-GC-MS/FID (VOCs & sVOCs emission)	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
UPLC-tofMS (dissolved species analysis)	(✓)	✓			✓	✓			✓
GC-MS (dissolved species analysis)		✓			✓	✓			✓
Optical counter & AUC (µ/nano plastics release)	✓	✓			(✓)	✓			(✓)

Figure 5. Overview of the assessed PU specimens and associated characterization methods for CS#1

Micro- and nanoplastic spot-checks

In the microplastic spot-check analysis for CS1 materials, the NanoRelease sampling protocol was applied before and after UV aging of the test specimen, as described above (1000 h according to ISO4892). The purpose of the NanoRelease protocol is to remove loosely attached secondary micro- and nanoplastics from the surface of the (aged) test specimen and to disperse them in water for subsequent analysis. The pristine and aged PU plates varied in size, but a water volume of 6 mL was used in all cases. 6 mL of ultrapure water was filled in a glass container and a PU plate was placed onto it (with the aged side facing the water). In the next step the sample was treated in the ultrasonic bath at 100% power for 1 hour. During this time, regular cooling with ice was necessary to maintain the temperature below 40°C. After the ultrasonication treatment, the plate was removed, and the liquid was collected using a syringe. The collected volumes, the initial volume used for the treatment and the sizes of the plates were documented. Blank measurements in absence of a PU plate were conducted to determine the particle background.

For the subsequent analysis three different techniques were used:

- 1) A particle counter was used to quantify the released fragments from 1- 120 μm : measurements were done with an Abakus[®] Mobil Fluid laser particle counter (Klotz GmbH) equipped with a laser sensor LDS 2148(0) (1-120 μm). For this purpose, 0.7 mL of the NanoRelease dispersion was filled up to 500 mL with ultrapure water. For sensor protection the sample was filtered with a 190 μm pre-filter (nylon, Rotert). The measurement was performed with 200 mL of the sample. Data evaluation was performed with C.A.R. Lab. Duplicate samples were measured and values for blank measurements were subtracted.
- 2) Analytical ultracentrifugation (AUC) was used to quantify the mass of released nanoplastics from 20-999 nm: The AUC-Beckman XL centrifuge is equipped with an interference optical system synchronized to the centrifugal rotation, so that the colloidal sedimentation profile during centrifugation is monitored over time. By adjusting the centrifugation speed, the mass concentration and particle size distribution were determined in three overlapping size intervals of 10-150 nm (12 000 rpm $\hat{=}$ 10 500 rcf), 40-800 nm (3 000 rpm $\hat{=}$ 650 rcf) and 300-5000 nm (1 000 rpm $\hat{=}$ 70 rcf); with 3 hours centrifugation time each. For data evaluation of the absorption profiles (resolved in time and radius) SedFit v14.0 was used with the corresponding polymer density. Duplicate samples were measured and values for blank measurements were subtracted.
- 3) Part of the solution was filtered < 0.02 μm to assess the release of water-soluble non-particulate organics (DOC) via TOC measurements: the filtered NanoRelease sample was diluted with ultrapure water with dilution factors of 1:10 and 1:20 and total carbon (sample combusted catalytically on a Pt/Al₂O₃ catalyst in an oxygen stream at ca. 680 °C) and total inorganic carbon (sample acidified with 25 wt.-% phosphoric acid) were quantified as CO₂ via NDIR detection (Shimadzu TOC-L). DOC was calculated as the difference between total carbon and total inorganic carbon. Duplicate samples were measured.

1.2.1.3 Results

1.2.1.3.1 *Cutting/milling activities (Powder characterization)*

Two powders involved in Reference and SSbD#1 routes are characterized in this section. The first one is the fossil-based PU powder obtained by milling operation (performed by Indresmat) and the second is the impregnated PU powder after CEA vitrimer additives addition process developed by CEA (PU_{fb} and $Vit.PU_{fb}$ cf. Figure 2). As presented in Figure 6, the visual aspect of the powders is similar, apart from a noticeably more pronounced yellow colour for the impregnated PU powder.

Figure 6. Visual aspect of PU_{fb} and $Vit.PU_{fb}$ powders

Morphological characterization

Morphological characterization of the individual particles constituting the powder materials was performed by feSEM. Representative images obtained for PU_{fb} and $Vit.PU_{fb}$ powders are presented in Figure 7. For both powders, similar morphological features are revealed with predominantly micron-sized angular chips, typically observed upon abrasion/cutting/shredding processes. Qualitatively, one can sense smaller particle size in the case of PU_{fb} powder (with the presence of a larger number of sub-micron sized particles).

Figure 7. feSEM images of particles constituting the PU_{fb} and $Vit.PU_{fb}$ powders

To get more quantitative information on the particle size of the powders, automated optical microscopy acquisition and image analysis have been performed. The results are reported in Figure 8. It clearly confirms the feSEM observations, with a mean diameter centred at approximately 15 μm for the PU_{fb} powder and increased up to 45 μm in the case of the $Vit.PU_{fb}$ powder.

PSD - Fossil-based PU powder

PSD - Vitrimerized fossil-based PU powder

	PU powder	Impregnated PU powder
CE Diameter Minimum (μm)	2.1	2.1
CE Diameter Maximum (μm)	396.1	425.1
CE Diameter Mean (μm)	14.7	45.1
CE Diameter STDV (μm)	21.1	39.5
CE Diameter D[n, 0.1] (μm)	2.7	5.3
CE Diameter D[n, 0.5] (μm)	8.1	35.1
CE Diameter D[n, 0.9] (μm)	31.4	96.4

Figure 8. Number-based particle size distributions (PSD) for PU_{fb} and $Vit.PU_{fb}$ powders

Dustiness characterization

In addition to particle morphological and size characterization, the tendency of the PU powders to produce airborne particles when subjected to mechanical or aerodynamic solicitation was assessed by dustiness measurements. The experiment was carried out using the vortex shaker (VS) method, as described in the European standard EN 17199-5:2019. The following methodology enables:

- The measurement of dustiness in terms of respirable index mass fraction, i.e. mass-based dustiness index (DI_{RM})
- The measurement of dustiness in terms of respirable index number fraction, i.e. number-based dustiness index (DI_{RN})

The test protocol has two separate steps. The experimental set-up shown in Figure 9 is therefore used once with a downstream sampling line for the mass-based dustiness index in respirable fraction (Figure 9a), and once with another measurement line for the number-based dustiness index (Figure 9b).

The mass-based dustiness index in the respirable fraction (DI_{RM} in mg/kg), reported in milligrams of aerosol per kilogram of powder, is calculated by dividing the mass Δm_f collected by the respirable fraction sampling filter, by the mass M_0 of powder placed in the cylindrical tube:

$$DI_{RM} = \frac{\Delta m_f}{M_0} \cdot 10^6$$

The number-based dustiness index in the respirable fraction (DI_{RN} in #/mg), given in particles per milligram of powder, is calculated by dividing the total number of particles emitted over the duration of the vibrating period (i.e. 60 sec) (in particles) by the mass M_0 of powder placed in the cylindrical tube (in milligrams):

$$DI_{RN} = \frac{1}{M_0} \sum_0^{60} C_{CPC}(t) \cdot Q_{VS} \cdot \Delta t_{CPC} \cdot \frac{10^3}{60}$$

The average and the standard deviation (SD) of dustiness indexes presented in this report were calculated based on the average of three replicates per reference.

Figure 9. Dustiness measurement by vortex shaker method - Experimental setup principle

The dustiness indexes and bulk densities of PU_{fb} and $Vit.PU_{fb}$ powders are reported in table 1.

Table 1. Dustiness indexes for the two PU powders

	Fossil-based PU powder (PU_{fb})	Vitrimerized fossil-based PU powder ($Vit.PU_{fb}$)
Average Bulk Density, ρ_{bulk}	0.48 +/- 0.01 g/cm ³	0.41 +/- 0.01 g/cm ³
Average DI_{RM}	1 407 +/- 134 mg/kg	121 +/- 15 mg/kg
Average DI_{RN}	29 577 +/- 3 657 #/mg	4 948 +/- 213 #/mg

The decrease of DI_{RM} and DI_{RN} values by respectively over ten and five folds for the *Vit.PUR_{fb}* powder as compared to *PUR_{fb}*, clearly indicates that the impregnation process significantly reduces the dustiness of the initial PU powder.

To place the obtained dustiness values in a reference frame, a pre-normative classification is being built at CEA based on an internal database of over 100 substances. As illustrated in Figure 10, when reported on the categorization chart, the DI_{RM} and DI_{RN} values of *PUR_{fb}* and *Vit.PUR_{fb}* powders respectively place them in moderate and low categories.

Figure 10. Dustiness categorization chart (CEA internal reference frame)

The reduced dustiness of *Vit.PU_{fb}* powder is consistent with the previous observations revealing an increased particle mean diameter after impregnation process. Different hypotheses may be formulated to explain this increase. Indeed, during the impregnation, the finer fraction of the powder may be lost (specifically during solvent removal steps under fume cupboard for safe conditions) or phenomena of particles agglomeration/aggregation may occur.

1.2.1.3.2 Thermal compression step (Thermal degradation study)

Thermal stability study

To get preliminary information on the thermal behaviour of the PU_{fb} and $Vit.PU_{fb}$ powders, a thermal stability study by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, TA Instruments Q600 SDT) was carried out. The first analysis consists in monitoring the powder mass loss as a function of increasing temperature with a constant heating rate of 10 °C/min under N_2 . The thermographs of the powders are reported in Figure 11.

Figure 11. PU_{fb} and $Vit.PU_{fb}$ powders thermographs from 20°C to 1200°C

One can notice very similar mass loss profiles with a main degradation temperature at 328 °C (maximum value of the mass derivative), consistent with typical thermal degradation profile of PU (Jiao et al. 2013). Below 150 °C, a first mass loss step of approximately 1.5 wt. % for both PU_{fb} and $Vit.PU_{fb}$ is identified and corresponds to the loss of high volatility species from the polymer (adsorbed water or low molecular weight additives). Above 500 °C the mass stabilizes and reaches a pseudo-plateau. At this point a difference is observed between PU_{fb} and $Vit.PU_{fb}$ powders mass losses: at 600 °C, the $Vit.PU_{fb}$ remaining mass (residues) represents 91.5 % of PU_{fb} remaining mass (91.0 % at 800 °C). This observation may be considered as an indirect validation that the $Vit.PU_{fb}$ comprises approximately 10 wt. % of additives (THEED 5 wt. % and Cystamine 5 wt. %) which are integrally evaporated/degraded at 600°C.

To get more information on the thermal stability of the impregnated powder during the thermal compression step, a specific protocol has been implemented on the TGA. It consists in increasing the temperature at a pace of 10 °C/min up to 200 °C followed by a steady step of 2 h. The results are presented in Figure 12. The analysis of the thermographs shows that, in the process conditions of the thermal compression (i.e. 30 min at 200 °C), both PU_{fb} and $Vit.PU_{fb}$ powders undergo significant mass loss. This mass loss is more pronounced for $Vit.PU_{fb}$ powder, and the contribution of the loss of vitrimerization additives can be calculated $(1 - \text{wt. \%}(Vit.PU_{fb}) / \text{wt. \%}(PU_{fb}))$ in the range of 3 wt. %. This observation points out that about a third of the total amount of additives introduced during impregnation process of the powder could be lost during thermal compression process.

Figure 12. PU_{fb} (solid orange line) and $Vit.PU_{fb}$ (dotted orange line) powders thermographs at 200°C and corresponding mass losses

Then, the thermal stability of the additives (THEED and cystamine) and the impregnation solvent (anisole) was assessed with the TGA specific protocol described above for PU_{fb} and $Vit.PU_{fb}$ powders (Figure 13). Anisole and cystamine appear quite sensitive to temperature, anisole being totally evaporated at around 100 °C and cystamine loses between 80 and 90 % of its mass after 30 min at 200 °C. The THEED is more stable at 200 °C, and presents a mass loss below 10 % after 30 min. Furthermore, the cystamine thermograph shows a very high mass loss rate from ~ 150 °C followed by a strong reduction when reaching temperatures around 200 °C. One can also notice that the mass loss rate during the plateau is lower for cystamine than for THEED contrary to their expected vaporization with boiling points at 265 °C and 327 °C, respectively. Therefore, cystamine appears to be thermally unstable and be decomposed at temperature close to 200°C. In conclusion, the more pronounced mass loss for $Vit.PU_{fb}$ powder (~3 wt. %) is most probably due to the evaporation/degradation of cystamine and potentially the evaporation of residual solvent.

Figure 13. Anisole (dashed orange line), cystamine (densely orange dashed line) and THEED (solid orange line) thermographs at 200°C

VOCs & SVOCs emission assessment

Considering the significant mass loss (few wt. %) measured by TGA at the compression temperature, the VOCs & lighter SVOCs were characterized from a very low powder amount by a direct TD-GCMS/FID analysis (TD Ultra-xr Unity series 2 from Markes and GC5975C VL MSD from Agilent Technologies). To achieve this goal, a polymer powder sample (about 5 mg) is directly introduced into an empty tube dedicated for a TD-GCMS/FID analysis. Thermal desorption conditions of the tube under a controlled flow were defined to reach and maintain the polymer powder at 200 °C (Figure 14). The final temperature is reached in less 2 min for a total heating time of 5 min where the emitted VOCs & SVOCs in the flow are then injected for GC-MS/FID analysis. This procedure was repeated once during 10 min for each material, showing that more than 90 % of the total VOCs was released during the first 5 min step.

Figure 14. Temperature conditions of the TD of the polymer powder during direct TD-GCMS/FID analysis

First, release rates of Total VOC (TVOC) evaluated at 200 °C during 5+10 min are quite significant, 2.5 wt. % and 4.3 wt. %, respectively for the Fossil-based powder and the Vitrimized Fossil-based powder (Figure 15). Considering the semi-quantification performed by FID with a toluene calibration and the experimental conditions differences (strong vs slow temperature gradients), these results are in the same order of magnitude than those measured by TGA. In particular, the difference of released VOCs between the 2 materials (1.8 wt. %) appears in very good agreement with the mass loss difference for 15 min at 200 °C (~ 1.5-2 wt. %; cf. Figure 12-right) revealing that additional outgassing from vitrimerized PU is well characterized as VOCs.

Regarding the nature of the emitted compounds (Table 2), the main VOCs were identified leading to a recovery of ~ 95 % of the TVOC mass. The release from the fossil-based PU is mainly marked by the emission of well-known additives namely:

A flame retardant, the Tris(1-chloro-2-propyl)phosphate (TCPP) and its 3 isomers representing 88 % of the total release. Very low amounts of 1,2-dichloropropane are detected, this organochlorine compound being likely a TCPP degradation product.

- Significant amounts of plasticizers, especially dioctyl phthalate (DOP; ~ 7 %) are also measured.
- Slight amounts of triethylenediamine, a well-known PU catalyst.

The vitrimerized fossil-based PU also outgasses the TCPP flame retardant and phthalates but DOP is detected in much lower amounts. This strong decrease could be related to the use of anisole solvent for impregnation treatment of the powder, this latter being able to extract additives. Additionally, specific compounds directly linked to the impregnation process were detected:

- Very large amount of anisole, the solvent used for THEED and cystamine impregnation,
- Several sulphurous compounds which are identified, in regard to their structures, as by-products of cystamine, namely: ethylene sulfide; 2-methyl- and 2-ethyl-thiazolidine and 2 larger unidentified S-compounds. These results confirm that cystamine is decomposed at temperature close to 200 °C in agreement with its previous TGA thermograph behaviour.

Finally, the thermal compression step leads to very significant releases of initial additives present in the fossil based PU powder, in particular TCPP flame retardant (2.2 wt. %) as illustrated in Figure 15. Regarding the vitrimerized PU powder, the most pronounced release rate is mainly due to anisole evaporation (1.6 wt. %), this one being not fully eliminated after impregnation, and by significant emission of cystamine by-products (0.26 wt. %). One can notice, that no THEED or related degradation products were detected.

Table 2. Identification and semi-quantification of organic compounds released at 200°C by Fossil-based PU powder and Vitrimerized Fossil-based PU powder by TD-GC-MS/FID (5+10 min TD consecutives steps; in mg equivalent toluene / g of powder)

	Fossil-based powder		Vitri. Fossil-based powder		compounds origin / role
	mg/g	part (%)	mg/g	part (%)	
Ethylene sulfide (Thiirane)	-	-	0,18	0,43%	cystamine degradation
Propane, 1,2-dichloro	0,04	0,15%	0,01	0,03%	TCPP degradation
Triethylenediamine	0,15	0,62%	-	-	PU catalyst
Ethanol, 2-chloro-	-	-	0,05	0,11%	TCPP degradation
Anisole	-	-	16,3	38%	impregnation solvent
Thiazolidine, 2-methyl-	-	-	1,0	2,3%	cystamine degradation
Thiazolidine, 2-ethyl-	-	-	0,07	0,17%	cystamine degradation
Dipropylene glycol	-	-	0,05	0,11%	
phénol	-	-	0,02	0,05%	solvent by-product
S-compound #1 (m/z: 103 (C ₄ H ₉ NS ⁺), 60 (CH ₂ CHS ⁺ H), 45 (CHS ⁺))	-	-	0,18	0,43%	cystamine degradation
S-compound #2 (m/z 60, 172, 113, 45, 144)	-	-	1,2	2,9%	cystamine degradation
TCPP - Tris(1-chloro-2-propyl)phosphate	17,1	69%	17,6	41%	flame retardant
TCPP isomer-1 : Bis(1-chloro-2-propyl)(3-chloro-1-propyl)phosphate	4,2	17%	3,6	8,5%	flame retardant
TCPP isomer-2 : Bis(3-chloro-1-propyl)(1-chloro-2-propyl)phosphate	0,43	1,7%	0,31	0,72%	flame retardant
TCPP isomer-3 : Tris(3-chloropropyl) phosphate	0,02	0,10%	-	-	flame retardant
DiButylPhthalate (DBP)	0,02	0,08%	0,09	0,22%	plasticizer
DiocetylPhthalate (DOP)	1,7	6,9%	0,05	0,13%	plasticizer
Identified VOCs	23,7	95%	40,7	96%	
Total VOCs	25,0	100%	42,5	100%	

Figure 15. Comparison of the release rates of main compounds between PU_{fb} and Vit.PU_{fb} powders

1.2.1.3.3 Consumer use (Environmental weathering & release)

As described in section 1.2.1.2, potential release during consumer use phase was assessed through combined weathering and leaching protocols.

Visual check and color change assessment

Figure 16 reports examples of PU specimens exposed to different UV doses. By simple visual observation, weathering protocol has an impact for all PU References, with a darkening of the exposed surface (even for the initially darker brown references).

Figure 16. Pictures of pristine and aged specimens, associated with the corresponding UV dose

In order to quantify the color change, colorimetry analysis was performed. The color differences between pristine and aged specimens (ΔE) were calculated in L*a*b* (CIE) coordinates, with the following formula:

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{dL^*{}^2 + da^*{}^2 + db^*{}^2}$$

Color differences for Reference, SSbD#0, SSbD#1 and SSbD#2 routes are summarized in Figure 17. For all specimens, a color change is revealed, with no major evolution between 500 h and 1000 h UV exposure. SSbD#1 (vitrimerized dense fossil-based PU) is the darkest colored specimen, and its color is only little altered by the irradiance process. The other specimens show more pronounced color changes, particularly in their foam versions.

Figure 17. Total colour difference ΔE (in CIE color space) for PUs specimens exposed to 500 h and 1000 h artificial weathering

The initial step of the approach is to characterize the effect of weathering on PU materials properties. With this aim, surface morphology and chemical changes were studied (by feSEM and ATR-FTIR) and impacts on mechanical properties were evaluated (by tensile and abrasion testing).

Surface morphological characterization

To evaluate the impact of UV exposure on surface topology, feSEM imaging was performed on pristine and aged specimen surfaces. Figure 18 provides an overview of the images obtained with magnification ranging from x250 to x10000 (additional images are provided in Appendix). For the foam samples, their manufacturing process implies that the porosity is not uniform on the initial bulk specimen, with external surfaces much denser than the inner material. To take this inhomogeneity into account, different specimens were cut out of the foam materials and aged: some exposing the denser external surface and others the foamy inner surface perpendicularly to the UV radiation source. To illustrate this subtlety, Figure 18 reports images obtained on foamy surface (identified as CROSS SECTION in the figure) of bio-based PUs (SSbD#0 and SSbD#2 routes) exposed to UV. From the cross-sectional low-magnification images, information on pores may be retrieved: the pore structure is similar for SSbD#0 and SSbD#2 routes specimens, presenting spherical shapes and diameters ranging from 50 to 500 μm (in average slightly larger pores for SSbD#0 route samples).

For all references assessed morphology changes are reported, with the tendency of smoothness decrease, irregularities formation and pores cracking in the case of foam materials. More specifically, discrepancies may be pointed out between 'regular' PU specimens (Reference & SSbD#0 routes) and their vitrimer counterparts (SSbD#1 and SSbD#2 routes):

- In the case of vitrimer fossil-based PU (SSbD#1 route): after 250 h UV exposure, images show the formation of dendrite-like structures, evolving to a qualitatively much more eroded surface as compared to Reference route samples at 1000 h.
- In the case of vitrimer bio-based PU (SSbD#2 route): a large population of (sub)micron sized objects (solid particles or droplets) uniformly covered the specimen surfaces after 1000 h UV exposure, which was not observed for the SSbD#0 route samples.

Figure 18. feSEM surface analysis of the different samples at t_0 and after 1000h of aging (magnification factor from 250 to 10000)

The above observations clearly indicate a specific sensitivity of vitrimer PUs to the implemented combination of UV dose, temperature and humidity level and could reflect the migration and/or specific degradation of vitrimer additives or ability to nano/micro plastic release upon weathering.

Surface chemical characterization

The surface chemical changes upon weathering were monitored by ATR-FTIR. To enable band intensity comparison, all spectra were normalized to the polymethylene diphenyl diisocyanate (PMDI) aromatic ring deformation (aromatic $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ vibration) at 1598 cm^{-1} , which is a recognized approach in the literature (Kuka et al. 2023; Jakubowicz 2017).

Non-vitrimer fossil-based & bio-based PU

At first, the Reference and SSbD#0 routes PU specimens (dense and foam) were analyzed prior to UV exposure (pristine samples). The corresponding IR spectra are reported in Figure 19 together with the identification of the major bands. The four spectra are very similar, with identified bands characteristic of MDI-based polyurethanes. The only noticeable difference between fossil-based (Reference route) and bio-based (SSbD#0 route) PUs is the presence of 1375 cm^{-1} and 1068 cm^{-1} bands attributed to ether groups for the fossil-based PU. This observation corroborates the composition information provided by Indresmat stating that the fossil-based PU is synthesized from ether-based polyol whereas the bio-based PU is made out of a mix of ester-based polyols. One can additionally notice that unreacted isocyanate functions at 2276 cm^{-1} are present in larger amounts for the dense versions of the PUs.

Figure 19. ATR-FTIR spectra with bands identification for pristine (t_0) fossil-based and bio-based PU (dense & foam specimens)

The next step consists in tracking spectra changes as a function of weathering time. To do so, specimen surfaces have been characterized by ATR-FTIR after UV exposure time of 250 h, 500 h and 1000 h for Reference and SSbD#0 routes PU specimens. The overall trend is similar for all references, with the absorbance decrease of the majority of the bands happening predominantly during the first 250 h of exposure (Figure 20).

Figure 20. ATR-FTIR spectra for fossil-based and bio-based PU (dense & foam specimens) for different UV irradiation time

To go in more details in the analysis of the band absorbance changes, a convenient graphical representation is to plot a difference spectrum obtained by subtracting the initial spectrum to the spectrum obtained at a given exposure time ($A(t_0) - A(t)$). This way, the absorbance values below zero correspond to loss species and the absorbance values above zero can be attributed to formed species.

An example of this representation is presented in Figure 21 for the dense specimen of fossil-based PU. The analysis of this difference spectra enabled us to correlate bands evolution to aromatic PU degradation mechanisms widely described and accepted in the literature. Those mechanisms may be divided in two categories:

- Degradation due to the urethane functions (hard segment) reactivity, including three pathways potentially leading to the formation of:
 - Aromatic primary amines (by photo-Fries type rearrangement)
 - Diquinone imide species
 - Benzoic acid derivatives (chain scission)
- Chain scission due to the oxidation of the soft segments (polyether/polyester), leading to formic acid ester like species

It is worth mentioning here that some of the products deriving from the hard segment degradation are identified in the literature to be responsible for the yellowing of the PU foam (Rosu, Rosu, and Cascaval 2009).

The same approach has been followed for all the non-vitrimer fossil-based and bio-based PU (dense & foam) and markers of identical degradation mechanisms were identified (not presented here).

Figure 21. ATR-FTIR spectra and associated photo-degradation mechanisms found in the literature for dense fossil-based PU (Wilhelm, Rivaton, and Gardette 1998; Dannoux et al. 2008).

To get insight on the degradation kinetics, the relative absorbance of the main bands identified and attributed to urethane linkage activity or soft segment degradation were plotted as a function of UV exposure time. Results are reported in Figure 22j **Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** for fossil-based and bio-based PU (dense and foam). It shows that most of the degradation occurs within the first 500h, with no major absorbance changes between 500h and 1000h exposure time. Overall, the degradation rates are similar for all specimens, with maybe a slightly more pronounced degradation for the fossil-based (ether) soft segments.

Figure 22. Relative absorbance changes for urethane linkage and soft segment degradation

Vitrimerized fossil-based and bio-based PU

Similarly, the vitrimer versions of PU (SSbD#1 and SSbD#2 routes) were assessed by ATR-FTIR upon UV exposure. The pristine specimens (before weathering) IR spectra are presented in Figure 23 which depicts the vitrimer PU results compared with their non-vitrimer counterparts. Even though vitrimer additives were integrated in substantial amount (10 wt. %), no noticeable change was detected on ATR-FTIR signatures between pristine (fossil & bio-based) PUs and their vitrimer counterparts.

Figure 23. Comparison between pristine non-vitrimer and vitrimer PUs ATR-FTIR spectra

Nevertheless, when tracking spectra changes as a function of weathering time (Figure 24), some discrepancies arise (specifically in the 600 – 1600 cm^{-1} region) between vitrimer and non-vitrimer PUs. For both fossil and bio-based vitrimer PUs a series of bands heighen, noticeably at 614 cm^{-1} , between 1000 cm^{-1} and 1200 cm^{-1} and at 1416 cm^{-1} .

Figure 24. ATR-FTIR spectra for fossil-based and bio-based PU (non-vitrimer & vitrimer specimens) for different UV irradiation time

A more in-depth analysis of these spectral changes upon weathering may be performed by plotting the difference of the subtracted ($A_{1000h} - A_{t0}$) spectra for vitrimer and non-vitrimer PUs. A graphical illustration of this approach is presented in Figure 25. The obtained spectra correspond to the specific signature of the additional degradation products arising on the aged vitrimer PUs. For both fossil-based and bio-based PU vitrimers, the same signature is revealed, with main peaks at 3220, 1416, 1090 and 1032 cm^{-1} – which could potentially correspond to alcohol functions and/or sulfoxides functional groups. It is very likely that the specific by-products evidenced for the PU vitrimers result from the reactivity of the disulphide bound present in both fossil and bio-based vitrimer formulations (cystamine & HEDS).

Figure 25. Difference of the subtracted ATR-FTIR spectra for fossil-based (in black) and bio-based (in red) PU vitrimers

Mechanical properties (tensile testing)

To assess the mechanical properties of the various PU References and their evolution upon ageing, tensile testing has been carried out on 1.5-2 mm thick by 4 mm large specimens. A minimum of 5 replicates have been tested for each Reference and exposure time. Tensile stress-strain curves and associated Young's modulus, stress at break and strain at break are respectively reported in Figure 26 and Figure 27.

Before ageing, the bio-based PUs present lower mechanical properties than the fossil-based PUs: for instance, the dense bio-based PU exhibits a Young's modulus of 0.95+/-0.07 GPa and a strain at break of 4.7+/-0.8 % as compared to 1.60+/-0.09 GPa and 7.3+/-0.6 % for the dense fossil-based PU. As one can expect, the foamed References also present diminished mechanical properties as compared to the dense Reference. The Young's modulus of foamed specimens is reduced by approximately 65-75 % in comparison to dense References, which would theoretically correspond to the overall porosity level of the foam. Regarding the vitrimer References, in the case of fossil-based PU, the vitrimerization process leads to a slightly stiffer material (higher modulus) with a reduced strain at break. This lower ductility may be explained by the reprocessing step involving powder, leading to the potential presence of local defects and singularities (particles boundaries), which would promote fracture initiation and propagation. Since the vitrimer versions of the bio-based PU (dense & foam) have not endured yet a recycling loop including a powder state step, its mechanical properties are very similar to their non-vitrimer counterparts.

In the conditions tested, the impact of weathering on the mechanical properties of the fossil-based PUs appears very limited. Indeed, the fossil-based References did not exhibit any mechanical change apart from a slight decrease of the Young's modulus of the vitrimer PU. Comparatively, all the bio-based References suffered a more pronounced impact, becoming stiffer (Young's modulus increase) and more brittle (strain at break decrease).

Figure 26. Tensile stress-strain curves for pristine (t₀) and aged PU specimens

Figure 27. Young's Modulus, Stress at break and strain at break of pristine (t_0) and aged PU specimens

Wear resistance (Linear abrasion)

The influence of the ageing process to surface wear resistance was assessed by linear abrasion tests, which consist in a rubbing process of the surface using a linear abrader that can accommodate a wearaser collet holding abradant cylinders of various levels of abrasiveness (Figure 28). The chosen Calibrade H18 abradant is composed of silicon carbide embedded in a non-resilient vitrified clay binder for a medium-to-coarse abrasive action. The conditions applied are adapted from ECCA-T11 and ASTM D6279 standards. They have been implemented in an identical manner on all the specimens to allow ranking of their performances with regard to their ability to resist deterioration.

Figure 28. Linear abrasion setup

The weight loss after 500 cycles of the abrader head is provided in Figure 29. Despite a large standard deviation of the data, abrasion consequences are obviously more severe in the case of foam-type samples. Mechanical resistance to wear is lower for these porous structures. Notably, the weight loss of the vitrimer version of the bio-based foam material was significantly lower than that of its reference counterpart, which implies a likely better resistance of the former. Contrary to the results obtained from the tensile testing, where bio-based PU became stiffer and more brittle, there is no evidence of weight loss evolution with irradiation time, neither for fossil-based-, nor for bio-based PU specimens.

Figure 29. Surface weight losses after linear abrasion protocol

The powder collected from the abrasion tests was analyzed by TGA to investigate the possible changes in thermal stability of the PU materials after ageing. The thermal gradient was set at 5 °C/min to 1000 °C in nitrogen. For each specimen, three samples were tested: the pristine bulk material (small chunk), the powder from abrasion of the pristine specimen, and the abrasion powder of the corresponding sample after 1000 h of ageing. The thermal degradation profiles are displayed in Figure 30. In the graphs, the curves have been normalized to the total loss between ambient temperature and 1000 °C in order to disregard the residual mass at 1000 °C which includes both the material residue (8 - 14 %, in agreement with the results described above (see figure 11)) and a contribution of the abradant powder set free from the tool during the abrasion process. The profiles of fossil-based materials are similar to those in Figure 11 with a maximum weight loss between 300 °C and 330 °C. The profile of the bio-based materials is more complex reflecting a greater number of constituents, some of them displaying thermal stability higher than 400 °C. In all cases except the dense form of fossil-based PU, the ageing process induces a more rapid loss of weight at low temperatures (< 300 °C), which suggests a decrease of the thermal stability of the material, obviously induced by its photolysis during the ageing test. Conversely, the weight loss of 1000 h-powder is reduced at temperatures higher than 400 °C, which may be correlated to the mechanical results (stiffness and brittleness).

Figure 30. Thermal degradation of bulk and abrasion powder residues for fossil-based and bio-based specimens.

Analysis of the extractable compounds (Total extraction + GCMS & UPLC-tofMS)

To identify and quantify the total amount of extractable species present in the PU matrixes of the different routes, pristine and aged (1000 h) specimens were cryo-milled and the resulting powders were immersed in a solvent mix for a total extraction step. For this purpose, a given mass of PU is introduced in a 50/50 vol. mixture of methanol and toluene heated at 80°C under reflux and stirred for 24 h. The solvent mix is then filtered (PTFE 0.22 µm) and diluted for subsequent UPLC-tofMS and GCMS analysis. The objective of this extraction protocol is to retrieve all the extractable species of the PU powder in the solvent mix.

The analysis of the extracted species was performed on a UPLC-tofMS (PerkinElmer ALTUS A-30 system) equipped with Brownlee Analytical DBC18 column and a Perkin Axion TOF 2 APCI (+/-) detector. The analytical principle relies on the separation of the dissolved organic species through the column, followed by their ionization and detection by the tof-MS detector. The UPLC-tofMS signal was calibrated with an internal standard (ISTD) protocol using 3,3',5,5'-tetra-ter-butylidiphenoquinone leading then to semi-quantitative results.

Detected species are identified with four levels of certainty:

- *Unknown*: insufficient data – unidentified chemical compound
- *Tentative*: data consistent with a molecule class or molecular mass range
- *Confident*: sufficient data to identify a compound based on literature data or NIST database
- *Confirmed*: sufficient data to identify a compound based on literature data or NIST database and confirmed by the internal data of the specific compound

In parallel, extracted molecules with lower molecular weights (organic volatile and semi-volatile compounds – VOCs & SVOCs) were analyzed by GCMS (PerkinElmer GC Clarus 680 equipped with Elite-5MS column coupled with PerkinElmer MS Clarus 600T). A semi-quantification analysis is then obtained, the GC-MS response being calibrated with an internal standard (ISTD) protocol using 2-fluorobiphenyl.

UPLC-tofMS results

UPLC-tofMS analysis revealed the presence of a broad range of molecules, which were sorted in the following categories:

- Chlorinated organophosphate **flame retardant** - *Confident*
Comprising tris-(2-chloroisopropyl)phosphate (TCPP) and its derivatives
- Diamines (**PU catalysts**) - *Tentative*
Comprising mainly triethylenediamine and benzenamine 4,4'-methylenebis-, and their fragments
- Polypropylene Glycol (**PPG**) compounds - *Tentative*
- Bio-based **polyol-fatty acids ester-based fragments** - *Tentative*
Comprising the triol trimethylolpropane (TMP) and C₁₈-fatty acids ester (including ricinoleic acid as major constituent)
- **Other** - *unknown*
Comprising all the unidentified species

Figure 31 presents the Total organic compounds extracted and Figure 32 summarizes the mass contents (in $\mu\text{g/g}$) obtained for each category of compounds, before and after photo-ageing, for different bio-based and fossil-based PU References.

Figure 31. Comparison of the total rate of extracted organic compounds in fossil-based and bio-based PU using the total extraction protocol - UPLC-tofMS

Figure 32. Semi-quantitative analysis by UPLC-tofMS of extractable compounds for total extraction protocol

First of all, a global comparison of the whole organic compounds extracted highlights that fossil-based materials present quite higher extraction rates than bio-based PU. However, different trends appear depending on the compound considered. One can also notice that unidentified compounds were mostly observed for vitrimerized dense fossil-based PU without any relation with the vitrimerization additives (THEED, cystamine) or solvent used (anisole).

TCPP flame retardant was only detected in fossil-based PU samples, this additive or other flame retardant additives being absent of the bio-based PU formulation. Its extraction rates were the highest and relatively similar except for the vitrimerized fossil-based PU which presents significantly decreased rates. This trend is likely linked to losses during the thermal compression promoted by the material

modifications induced by the vitrimerization since compressed fossil-based PU (w/o vitrimerization additives) does not present such behaviour. Regarding extraction rates after photo-aging, a clear decrease was showed implying that some TCPP release occurred over time.

Regarding diamines, the triethylenediamine (TEDA), likely present as PU catalyst in the formulation, was only detected in fossil-based PU samples. Furthermore, benzenamine, 4,4'-methylene-bis was detected in case of thermo-compressed materials (compressed and vitrimerized fossil-based PU), likely in relationship with a thermal degradation. This compound was also extracted in all bio-based PU specimens. Finally, no clear influence of the aging was evidenced on the extraction levels of diamines.

Concerning PPGs, these compounds were detected on foam PU (fossil-based and bio-based) at relatively low concentrations and seems to decrease with ageing. Higher extraction rates were obtained in compressed and vitrimerized fossil-based PU showing that the thermo-compression step seems to promote the formation of PPG residues likely due to ether-based polyols thermal degradation.

Finally, fragments of (TMP triol-C₁₈ fatty acids)-ester were measured in case of bio-based PU in straight link with the use of ester-based castor oil derivates as polyols source in their formulation. This shows that a part did not fully react in the polymerization process (between isocyanate and hydroxyl group). Extraction rates were still significantly higher for vitrimerized bio-based PU, suggesting a less efficient polymerization yield related to the addition of HEDS in the PU formulation.

GC-MS results

For fossil-based materials, GC-MS analysis was focused on foam PU and vitrimerized dense PU, these polymers being the more relevant in regard with the final development of a sustainable PU.

Regarding the total extraction rates of organic compounds, fossil-based PUs present significantly higher mass contents in organic compounds than bio-based PUs as illustrated by Figure 33. Contrary to UPLC-tofMS, only PPG residues were detected simultaneously from fossil-based and bio-based PUs (GCMS addresses the analysis of VOCs and lighter SVOCs in complement to UPLC-tofMS) and very different analytical signatures were obtained. Figure 34 presents mass rates (in µg/g) obtained for each main compounds or species families determined before and after photo-ageing for the different materials.

Figure 33. Comparison of the total rate of extracted organic compounds in fossil-based and bio-based PU using the total extraction protocol-GCMS

In case of fossil-based materials, the initial foam PU showed huge amounts of TCPP flame retardant (1.3 wt. %) and low levels of triethylenediamine and propylene carbonate (main species of PPG family group). The vitrimerized dense PU presents a significant but lower content of TCPP (0.27 wt. %) highlighting the strong decrease of this additive, likely related to vitrimerization process (solvent impregnation, thermal compression). Moreover, this latter material was characterized by the extraction of very specific species due to the vitrimerization process, namely significant contents of residual anisole (impregnation solvent) and 2 sulphurous-compounds not formally identified (named S-compounds #1 and #2) but corresponding to cystamine by-products. One can notice that these 2 S-compounds have been already detected during the thermal degradation study by TD-GC-MS/FID (cf. § 1.2.1.3.2). Also, PPG residues and benzenamide, 4,4'-methylene-bis were detected in vitrimerized fossil based materials likely due to thermal degradation during compression.

Regarding the effect of the photo-ageing on extraction contents, results for fossil-based PU confirmed the expected decrease of extractable compounds related to their probable release over time. Surprisingly, no effect was observed for the vitrimerized dense PU, the extractable contents staying very similar after photo-ageing (contrary to previous UPLC-tofMS results).

Figure 34. Semi-quantitative analysis by GC-MS of extractable compounds for total extraction protocol.

Regarding bio-based materials, both initial foam and vitrimerized foam PU presented common extractable species such as fragments of probable catalysts, the bis-(2-(Dimethylamino)ethyl) ether, and fragments of incomplete polymerization residues, such as methylene diphenyldiisocyanate (MDI); TMP & C₁₈-fatty acids methyl esters. These latter were likely initially present as acids but derivated in methyl ester during extraction protocol in methanol/toluene mixture. Moreover, the breakdown of the different C₁₈-acids well corresponds to species originated from castor oil (major specie is ricinoleic acid). One can remark that their concentrations are lower for the vitrimerized-forms suggesting a better polymerization reaction (contrary to ToF-MS results).

Initial bio-based PU showed additionally contents of cardanol-family compounds (known as antioxidant, plasticizer) and PPG fragments whereas the HEDS additive was specifically detected in the vitrimerized foam.

Finally, the photo-ageing led to a decrease of the extractable compounds over time indicating a potential VOC release and/or a complementary polymerization reaction, especially for MDI, fatty acids residues and HEDS. Moreover, specific oxygenated compounds (C₈- ketone and alcohol) were only

extracted after photo-ageing protocol likely characterizing photo-induced cleavage and oxidation of some polymer chains.

Water-dissolved species lixiviation and airborne compounds release assessment in use conditions

Airborne organic compounds release assessment by TD-GC-MS/FID

Release of organic compounds present in a polymer matrix (e.g., additives, degradation products, residues of solvent, monomer) without being strongly bound to the polymer backbone can occur at ambient temperature. This process is generally temperature-dependent (Beel et al. 2023; Noguchi and Yamasaki 2020), related to the molecule properties (e.g., size, polarity, diffusion coefficient) and to the polymer-chain movements, and is governed by an Arrhenius-like law where the release rate, r , can be expressed as:

$$r = A \cdot \exp(-E_a / RT) , \text{ where:}$$

A : pre-exponential constant (independent of the temperature) (in $\mu\text{g/g}$ or $\mu\text{g/m}^2$)

E_a : activation energy for emission (J)

R : universal gas constant ($\text{J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$)

T : temperature (K)

At ambient temperature, outgassing can be low and then difficult to easy and rapidly characterized from very low amounts of material. Thus, in order to evaluate airborne release of VOCs and lighter SVOCs by the different PU materials during their usage conditions, a specific methodology was implemented. The principle is based on the measurement of the outgassed compounds at several temperatures, for instance from 50 °C up to 90 °C, leading to characterize the Arrhenius-like behavior (linear law in Log scale) of a released specie and allowing then to extrapolate its emission rate at a lower temperature representative of the use case, as illustrated in Figure 35 left.

Figure 35. Principle of the VOC release rate determination at low temperature (left) and description of the desorption experimental set-up used (right)

By this approach, different temperature-dependent results could be obtained characterizing different behaviours:

- an Arrhenius-like behaviour is showed over the whole tested temperatures range meaning that a release at lower use temperatures occurs,
- an Arrhenius-like behaviour is observed for higher tested temperatures indicating that the release process is thermally activated and required a threshold temperature (related to polymer chain movement, compound-polymer interactions...) and that no outgassing happens at low / use temperature.
- A detection of compounds at higher temperature is showed but without an Arrhenius-like behaviour. This complex case can be due to more complex release kinetic and/or to release due to thermal degradation process induced at these temperatures.

The 2 latter cases give interesting data about the thermal stability of the materials but only the former behaviour reveals an airborne release in use conditions.

Concretely, the method implemented consists in putting a small polymer sample (~0.5g) inside a stainless steel chamber (Markes μ -CTE™ 250 from) heated at different defined temperatures and flushed by a known clean nitrogen flow (~60-80 ml/min) (Figure 35-right). At the chamber outlet vent, the N₂ flow goes through an adsorbent tube (Markes Universal® tube) cooled by a small fan where the emitted VOCs and SVOCs are then trapped. More precisely, for each increasing temperature (typically 50, 60, 70, 80, 90 °C), a 30 min sampling is performed after a 10 min stabilization time of the material at the tested temperature. Then, the subsequent TD-GC-MS/FID analysis of the tubes (TD Ultra-xr Unity series 2 from Markes and GC5975C VL MSD from Agilent Technologies) allows the identification (by MS) and quantification (by FID using a toluene calibration) of trapped VOCs and SVOCs at different temperatures. The analytical method is derived from US-EPA Method TO-17 and allows the determination of VOCs (C₃ to C_{12/14}) and lighter SVOCs (C_{12/14} to C₂₄ in reference to the volatility of the n-alkane family).

Both Pristine and 1000 h photo-aged samples of the various fossil-based and bio-based PUs were characterized in order to evaluate release over time. First of all, the total organic compounds release rate depending on the temperature is compared in order to have a behavior overview of the different materials. Then, the individual emitted compounds will be presented and discussed.

In case of fossil-based PUs, Figure 36 shows that the total VOCs release rates depending on temperature respect well the expected Arrhenius law. Measurements were repeated in case of the Foam PU and Vitrimerized dense PU, showing relatively similar results. Very different emission rates were observed, showing that materials can be ranked in terms of increasing released materials as: **dense < thermo-compressed < foam < vitrimerized dense**. Therefore, the vitrimerization process leads to significant stronger release likely related to the polymer modifications. Higher outgassing rates from Foam and Compressed PU versus Dense PU can be explained respectively by higher porosity/surface exchange and by thermal degradation products produced during the thermo-compression process.

Figure 36. Arrhenius plots for experimental release rates (in $\mu\text{g/g}$) of Total organic compounds emitted from pristine and 1000h-photoaged fossil-based materials – 50°C - 90°C temperature range.

Regarding the individual organic compounds, numerous species were detected and most of them are released following an Arrhenius temperature-dependence meaning that an outgassing occurs and can be extrapolated at low temperature (as illustrated in Figure 37-a and Figure 38-a respectively for Foam PU and Vitrimerized dense fossil-based PU). However, some compounds are detected only at higher temperature or with non-Arrhenius behaviour (cf. Figure 37-b and Figure 38-b). Among these latter ones, ethyleneglycol ether-compounds for initial fossil-based materials or propylene glycol ether-compounds, phenol and methoxy-phenols (as possible anisole derivatives) are likely oxidation/degradation compounds induced by increased temperatures.

Figure 37. Arrhenius plots for experimental release rates (in $\mu\text{g/g}$) of main organic compounds emitted from Foam fossil-based PU: compounds respecting (a) and not respecting (b) the Arrhenius-type behaviour. 50°C - 90°C temperature range

Figure 38. Arrhenius plots for experimental release rates (in $\mu\text{g/g}$) of main organic compounds emitted from Vitrimized dense fossil-based PU: compounds respecting (a) and not respecting (b) the Arrhenius-type behaviour. 50°C - 90°C temperature range

Figure 39 gives the main compounds released in ambient conditions with their emission rates extrapolated at 40 °C and also those experimentally determined at 80 °C. Among these species, different groups of species or main compounds can be considered:

- TCPP flame retardant and its isomers, emitted by all materials but in higher contents by foam and compressed PU,
- TCPP by-products, namely C₃-organochlorine compounds (1-chloro-1-propene; 1-chloro-2-propanol; 1,2-dichloropropane...) likely related to chloro-isopropyl chains of the TCPP. This group is emitted by Compressed and Vitrimized materials showing that the 200 °C-compression process induced the thermal degradation of the flame retardant.
- Anisole (impregnation solvent), detected only for the Vitrimized dense PU in very large levels
- Cystamine vitrimerization agent by-products (S-compounds #1 and #2), only detected for the vitrimerized dense PU.
- Propylenecarbonate and propyleneglycol, likely related to a degradation process and released by Foam PU and Vitrimized PU.

These groups/compounds are also gathered and compared for the different fossil-fuel materials in the histograms presented in Figure 40. One can also emphasize the coherence of these results in regards with the polymer formulation and also their full agreement with the previous thermal study of the compression step.

After a 1000 h photo-aging, Arrhenius plots of TVOC release rates for the different materials always show a linear behaviour. However, a significant decrease is highlighted for Vitrimized dense PU and for Foam PU while Compressed PU and Dense PU lead to a relatively higher emission.

Concerning the nature of the outgassed species, same main compounds or groups of compounds are observed and globally the release rates are distinctly reduced in direct relationship with a depletion of the species in the polymer matrix. For instance, TCPP emission rate reached very low amounts, and anisole was decreased by more than a factor 3. Nevertheless, an additional group consisting of small oxygenated molecules (acetaldehyde, acetone, acetic acid) were significantly detected whatever the aged PU. Their release is likely due to an (photo-) oxidation process of the polymer.

compounds	Dense Fossil-based PU		Foam Fossil-based PU		Compressed Fossil-based PU		Vitrimer Dense Fossil-based PU		
	at 40°C	at 90°C	at 40°C	at 80°C	at 40°C	at 80°C	at 40°C	at 80°C	
	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	
TVOC	1,7	1,2	188	6,5	56	3,3	369	85	TVOC
2-chloro-1-Propene							n.a.	0,02	T CPP-by-product
1-chloro-1-Propene					0,68	0,02	1,4	0,23	T CPP-by-product
1-chloro-1-Propene (isomer-2)					5,84	0,04	7	0,27	T CPP-by-product
1,2-dichloro-propane		0,01			1,6	0,16	3,8	2,2	T CPP-by-product
2-Chloroethanol							1,2	0,45	T CPP-by-product
1-chloro-2-propanol					0,27	0,09	2,4	0,73	T CPP-by-product
2-chloro-1-propanol					0,11	0,02	0,4	0,30	T CPP-by-product
Chlorobenzene			0,22	0,04					additive?
Propylene Glycol							2,1	1,4	PPG fragment
Anisole							132	71	solvent residue
Dipropylene glycol			0,61	0,05					PPG fragment
Propylene carbonate		0,01	4,0	0,93	0,15	0,02	2,4	0,89	PPG fragment
S-compound #1 (m/z 60;103)							0,23	1,4	cystramine by-product
S-compound #2 (m/z 172)							0,05	0,74	cystramine by-product
T CPP	0,19	0,78	0,54	2,2	2,6	0,65	0,003	0,67	T CPP
T CPP isomer #1	n.a.	0,17	0,15	0,52	0,62	0,16	n.a.	0,13	T CPP
T CPP isomer #2		0,02	0,14	0,06	0,62	0,04	n.a.	0,02	T CPP

a)

compounds	Dense Fossil-based_1000h		Foam Fossil-based_1000h		Compressed Fossil-based PU_1000h		Vitrimer Dense Fossil-based_1000h		
	at 40°C	at 80°C	at 40°C	at 80°C	at 40°C	at 80°C	at 40°C	at 80°C	
	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	
TVOC	45	0,63	4,6	4,11	317	2,82	197	16,7	TVOC
Acetaldehyde		0,02	3,6	0,09		0,06	3,7	0,11	oxidation product
2-chloro-1-Propene							0,01	0,003	T CPP-by-product
1-chloro-1-Propene - isomer-1					1,1	0,02	0,58	0,05	T CPP-by-product
acetone	9,2	0,15	1,0	0,75	23,1	0,24	1,7	0,16	oxidation product
1-chloro-1-Propene - isomer-2							5,8	0,07	T CPP-by-product
Acetic acid	0,10	0,04	0,59	1,19	0,4	0,10			oxidation product
1,2-dichloro-propane			0,08	0,01	3,6	0,20	1,7	0,44	T CPP-by-product
1-chloro-2-propanol					0,4	0,14	0,37	0,09	T CPP-by-product
1-chloro-2-propanol					0,0	0,03	0,04	0,03	T CPP-by-product
Anisole							41	13,0	anisole
Propylene Carbonate			0,01	0,29	2,2	0,07	0,24	0,11	PPG fragment
S-compound #1 (m/z 60;103)							0,19	0,13	Cystamine by-product
S-compound #2 (m/z 172)							0,01	0,03	Cystamine by-product
T CPP	0,03	0,02	3E-07	0,14	0,18	0,08	0,03	0,03	T CPP
T CPP isomer #1				0,03	0,01				T CPP

b)

Figure 39. List of main compounds released by Pristine (a) and 1000h-aged (b) fossil-based PU in use conditions and their emission rates measured experimentally at 80°C (in µg/g/h) and extrapolated at 40°C from Arrhenius-law (in ng/g/h)

Figure 40. Comparison of the emission rates measured at 80°C (a) and emission rates extrapolated at 40°C (b) of the main compounds groups for the different fossil-based PU and for Pristine & 1000h-photaged samples.

In case of bio-based materials, the Arrhenius plots for total organics release show a relative linear temperature-dependence (cf. Figure 41). Dense bio-based material presents a lower total emission than foam PU while vitrimerized dense and vitrimerized foam PU led to higher release rates (**dense < foam < vitrimerized dense ~ vitrimerized foam**). Analogously to fossil-based, foam material and vitrimerized materials appear as the more emissive, likely related to the porosity/surface exchange and the vitrimerization process. In comparison with similar fossil-based polymers (cf. figure 30) total emission levels are slightly higher for non-vitrimer dense and foam materials whereas the vitrimerized-forms present lower levels.

Figure 41. Arrhenius plots for experimental release rates (in $\mu\text{g/g}$) of Total organic compounds emitted from pristine and 1000h-photoaged Bio-based materials – 50°C - 90°C temperature range.

In regard to individual compounds, most of species detected present release behaviours which respect an Arrhenius temperature-dependence allowing the calculation of extrapolated rates at ambient temperature (cf. Figure 42). Few species were detected at higher tested temperature, mainly ethylene and propylene glycol-type residues, which probably correspond to degradation products induced by these thermal conditions.

Figure 42. Arrhenius plots for experimental release rates (in $\mu\text{g/g}$) of main organic compounds emitted for Foam bio-based PU after 1000h-photoageing. 50°C - 90°C temperature range

Main compounds released in ambient conditions and their emission rates extrapolated at 40 °C as well as those experimentally determined at 80 °C were gathered in Figure 43 and also compared in the histogram in Figure 44. No common compound with fossil-based PU was showed, the main species detected being quite characteristic of these bio-based materials studied. Indeed, the following compounds or groups of compounds were highlighted:

- By-products of (polyol/fatty acids)-esters, and more precisely glycerin (the triol originating from the triglycerides family) and C₁₆- & C₁₈- alkanolic & alkenolic acids esters, these species corresponding to typical components of the castor oil. For reminder, the bio-based polyols used for the bio-based PU are precisely derived from castor oil. These compounds are detected whatever the bio-based PU considered, and foam materials present slightly higher outgassing rates than their homologous dense materials.
- Hydroxyethylthiosulfate (HETS), the vitrimerization agent used in the bio-based PU route, and the ethylenesulfide identified as its by-product. These 2 compounds are logically only detected for Vitrimerized dense and foam PUs.

After 1000 h photo-ageing, quite different releases were observed. First, Arrhenius plots of Total Volatile Organic Compounds (TVOC) release rates confirm the expected outgassing behaviour (linear trend). These curves also highlight a significant decrease in the TVOC release for all materials after 1000 h ageing. Moreover, the release rate appears perceptively more pronounced for foam materials than for dense materials, higher porosity likely facilitating the outgassing of compounds.

Regarding the nature of the released compounds after ageing, neither (Polyol/fatty acids)-ester by-products nor HETS & ethylene sulfide were detected indicating that their release over time diminished up to undetectable levels. As a result, two main other types of compounds were released, namely:

- Oxygenated compounds, composed of acetone, acetic acid as well as C₆-and C₇- acids and C₈-ketone. These species are likely produced during (photo-)oxidation process of the polymer materials, the oxidation products yielded being then able to outgassing.
- Volatile alkanes such as propane, pentane, hexane and C₈-alkane. Similar photo-degradation by scission of alkyl-chains of the polymer is assumed to explain the release of these alkanes.

In conclusion, the airborne organic compounds released in use conditions were comprehensively identified for each material in their new and aged states highlighting mainly the released of additives, formulation components, degradation products, etc. Furthermore, the assessment of release rates was carried out at 40 °C showing that the overall emission rates are very low, in the ng/g/h range.

compounds	Dense Bio-based PU		Foam Bio-based PU		Vitrimerized Dense Bio-based PU		Vitrimerized Foam Bio-based PU		
	at 40°C	at 80°C	at 40°C	at 80°C	at 40°C	at 80°C	at 40°C	at 80°C	
	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	
Ethylene sulfide					0,14	0,04	0,16	0,02	HEDS by-product
Chlorobenzene	0,77	0,01	0,30	0,03	0,24	0,01	0,50	0,04	other
Glycerin	0,63	0,15	3,66	0,07		0,60	0,17	0,35	(polyol/fatty acid)-fragment
HEDS					2,04	0,30	0,96	0,03	HEDS
n-Hexadecanoic acid methyl ester	0,64	0,02	0,37	0,07			0,76	0,07	(polyol/fatty acid)-fragment
C18-alkenoic acid, ester	0,07	0,04	0,03	0,07	0,20	0,07	0,14	0,15	(polyol/fatty acid)-fragment
C18-alkenoic acid, ester	0,40	0,06	0,22	0,06	0,71	0,08	0,55	0,07	(polyol/fatty acid)-fragment
Octadecanoic acid, methyl ester	0,02	0,01	0,02	0,01	0,07	0,01	0,12	0,03	(polyol/fatty acid)-fragment

a)

compounds	Dense Bio-based PU - aged 1000h		Foam Bio-based PU - aged 1000h		Vitrimerized Dense Bio-based PU - aged 1000h		Vitrimerized Foam Bio-based PU - aged 1000h		
	at 40°C	at 80°C	at 40°C	at 80°C	at 40°C	at 80°C	at 40°C	at 80°C	
	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	ng/g/h	µg/g/h	
TVOC	8	0,27	3	1,1	5	0,35	21	1,1	TVOC
Propane	1,4	0,03	1,85	0,03	0,38	0,005	2,9	0,03	alkane
Pentane	2,2	0,02	1,33	0,07	0,51	0,02	1,5	0,03	alkane
Acetone	0,47	0,03	0,35	0,05	n.a.		0,55	0,02	oxidation product
Hexane	0,36	0,03	1,30	0,12	0,35	0,03	0,60	0,04	alkane
Acetic acid	0,26	0,02	0,01	0,14	n.a.	0,03	0,03	0,07	oxidation product
C8-alkane	0,02	0,01	0,18	0,02	0,54	0,01	0,54	0,01	alkane
C8-ketone	0,15	0,01	0,25	0,07	0,47	0,02	0,86	0,04	oxidation product
Hexanoic acid	0,05		0,05	0,02				0,01	oxidation product
Heptanoic acid			0,10	0,04			0,01	0,01	oxidation product

b)

Figure 43. List of main compounds released by Pristine (a) and 1000h-aged (b) Bio-based-PU in use conditions and their emission rates measured experimentally at 80°C (in µg/g/h) and extrapolated at 40°C from Arrhenius-law (in ng/g/h).

Figure 44. Comparison of the emission rates measured at 80°C (a) and emission rates extrapolated at 40°C (b) of the main compounds groups for the different Bio-based PU and for Pristine & 1000h-photoaged samples.

Partial extraction + UPLC-tofMS analysis.

A given mass of PU was introduced in ultrapure water heated at 50°C and stirred for 24 h. The ultrapure water was then filtered (PTFE 0.22 µm) and diluted for subsequent UPLC-tofMS analysis performed with the same method used for total extraction analysis. The objective of this extraction protocol is to evaluate the potential release of dissolved species in water in order to consider environmental conditions of the PU use phase, in particular the possible rain leaching of frame windows. Despite experimental conditions (50 °C, 24 h, cryo-milling) far from real conditions, this protocol allows a comparative assessment of the potential chemicals release in water for the different PU routes.

Figure 45 shows the mass rates (in µg/g) extracted for the various compounds or compound groups detected before and after photo-aging for the different fossil-based and bio-based PU References. Globally, fossil-based PU shows high release rates, and especially the vitrimerized-form, while bio-based PU leads to low levels.

Figure 45. tofMS semi-quantification of compounds extracted in water matrix (partial extraction protocol) for fossil-based PU (left) and bio-based PU (right).

Fossil-based PUs release in water their additives (TCPP and triethylenediamine), but in relative low content in comparison with total extracted values (respectively about 10-20%, cf. Figure 32), meaning that if the transfer is possible, it remains low. Vitrimerized fossil-based PUs showed strong additional release, composed of PPG compounds; TMP; benzenamine, 4,4'-methylene-bis and also unidentified species. The polarity of PPG compounds and TMP is likely favorable to their extraction in water, the detected amounts corresponding to about 50 % of the total extracted amounts.

Regarding bio-based PU, a slight release of PPGs and benzenamine, 4,4'-methylene-bis is observed. Contrary to total extraction results, no fragment of bio-based ester of polyol-C18-fatty acids was detected confirming that, even if these species are strongly present in the bio-based matrix, they have no affinity for water.

Finally, no very significant release difference and clear trend are highlighted between pristine and aged materials meaning that the photo-aging and the material-induced modifications have no significant impact on the ability to be lixiviated by water.

Micro- and nanoplastic spot-checks

In the previous version of the deliverable, each type of fossil-based polyurethane (both foam and dense, in pristine and aged forms) and the vitrimer (also in pristine and aged forms) was measured at least once; however, the evaluation of duplicate samples was still in progress. The biobased polyurethane materials were introduced later in the project, and measurements for BIO-PU + Add no HEDS and BIO-PU + Add + HEDS were still ongoing, which is why they were not included in the earlier version. In this updated version, the assessment has been completed, allowing for a more detailed discussion of the results.

The raw data obtained from the three different analytical techniques were utilized to calculate the release of each species in mass per (aged) surface area. **Figure 46** illustrates the comparison of releases from the fossil-based polyurethanes (both foam and dense), the vitrimer, and the biobased PUs (BIO-PU + Add without HEDS and BIO-PU + Add with HEDS), each in pristine and aged forms.

Figure 46. Release of secondary microplastics, nanoplastics and DOC in mg/cm² from different SURPASS PUs before and after UV aging. Samples with different sizes are highlighted in red.

In the previous version of the deliverable, it was noted that no significant differences in micro- and nanoplastic releases were observed between pristine and aged samples, nor among the different types and shapes of fossil-based polyurethanes. However, the standard deviation between duplicates was relatively high, and this discrepancy became even more pronounced when all duplicate and the biobased PU data were added to the graph. It was previously suggested that this variation might have arisen from the differing sizes of the PU foam and dense plates (25 cm² versus 6 cm²), as well as the influence of release from the aged edges compared to the aged surface. The biobased PU specimens exhibited even greater variability in shape and size (25 cm² x 1 cm versus 3 cm² x 0.2 cm). Consequently, it was decided to conduct additional microscopy analyses on the plates to further investigate these differences. **Figure 47** highlights the main findings from this assessment: The 25 cm² plates typically

featured three cutting edges (indicated as index 2 in Figure 47) and one smooth edge, which was likely in contact with the production mold. The UV-aged surface (index 1 in Figure 47) was also smooth, as it should have been in contact with the production mold as well. In contrast, the 6 cm² duplicate samples of the fossil-based PU foam had four cutting edges. The smooth 6 cm² surface was exposed to UV irradiation. For the biobased PUs, the 25 cm² plates were comparable to the fossil-based ones. However, the 3 cm² plates were significantly shorter in height (0.2 cm compared to 1 cm). As a result, it was not the smooth surface that was exposed to UV irradiation, but rather the cutting edge. This aspect is of high importance to consider when discussing the further results, since the differences between smooth surfaces and cutting edges were significant: In comparing the smooth surfaces of pristine and aged samples prior to NanoRelease treatment, we did not observe a significant number of particles attached to them. This suggests that 1000 hours of UV aging may not have been sufficient to induce substantial microplastic formation. However, we did find that the surfaces of the cutting edges were covered with a high density of particles. When comparing the cutting edges before and after sonication treatment (NanoRelease), we discovered that these particles were released from the cutting edges, leading to their unintentional quantification in the particle counter and AUZ measurements. In the case of the 3 cm² duplicates of the biobased PUs, these particles that inadvertently adhered to the cutting edges were directly exposed to UV irradiation, which further explains the significant deviations observed between duplicates in this specific instance. Based on these observations, we can conclude that the micro- and nanoplastic releases from the cutting edges were greater than those resulting from UV aging. Additionally, it is worth considering that the samples may have been aged at CEA and then shipped to BASF, meaning that the loss of UV-aged fragments during transit cannot be entirely ruled out.

Figure 47. Microscopy analysis of received test bodies (pristine and aged, treated and untreated) for microplastic assessment. Test bodies varied in shape and sizes, as well as in the number of smooth surfaces vs. cutting edges.

Given the points discussed above, the current dataset is not suitable for comparisons between different types of polyurethanes or between pristine and aged versions of these materials. However, some indicative conclusions can be drawn by comparing the results of plates that are of the same size (Figure 48).

Figure 48. Release of secondary microplastics, nanoplastics and DOC in mg/cm² from different SURPASS PUs before and after UV aging. Only samples with same plate sizes compared: a) 25 cm², b) 6 cm², c) 3 cm².

In nearly all instances, the release of DOC was greater than the release of particles. An increase in DOC release was observed after aging, indicating that a portion of the polymer was transformed into non-solid, water-soluble oligomers. The particle release from the larger plates was significantly lower than that from the smaller plates, which can be attributed to the differing ratios of smooth surfaces to cutting edges based on their size, as described and discussed above. The increase in micro- and nanoplastic release after aging the 25 cm² plates was relatively modest, while it was much more pronounced in the 6 cm² PU foam plates. Notably, an increase in nanoplastic release was observed for BIO-PU + Add without HEDS after aging for both plate sizes (25 cm² and 3 cm²). For the 3 cm² plates, where the cutting edge was directly exposed to UV light, the microplastic release was lower than that from the pristine sample, suggesting further degradation and transformation of attached microplastics

into nanoplastics. Conversely, for the 3 cm² BIO-PU + Add + HEDS plates, no changes in particle release were detected. However, a slight increase in microplastic release was observed in the 25 cm² plates of this material after aging, which was comparable to the release from BIO-PU + Add without HEDS.

For future assessments of micro- and nanoplastic release rates from PU foams, the points discussed above should be carefully considered. It is advisable to use plates of comparable sizes and shapes while minimizing the number of cutting edges. If cutting edges are unavoidable, it is recommended to clean them using ultrasonication in water to remove any attached particles prior to aging. Additionally, conducting aging for a minimum of 2000 h is suggested to ensure significant micro- and nanoplastic release caused by UV irradiation.

For this CS, the considerations and findings on transformation and degradation products were provided directly in the previous paragraphs and integrated as part of the experimental results obtained.

1.2.1.4 Main findings in Case Study 1

The comprehensive release study of the SSbD alternatives compared to Reference materials was done for the 3 identified hotspots (ref. 1.2.1 Case study 1 (CS#1)). Main findings in terms of release behaviour are summarized hereafter.

During **the cutting/milling activities**, the potential workers exposure through release of powder during this activity was assessed for fossil-based PU (Ref. & SSbD#1 routes) using feSEM & optical observations and dustiness measurements in order to characterize the tendency of the polymer powder to form airborne particles during processing. Results revealed that the powder of the vitrimer form present bigger micron-sized particles than the non-vitrimer one (mean diameter of 15µm vs. 45µm) while dustiness indexes were evaluated as low and moderate for vitrimer and non-vitrimer samples, respectively. Therefore, lower potential release of powder from SSbD#1 may be expected versus Reference route, probably due to the wet impregnation step of the vitrimerization agents.

In case of the **thermal compression activity**, the release of different substances and by-products for the fossil-based PU route (SSbD#1) was studied at its process temperature (i.e. 200°C) and compared to non-impregnated powder. Significant ATG mass losses were highlighted (few wt. %), the vitrimer form leading to an additional loss of ~3 wt. %. The d-TD-GC-MS/FID analysis showed that the impregnated powder (SSbD#1) emits strong amounts of the flame retardant TCPP. TCPP was also detected in similar levels in the non-impregnated powder, while additional release of materials was identified as mainly due to anisole residues, the impregnation solvent, and cystamine by-products. Consequently, a potential inhalation exposure of workers to these PU additives and by-products can occur during the thermal compression activity of SSbD#1 route.

Regarding the **consumer use stage**, potential release of powder and organic compounds from the Reference material and the different SSbD alternatives was assessed over time through combined weathering and leaching protocols to simulate potential consumer exposure through airborne exposure and environmental release of materials in air and water. As a first step, the effect of weathering was examined through mechanical and physico-chemical surface properties of the investigated materials to highlight potential degradation mechanisms over time in relationships with potential release. This step also gives an extensive knowledge that can help materials developers for the design of the product. In a second step, release evaluation tests of micro/nano plastics and organic compounds were performed and main findings are summarized below.

The release of micro/nano plastics was evaluated for selected fossil- and bio-based materials and no significant differences were shown between pristine and aged specimens and between the different types of PU investigated. However, it must be noted that the sample preparation of the PUs for this assessment was not ideal, and recommendations described above should be considered for future micro- and nanoplastic assessments on PU foams. Analogously, wear resistance tests performed for both fossil & bio-based PUs showed that the vitrimerization and the weathering did not negatively affect the abrasion resistance.

Then, the release of *airborne organic compounds* was assessed at 40°C from measurements at higher temperatures based on an Arrhenius extrapolation method. Both pristine fossil-based and bio-based vitrimer forms (SSbD #1 and SSbD#2, respectively) showed more VOC emissions than their non-vitrimer counterparts (Ref and SSbD#0, respectively) while the bio-based vitrimer material (SSbD#2) appears less emissive than the fossil-based vitrimer (SSbD#1) and the bio-based non vitrimer PU (SSbD#1) leads to very slightly higher emission than its fossil-based homolog (Ref route).

In general, different compounds are released from bio based and fossil-based materials.

Fossil-based routes release the TCPP and its thermal degradation products. For the vitrimer form (SSbD#1), the emission of TCPP is lower but additional compounds linked to the vitrimerization process are released:

- C₃-organochlorine compounds identified as TCPP thermal degradation products (1-chloro-1-propene; 1-chloro-2-propanol; 1,2-dichloropropane...),
- Anisole (impregnation solvent)
- Unidentified by-products (S-compounds #1 and #2) of the cystamine vitrimerization agent.

The release of these species is strongly reduced with ageing and a low outgassing of small oxygenated molecules then occurs: acetaldehyde, acetone, acetic acid.

Bio-based materials release quite different substances that are characteristic of these routes, namely C₁₆- & C₁₈- alkanic & alkenic acids esters and glycerin corresponding to by-products of typical (polyol/fatty acids)-esters of the castor oil. Additionally, the vitrimer form (SSbD#2) releases the hydroxyethylthiol (HETS) and the ethylenethiol (the vitrimerization agent and one by-products). After photo-aging of PU, the release of these molecules decreases to undetectable levels, but a low release of 2 new types of degradation products occurred:

- Oxygenated compounds: acetone, acetic acid, C₆- and C₇- acids and C₈-ketone.
- Volatile alkanes such as propane, pentane, hexane and C₈-alkane.

Organic compounds released in water were evaluated by water extraction (leaching simulation)- UPLC-tofMS and showed that bio-based PU led to quite lower release of organic compounds than fossil-based PU.

Compounds emitted by fossil-based materials are mainly TCPP and triethylenediamine. Additionally, for the vitrimer form (SSbD#1 route), polypropylene glycols (PPG) residues are emitted, leading to an increase in release compared to the Ref route. In case of bio-based materials, no significant release is shown for vitrimer form (SSbD#2) while low release of PPG residues and 4,4'-methylene-bis-benzamine are observed for the non-vitrimer form.

1.2.2 Case study 2 (CS#2)

Case study 2 aims to develop a composite material, lighter than metal, to be used in structural applications for the railway sector. The use of composites which are much lighter materials than metal would allow a significant reduction in vehicle weight and, thus, energy.

The SSbD objectives of this CS is to design a composite material that:

- Meet all the fire, smoke, and toxicity (FST) requirements, established by the EN45545 standard, of the railway sector, that ensure the safety of people and the environment.
- Achieve the required mechanical performance and the needs of the manufacturing process.

- Contribute to the safety of people and the environment using non-harmful flame retardants and inherently flame-resistant materials.
- It is inherently recyclable at the end of its useful life.

More details related to the material design can be found in D4.1 *Polymeric material specific SSRbD criteria and scoring strategy*.

1.2.2.1 Hotspot identification

Figure 47 showed the starting point used in CS2 (Reference route) in which metal part is expected to be substituted by a lighter weight material in order to decrease energy consumption during use in railway application and part recycling at the end of life. Because of the impossibility to perform release tests using this material, this Reference route was replaced with the SSbD#0 route using a lightweight material (carbon fibre epoxy composite) which is not recyclable and containing a halogen-based flame retardant (FR). To go further, in SSbD#1 route, a halogen-free FR is used, combined with a reversible hardening technology, where the infusion manufacturing process permits to develop a recyclable composite, thus increasing the performance in terms of safety and sustainability. To investigate release performances of the different materials, SSbD#0 and SSbD#1 have been tested.

Figure 47. SSbD and Reference routes developed for CS2.

In table 3, the activities made, and materials used for SSbD#1 are presented for each life cycle stage, the identified hotspots of release in yellow and, whenever possible, the associated experimental tests performed.

Table 3. Hotspots of release identified and associated experimental test performed.

Life Cycle Stage	Activity / Exposure Scenario	Route	Potential Hotspot of release	Potential receptor(s) of release/ exposure	Potential exposure route(s)/ Exposed environmental compartments	Experimental test	Substance of interest
Step 1 & Step 2 - Material design (Formulation & Manufacturing) - Fire retardant resin (FR) formulation	Resin weighting	SSRbD#1	NO				
	Hardener weighting	SSRbD#1	NO				
	Mechanical mixing and heating of FR + resin + hardener	SSRbD#1	NO				
	Handling/cutting of fibres	SSRbD#1	YES - Dry solid carbon fibres, high energy level of the process, manual activity, 60 min duration	Workers	Inhalation, dermal	Monitor particles emission in air during cutting	Micro and nano fibres
Step 1 & Step 2 Material design (Formulation & Manufacturing) - Composite manufacturing process	Resin impregnation of fibres - moulding	SSRbD#1	NO				
	Infusion + 2h curation + decreasing T	SSRbD#1	NO				
	Composite screening (set requirement tests)	SSRbD#1	NO				
Step 3 - Use	Use as lightweight structural part of the train	SSRbD#1	YES - potential release during aging & abrasion	Environment	Soil, waters	Outdoor aging and hard abrasion	Powder of the composite, micro and nano fibres
Step 4 - EoL, reprocessing (mechanical)	Grinding	SSRbD#1					
	Sieving	SSRbD#1	YES - High energy mechanical activity	Workers	Inhalation, dermal	Experiments not planned because samples were not yet available	Powder of the composite, micro and nano fibre
	Grinder cleaning	SSRbD#1					
	Moulding (hot-pressing)	SSRbD#1					

NA: activity excluded from the study, NO: no release identified, and no experimental tests performed.

The hotspots selected for further investigations are:

- Cutting/handling activities: dry solid carbon fibres are used in manual activities with a potential release of fibrous particles.
- Consumer use: the solid material is used under challenging conditions which can cause release of powder following combined exposure to UV light, temperature and humidity potentially leading to degradation mechanisms and abrasion.

For each of the above-mentioned hotspots, exposure scenarios and associated characterization methods were defined to evaluate the potential release of various species, as detailed in the following sections.

Considering the gender dimension, the activities performed to formulate the material and develop the product have been carried out primarily by women, highlighting the contribution of female researchers and engineers in this field. Ensuring equal opportunities and visibility for women in material science and product development is essential for fostering diversity and innovation. During the use, the material will be applied in rail transportation, where personnel potentially exposed during the installation of the product in the train, as well as during maintenance activities (e.g., substitution of small parts of the train), may include workers of different genders. Therefore, it is essential to consider ergonomic factors, protective equipment fit, and potential gender-related differences in exposure levels to ensure safety and inclusivity. For the recycling process of this material has been studied at a laboratory scale, primarily by women with a background in chemistry. This highlights the significant role of female scientists in advancing sustainable solutions and developing efficient recycling strategies. Ensuring gender diversity in research contributes to a broader perspective in problem-solving and innovation. In future large-scale recycling applications, it will be essential to consider potential gender-related factors, such as the ergonomics of handling materials, the design of protective equipment, and exposure risks, to promote a safe and inclusive work environment for all personnel involved.

1.2.2.2 Transformation mechanisms and products detected

To investigate potential transformation mechanisms of the substances/materials investigated and the corresponding transformed products for CS2, a literature search has been conducted on components and released forms derived from the CS2 epoxy resin composite degradation or transformation

processes, with a focus on modifications on the flame retardant, the hardener and the carbon fibres (i.e., components conferring an increase of performance to the product) under simulated conditions.

For example, during the use stage conditions, Rai et al. 2022 underlined how weathering is one of the most critical processes affecting the physical-chemical attributes of plastic materials. This is due to the physical effect of the abrasion activity through microscopic surface cracks which in turn accelerates the leaching of additives (Luo et al. 2022) and also through the thermal oxidation and photo-oxidation. These photo/thermal-oxidations trigger polymeric yellowing when exposed to near-UV and visible radiation through the generation of various free-radical reaction mechanisms, altering the surface chemistry, mainly by forming new functional groups, such as $-C=O$; $-CO$, and $-OH$ in the presence of O/N oxides, OH radicals, and other photo-generated radicals (Rai et al. 2022). Under weathering conditions, an increase of surface area can be detected as a result of cracking and fragmentation after exposure to Xenon light (Luo et al. 2020). In addition, the geometry of the released particles also influences the release of flame retardants contained in the composite material that can be accelerated along the weathering process (Cheng et al. 2020). However, targeted analysis conducted by Menger et al. 2024 showed the vastly different chemical profiles that could be expected from different plastic products.

Other important components in composite materials to be investigated as part of transformation processes and their consequent transformed substances are intended and not intended added substances (i.e., respectively IAS and NIAS). For example, the formation of micro and nanomaterials (especially metal and metal oxide nanomaterials) can be detected from the weathering of plastic material as a consequence of transformation processed of the additives contained in the plastic (Jarosz et al. 2024), while the behaviour of IAS and NIAS in plastic debris was shown to be highly dependent on both the plastic-additive formulation and environmental factors (Bridson et al. 2024).

To extend the literature search conducted on transformation mechanisms during abrasion and weathering activities, articles investigating the performance of composite materials were also considered as an indirect investigation for materials release.

In the work by Das et al. 2023, the contribution of different reinforcing fibres in composites was investigated during accelerated weathering tests, concluding that these fibres play a dominant role in terms of performance on aged samples. In addition, the performance of a weathered composite is also influenced by the fibres structure, e.g., if the fibres are confined fibres in a reinforced polymer composite, or the number of layers. Indeed, as showed in Amirnuddin et al. 2023, the variation in percentage of moisture during weathering tests caused an effect in the structure of tin slag polymer concrete externally reinforced with carbon fibres.

1.2.2.3 Experimental setup

The compositions for all tested materials are shown in Table 4. The composite materials representing SSbD#1 route are SP1.1 RTM5 and SP3 RTM6, where SP3 RTM6 was considered by manufacturing partners (CIDETEC and ICT) as the most promising in terms of functionalities compared to similar composites differing by their FR and hardener composition. The alternative to SP3 RTM6 (i.e., SP1.1 RTM5) using only one epoxy resin was also developed to investigate the eventual contribution of resin in material released (i.e., SP1.1 RTM5). The SSbD#0 route is represented by a composite containing the halogen-based FR TCPP (i.e., TCPP RTM1.1). To investigate the contribution also of carbon fibres in the

material release during simulated exposure scenarios of SP3 RTM6 and SP1.1 RTM5, composites without carbon fibres were also tested (indicated as SP3 and SP1.1).

Table 4. Tested composite materials and their compositions.

Route	Composite name	Flame retardant epoxy resin	Carbon fibers	Hardener
SSbD Route 1	SP1.1 RTM.5	Araldite LY1564 (35%)	Yes	4 diaminephenyl disulfide (30.6%)
NR	SP1.1	Araldite LY1564 (35%)	No	4 diaminephenyl disulfide (30.6%)
SSbD Route 1	SP3 RTM.6	Araldite LY1564 + Exolit EP360	Yes	4 diaminephenyl disulfide (29%)
NR	SP3	Araldite LY1564 + Exolit EP360	No	4 diaminephenyl disulfide (29%)
Route 0	SP1.1 + TCPP RTM11	Araldite LY1564 + TCPP (C ₉ H ₁₈ Cl ₃ O ₄ P)	Yes	4 diaminephenyl disulfide

NR: no routes are associated with this material

A summary of the chemistry for the substances used to make the various composites is reported here below. All the detailed information related to the chemistry and performances was given in the sensitive classified reports (D2.2 and D3.2), a summary on is given here.

The Araldite LY1564 epoxy resin permits to develop a composite by resin transfer moulding (RTM) and infusion and it is made of two resins: Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (DGEBA) and butanediol diglycidyl ether (DGEPPG) presented in figure 48.

Figure 48. Molecular structure of main components of Araldite LY1564 epoxy resin

For the development of a recyclable epoxy formulation, the conventional hardener (4,4-methylene dianiline, MDA) has been replaced by a dynamic hardener, 4-aminophenyl disulphide (AFD) represented in figure 49.

Figure 49. Molecular structure of the dynamic hardener (AFD)

Exolit EP360 is a phosphorous based flame-retardant epoxy resin that was selected because of its technical function, it is less toxic and an ecologically friendly alternative to halogenated FRs. Furthermore, P-based FRs show synergistic effects with sulphur and organic disulfides.

Here below the details of the experimental tests performed and the substances identified.

Handling/cutting of fibres – Fire retardant resin formulation

Two pieces of carbon fibres material used by CIDETEC to prepare SP1.1 RTM.5, SP3 RTM.6 and TCPP RTM1.1 were sent to LEITAT to perform air measurement during the cutting of these fibres simulating activities performed by workers during handling/cutting fibres.

Optical Particle Sizer and NanoScan

An Optical Particle Sizer (OPS) (TSI, model 3330) has been used to determine particle number concentrations in continuous mode at different particle sizes (16 channels settled from 300 nm to 9 µm) connected with a 50 cm Tygon tube settled at 10 cm of the emission source, and NanoScan (10-420 nm). The flow of the OPS was calibrated to ensure a fixed air flow of 1 L/min and measurement of particle number concentration at different size ranges was detected every second along the entire assessed process. Background measurement has been done before starting the cutting recording particle released with both the instruments for 1 hour.

Scanning Electron Microscopy

Since the measurement of airborne fibres is challenging, the online monitoring with the OPS equipment was coupled with an on-line sampler for subsequent microscope investigation. During the sampling, the air flow was passed through a TEM grid that was observed after the measurement to provide additional information on the presence of fibre material and their morphological characteristics. The microscope used to observe the TEM grid was a JEOL J-7100FE, operating at 20 keV with a secondary electron detector. Prior to SEM observation, the specimen was coated with carbon to increase its conductivity.

According to the fibre (pathogenicity) paradigm (Pott and Friedrichs 1972; Stanton and Wrench 1972) and as stated by the World Health Organization, fibres with a length > 5 µm, a respirable diameter < 3 µm and an aspect ratio (A/R) > 3:1 are regarded as critical fibres as they may cause severe harm to humans upon inhalation exposure if they are sufficiently bio-durable (World Health Organisation (WHO) 1997). Moreover, respirable fibres with a diameter greater than 30 nm can be classified as rigid fibres, and are considered more hazardous than non-rigid fibres (Dumit et al. 2024). To make size measurements on SEM images, manual measurement of particle size was performed using ImageJ software.

Hard abrasion and outdoor aging - Use stage

To simulate the use stage of these materials, cascade activities (i.e., two or more tests repeated sequentially) were proposed to investigate the contribution of sunlight, rain and abrasion once the

composite would be applied on the exterior part of a train. For this reason, a climatic chamber SUNTEST XXL and a Taber abrader have been used to perform this simulation.

Specifically, daylight filters and Xenon lamps have been used to simulate outdoor conditions in the SUNTEST XXL+ climatic chamber (ATLAS Electrical Devices) and following Method A of ISO 4892:2024. A 2000 h of accelerated aging, or nearly 3 months in the laboratory simulator, accumulated 432MJ/m²UV energy, which corresponds to roughly two years under mid-European external conditions (Wohlleben et al. 2017). In this study, a total amount of 1000 h of exposure has been selected where at different time slots (0-500 h – 750 h – 1000 h), abrasion and corresponding physico-chemical characterization were conducted to investigate material release.

Table 5. Parameters used to set the climatic chamber for outdoor simulation (ISO 4892:2024).

Method A — Exposures using daylight filters (artificial weathering)						
Cycle No.	Exposure period	Irradiance ^b		Black-stand-ard temperature °C	Chamber temperature °C	Relative humidity %
		Broadband (300 nm to 400 nm) W/m ²	Narrowband (340 nm) W/(m ² ·nm)			
1	102 min dry 18 min water spray	60 ± 2 60 ± 2	0,51 ± 0,02 0,51 ± 0,02	65 ± 3 —	38 ± 3 —	50 ± 10 ^c —

Duplicates of each composite were prepared with a size of 10 x 10 cm for the cascade activity, while samples of 1 x 1 cm of size were prepared to investigate only the total weathering effect by performing electron microscopy on the surface of the exposed samples.

For the abrasion, a Taber Abrader with 2 wheels of 1 kg each covered with a medium abrasive paper (TA 125320- CS10) have been used to simulate a strong and heavy abrasion. To obtain enough material to be then characterized, 500 cycles without using the aspiration system of the Taber was also settled.

Figure 50 represents the setting of the Taber abrader (Figure 50a) and samples in the climatic chamber before starting the weathering (Figure 50b). The weathering analysis were stopped at 750h of aging as the samples already showed a strong morphological alteration of the samples, e.g., possible oxidation due to the UV effect (Figure 50c and 50d).

Figure 50. Hard abrasion and weathering respectively using the a) Taber abrader and the b) SUNTEST XXL+ climatic chamber, the effect of 750h of weathering in c) SP3RTM and in d) SP1RTM.

Inductively Coupled Plasma- Mass Spectrometry

An ICP-MS analysis has been conducted using the triple quadrupole ICP-QQQ (Agilent 8900) after a total digestion of each investigated sample.

An acid digestion is carried out with 4 ml of concentrated ultrapure nitric acid (HNO₃ 70 %) and 1 mL of concentrated ultrapure hydrochloric acid (HCl 37 %) in an analytical microwave at 280 °C and each sample was weighted before the digestion. The digestion residue obtained is then diluted appropriately to analyse Phosphorous (P) and Sulphur (S). These elements were selected because of the presence (or not) in the different samples: P is not contained in SP1.1 sample as this material do not contain FR, S element as it is contained in the AFD hardener and its quantity varied among different samples. Quantification is performed by interpolation on a calibration line prepared from commercial standards of the elements of interest. The test is performed in duplicate.

The following samples were processed using the above-mentioned protocol:

- Clean sanding paper as a blank.
- Sanding paper after abrasion (left and right wheel paper separately).

- Composite samples 1 x 1 cm size.
- Piece of composite samples 1 x 1 cm size cut at the end of the cascade activity.

As the structural part of the climatic chamber simulating the effect of the rain is made of plastic tubes, it was not possible to analyse potential release of plastic materials during the aging due to the high background.

Scanning Electron Microscopy

Scanning Electron Microscopy analysis using JEOL J-7100FE, operating at 20 keV with a secondary electron detector. Prior to the SEM observation, the specimens were coated with carbon to increase their conductivity. The SEM has been used to study the powder generated during the abrasion collected with few drops of milliQ water and deposited on SEM stubs to determine particle morphology and size distribution of the material released. Because of the presence of carbon fibres, a focus on fibres-like particles was conducted. To make size measurements on particles observed in SEM images, manual measurement of particle size was performed using ImageJ software.

Thickness - Micrometre

The thickness of each sample in three different points was measured before and after abrasion (after removing the powder obtained from the abrasion) using the micrometre Mitutoyo model S1012XB (Figure 51). Results are reported in millimetres with 2 decimals as mean and standard deviation between the two replicates of each material.

Figure 51. Equipment used to measure the thickness of the composite samples.

Weigh – Analytical balance

An analytical balance (Denver Instrument, APX-200) has been used to weight samples and wheels with the sanding paper before and after performing abrasion. Results are reported in grams with 4 decimals for the mean and standard deviation of the two replicates of each material.

Micro- and nanoplastic spot-checks

In the microplastic spot-check analysis for CS2 materials, the NanoRelease sampling protocol was applied before and after UV aging of the test specimen (2000 h according to ISO4892), similar to CS1 investigations. The purpose of the NanoRelease protocol is to remove loosely attached secondary micro- and nanoplastics from the surface of the (aged) test specimen and to disperse them in water for subsequent analysis. The pristine and aged CS2 plates all had the same surface dimensions of 6 cm². For sampling, 6 mL of ultrapure water were filled in a glass container and a CS2 plate was placed onto it (with the aged side facing the water). In the next step, the sample was treated in the ultrasonic bath at 100% power for 1 hour. During this time, regular cooling with ice was necessary to maintain the temperature below 40°C. After the ultrasonication treatment, the plate was removed, and the liquid was collected using a syringe. The collected volumes, the initial volume used for the treatment and the sizes of the plates were documented. Blank measurements in absence of a CS2 plate were conducted to determine the particle background.

As described above in the microplastic spot-check analysis for CS1 materials, three different techniques were used for subsequent analysis (for details, see CS1 description):

- 1) A particle counter was used to quantify the released fragments from 1- 120 µm
- 2) Analytical ultracentrifugation (AUC) was used to quantify the mass of released nanoplastics from 20-999 nm
- 3) Part of the solution was filtered < 0.02 µm to assess the release of water-soluble non-particulate organics (DOC) via TOC measurements

1.2.2.4 Results

Handling/cutting of fibres – Fire retardant resin formulation

After reprocessing data obtained from OPS and NanoScan, no significant difference is detected between particles released during the measurement of background and the cutting activity for both the particles counters (Figure 52). Moreover, no differences in terms of particle size were also not observed which means that the instruments were not capable of detecting and measuring fibres potentially released during cutting in Route 0 and Route 1 (i.e., the Reference and the SSbD alternative).

Figure 52. Particle number concentration obtained using NanoScan and Optical Particle Sizer equipment expressed as total concentration (left) and for each different size range (right).

Focusing on the considerations on fibres toxicity reported in the previous paragraph, the off-line sample collected in a TEM grid containing the filter used during the monitoring campaign was carefully observed at the SEM at different magnifications. Few fibres (a total of 4 fibres) were identified, all having diameters of $6.8 \pm 0.7 \mu\text{m}$, length ranging from $42 \mu\text{m}$ up to $170 \mu\text{m}$, and all with an Aspect/Ratio (A/R) higher than 3:1. A representative picture of the fibres observed on the grid is shown in figure 53.

Figure 53. SEM image of a fibre collected on the filter used in the particle counter during cutting activities.

Even if the number of fibres was low, their morphology makes them potentially harmful considering the WHO report (World Health Organisation (WHO) 1997). This suggests that the carbon fibre material should be handled in closed and protected environments, especially when high energy processes are used, such as mechanical cutting or abrasion, to avoid any possible inhalation exposure of workers.

Hard abrasion and outdoor aging - Use stage

The effect related to the hard abrasion and the outdoor aging is presented in terms of weight loss of the sample, thickness and elemental analysis of the powder released.

For the weight loss (Figure 54), it is possible to notice differences between the effect of the abrasion alone (represented as the weight loss at 0h) and the effect of the combination of abrasion and weathering (i.e., at 500h and 750h). Higher variability of the weight loss after the weathering between the two repetitions can be noticed compared to the variability of the samples before weathering, probably due to the effects of water and light on samples that present a not completely homogeneous surface. In addition, no significant differences can be noticed between composites (i.e., SP3 RTM6, SP1.1 RTM5) and their corresponding version without carbon fibres (i.e., SP3, SP1.1 REF). Higher release of material after weathering and abrasion of the benchmark material (i.e., TCPP RTM1.1) can be observed compared to the SSbD alternatives (i.e., SP3 RTM6 and SP1.1 RTM5). From these results, SP3 RTM6 and SP1.1 RTM5 samples present a better performance in terms of release compared to the benchmark material TCPP RTM1.1.

Figure 54. Weight loss of each sample after abrasion at 0h, at 500 and 750 hours of aging.

From the measurements of the thickness, a reduction of the thickness of the material can be observed after the abrasion both in weathered and not weathered samples (Figure 55). Lower values can be detected for samples without carbon fibres (i.e., SP3, SP1.1) compared to the ones containing carbon fibres (i.e., SP3 RTM6, SP1.1 RTM5, TCPP RTM1.1) and a progressive decrease of the thickness along the aging for all the samples. Moreover, after aging, a slight thickness increase was detected, probably due to the effect of the water and the light during the 500 hours aging that could alter the structure of each sample.

Figure 55. Thickness results expressed in mm of aged and not aged samples before and after the abrasion.

Figure 56 shows the thickness results obtained for each sample and each repetition along the cascade activity. From figure 56, it is possible to notice the visible difference between samples with (i.e., samples on the top of the figure) and without carbon fibres (i.e., samples on the bottom part of the figure). Moreover, a general trend of the measurements of the thickness along the cascade activity was detected, where very similar values of thickness were obtained between repetitions of the same sample (e.g., SP3.1 and SP3.2), which indicates a high structure homogeneity of this sample.

Figure 56. Thickness results expressed in mm along the cascade activity (initial, abraded, aged and aged+ abraded) of the repetitions of each sample.

Considering the release investigations by elemental analysis expressed as wt. %, it was not possible to discriminate Al and P concentrations from the blank and the sanding paper after abrasion for all the samples, due to the high initial concentrations of these two elements present in the sanding paper. For this reason, results are only reported as S concentrations (Figure 57), allowing to track hardener (AFD) release.

Figure 57. S content (wt. %) released and attached on the Taber abrader wheels at the initial stage and after weathering.

As can be seen from figure 57, sulphur is released in higher quantities from the samples with no carbon fibres (i.e., SP3 and SP1.1) compared to the ones containing the fibres material (i.e., SP3RTM6, TCPP RTM1.1) during the hard abrasion test. This is because the carbon fibres functionality, improves the stability and the resistance composite samples. According to Figure 57, similar S concentrations are obtained following the abrasion of SP3 RTM6 and TCPP RTM1.1 which does not permit to discriminate the release of AFD between the SSbD alternative (halogen-free FR) and the benchmark composite (halogenated FR) during the simulation of the use stage. Similar releases between weathered and not weathered samples can be detected for each sample. From these results, it is possible to conclude that the weathering does not influence the AFD release during the use stage of the various materials.

Considering the volume of the abraded surface for each sample (the total area of the abraded surface is 30cm² for a volume of 12 cm³) and the S concentration obtained by the total digestion of a 1 x 1cm of sample (Table 6), the percentage of S attached on the surface of the abrader wheels compared to the total S amount was theoretically calculated (Figure 58). The percentages of S attached on the Taber wheels compared to the total S amount from the abraded sample surface are comparable between the different samples with a range of 0.15-0.25 %. Due to these low values, it is not possible to discriminate between the amount of AFD released in the different composite materials and neither between aged nor not aged samples.

Table 6. S content (%w/w) after total digestion of 1x1 cm² sample and corresponding total S concentration calculated for abraded volume sample.

Sample	S (% w/w) – 1x1 cm ² sample (Mean ± SD)	S (% w/w) related to the total abraded sample volume (Mean ± SD)
SP3RTM6	1.73 ± 0.06	51.92 ± 1.77
SP3FR	6.30 ± 0.11	188.92 ± 3.22
SP1.1RTM5	2.40 ± 0.03	71.86 ± 0.85
SP1.1REF	8.08 ± 0.02	242.38 ± 0.57
TCPP RTM1.1	1.53 ± 0.01	46.05 ± 0.26

Figure 58. Percentage of S released and attached on the Taber abrader wheels compared to the total amount of S at the initial stage and after weathering.

According to SEM observations (Figure 59), the particles collected after the abrasion of non-aged and aged materials have a quite broad size distribution, characterized by particles having irregular spheroidal shapes. In samples containing the carbon fibres materials (RTM), fibre fragments have different lengths. Spheroidal and fibre particles were counted and measured separately, to obtain information on size for spheroidal particles and on number, diameter, length and A/R for fibre particles.

Figure 59. Powder of samples after 0h, 500h and 750h of weathering and abrasion analysed with SEM technique.

After weathering, particles seem to be more aggregated, and the determination of the particles size is more challenging due to the presence of overlapping particles with very similar contrast in the SEM images. This increased aggregation makes it more difficult to measure small size particles and results in an apparent larger particle size (Figure 60).

Figure 60. Particles size in µm of spheroidal particles detected in SEM images for the different samples.

Regarding the fibres released from the materials containing the carbon fibres materials (RTM), in all observed samples, the fibre diameter was measured at $6.5 \pm 0.5\mu\text{m}$, therefore they can be considered as rigid fibres. The fibres diameter did not change after the first abrasion and the subsequent weathering plus abrasion, indicating that these types of fibres are not affected by these processes. Regarding the length of fibres, very few of them were shorter than $5\mu\text{m}$ after the first abrasion, and their length remained quite constant after the subsequent weathering plus abrasion. Accordingly, the fibres A/R remained higher than 3:1. The number of fibres per picture and the number of fibres with $A/R > 3$, for aged and not aged samples, were quite similar, suggesting that the two SSbD alternatives (i.e., SP3 RTM and SP1 RTM) have the same behaviour when subjected to the combined weathering and abrasion. In table 7, the measurements for length, diameter and the percentage of fibres with an A/R higher than 3 are reported for 15 fibres of each sample, where the highest value was obtained for the TCPP material abraded and aged for 750h.

Table 7. Number of fibres detected in SEM images and percentage of elongated particles with Aspect/Ratio (A/R) higher than 3 for the samples containing carbon fibres.

Sample	Weathering	Diameter (μm)	% elongated particles with A/R>3
TCPP RTM1.1	0h	5.92 \pm 0.88	53 %
	500h	6.75 \pm 0.52	60 %
	750h	6.99 \pm 0.72	73 %
SP3 RTM	0h	6.64 \pm 0.49	60 %
	500h	6.77 \pm 0.32	53 %
	750h	6.77 \pm 0.55	67%
SP1 RTM	0h	6.27 \pm 0.46	60 %
	500h	6.49 \pm 0.35	73 %
	750h	6.67 \pm 0.74	60%

Micro- and nanoplastic spot-checks

In the previous version of the deliverable, each species of SP3 with and without carbon fibres (SP3 RTM6 and SP3 respectively) and the TCPP Reference with and without carbon fibres (TCPP RTM1.1 and TCPP respectively) was measured at least once. In the updated version of the deliverable all duplicate results are included.

The measured raw data obtained with the three different analytical techniques was used to calculate the release of each species in mass per (aged) surface area. Figure 61a shows the comparison of releases from the SP3 (without carbon fibres) and the SP3-RTM6 (with carbon fibres) material, each pristine and aged. Figure 61b shows the comparison of releases from the TCPP Reference (without carbon fibres) and the TCPP-RTM1.1 (with carbon fibres) material, each pristine and aged. Compared to releases detected from CS1 materials, the standard deviation between duplicates is much lower, which might be due to the fact that all specimens had the same sizes and therefore edge effects are directly comparable between samples. Based on this dataset, for pristine SP3 materials (with and without carbon fibres) the release of particles and DOC is in the same range. After UV aging, the DOC release is increased 3-4-fold in SP3 as well as in SP3-RTM6. In the case of SP3 the microplastic release is decreased after UV aging, and the nanoplastic release only slightly increased. In contrast to that, an increase in micro- and nanoparticle release from the SP3-RTM6 composite material was detected after UV aging. In this context, it must be noted that micro- and nanoparticles released from the composite materials are most likely composite fragments as well. However, due to the definition of microplastics, they all must be classified as microplastics, if their polymer content is at least 1%, which is very likely the case, but can currently not be proven with the available analytical techniques. In the case of the TCPP Reference without carbon fibres, an increase of micro-, nanoplastic and DOC release was

detected after UV aging. Particle releases from pristine TCPP Reference samples (with and without carbon fibres) were lower compared to pristine SP3 samples (with and without carbon fibres). The particle release from the TCPP Reference without carbon fibres detected after 2000h UV aging is however higher than the particle release from SP3 after the same aging duration. In the case of TCPP-RTM1.1, the micro- and especially the nanoparticle release increased after aging.

Comparing the Reference material (i.e., TCPP-RTM1.1) and the SSbD alternative material (i.e., SP3-RTM6), the microparticle release from the Reference was in most cases lower than from the SSbD product, but the nanoparticle release was, especially after aging, higher than the nanoparticle release from any other SSbD material (pristine and aged).

Figure 61. Release of secondary microplastics, nanoplastics and DOC in mg/cm² from different CS2 materials before and after UV aging.

1.2.2.5 Main findings in Case Study 2

A comparative analysis between SSbD alternatives and a Reference or benchmark material is necessary to evaluate release performance in the context of the SSbD implementation. From an SSbD perspective, such a comparative assessment is particularly valuable, especially during the early stages of product development. For the release assessment in CS2, this comparison was possible only for the hotspot of use phase, which was simulated by a cascade experiment including weathering and abrasion tests performed on the SSbD alternative materials (i.e., SP3 and SP1) and the benchmark material (i.e., TCPP RTM1.1), thus comparing SSbD#0 and SSbD#1 Routes.

After the weathering (500h and 750h) and abrasion, significant differences were obtained in terms of weight loss between the SSbD alternatives and the benchmark material.

The morphology and the size of the particles generated after the abrasion were determined by SEM. For the composite particles, a similar morphology and size were observed in all samples. In addition, similar fibres, in term of dimensions and amount, were also found in all samples analysed. Therefore, no significant difference was observed comparing the SSbD alternatives and the benchmark composite.

To track the release of hardener, the S concentration was analysed in the powder generated from the abrasion. From this analysis, the 500 and 750 hours of weathering does not influence the release of hardener during the simulated use stage of the different composite materials, as similar levels of S release were detected before and after aging. Moreover, similar S concentrations were detected for SP3RTM6 and TCPP RTM1.1 samples, meaning that no significant difference in the release of hardener was observed comparing the SSbD alternatives (i.e., SP3 RTM6 and SP1.1) and the benchmark composite (TCPP RTM1.1) during the simulation of the use stage.

To conclude, considering the release data obtained up to now, SSbD alternative materials (i.e., SP3 and SP1) show similar behaviour in term of release of each substance compared to the benchmark material (i.e., TCPP RTM1.1) while considering the total weight, the SSbD alternative SP3RTM showed better results compared to the reference material TCPP RTM.

1.2.3 Case study 3 (CS#3)

Case study 3 aims to process Multi-nanolayer (MNL) films for food packaging from polyolefins, barrier layer (EVOH or PA) and compatibilizer.

The SSbD objectives of this CS is to design a MNL films that:

- Reduce the percentage of compatibilizer in MNL films compared to conventional 5-layer films containing 15% compatibilizer.
- Obtain an Oxygen Transmission Rate lower than 10 ml/(m² day) (compared to conventional multi-layer films with OTR between 2 and 25 ml/(m² day)).
- Reduce the released Non Intentionally Added Substances (NIAS) content from films MNL during life cycle simulation, >10% in comparison with conventional films.
- Reduce C-footprint.
- Improve the recyclability rate of MNL films according to the Recyclclass methodology.
- Adapt a decontamination process to new MNL films targeting recycling in the food packaging sector.

For this CS#3, MultiNanolayer (MNL) films – food packaging sector, two distinct routes for SSbD are considered in the release assessment.

In fact the MNL film has an SSbD character due to the improvement of its formulation. Moreover, its structure meets recyclability criteria.

The SSbD#1 route involves MNL films designed for food packaging, manufactured via the MNL co-extrusion process. These films are then recycled and decontaminated using a supercritical CO₂ (scCO₂) process, after which the recycled material is intended to be reintegrated in food contact plastic products.

The SSbD#2 route follows the same steps as SSbD#1 route but without the scCO₂ decontamination process. However, the recycled material is repurposed into plastic products suitable only for non-food-contact applications.

It should also be noted that the bi-axial stretching step is excluded from the SSbD criteria assessment. This process is being explored separately in an experimental context to enhance the barrier properties of the films.

The Reference route corresponds to the ML film commercialized by WIPAK partner for food packaging sector as illustrated in Figure 62. This film is produced through cast co-extrusion. Currently, most multilayer films in the food packaging sector are either incinerated or landfilled at the end of their life cycle, even if in some cases they could also be mechanically recycled.

Figure 62. SSbD solutions and Reference routes developed for CS#3.

The SSbD routes and the Reference have different Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs). This technological maturity gap must be considered when comparing the SSbD topics between the SSbD SURPASS solutions and the Reference. SSbD#2 route is preferred in the SSbD assessment of CS#3 due to the technological and health challenges of recycling and decontaminating plastic for incorporation into food-contact applications. However, regarding the exposure and release assessment, SSbD#1 route has more impact than SSbD#2 route with one additional step in the life cycle: decontamination by scCO₂ process. The SSbD#1 route is selected for exposure tests.

Below are the materials for the different routes with a description of their structures in Figure 63.

The commercial grades remain confidential and are not disclosed in this deliverable (D4.2). All materials have been supplied by the CS3 project partners, namely WIPAK and BASF.

Reference route – WIPAK ML packaging film

The film contains 11 layers and is manufactured through cast co-extrusion. The structure of this Reference is confidential (Table 8).

Table 8. Description of route n°0: commercial Reference CS#3

Structure of ML film	11 layers
Thickness	200 ± 50 µm
Raw material	PO _ PA _ Compatibilizer
Function of material	PO (PE and PP): external layer PA: barrier layer Compatibilizer: Tie layer
Composition (mass percentage %wt)	PO: 61 wt. % PA: 32 wt. % Compatibilizer: 7 wt. %

SSbD#1 and SSbD#2 routes– MNL packaging film

The MNL film contains up to 1024 layers and is manufactured through MNL co-extrusion. The names of the commercial grades are confidential (Table 9).

Table 9. Description of SSbD#1 and SSbD#2 of CS#3

Structure of MNL film	Up to 1024 layers
Thickness	200 ± 50 µm
Raw material	mLLDPE _ PA6 or EVOH _ compatibilizer
Function of material	mLLDPE: external and internal layers PA6 or EVOH: barrier layer Compatibilizer: Tie layer
Composition (mass percentage %wt)	PE: 61 wt. % PA6: 15 wt. % maximum EVOH: 5 wt. % maximum Compatibilizer (maleic anhydride grafted polyethylene) :15 wt. % maximum

Figure 63. General structure of polymers used for CS#3 (SSbD solutions or Reference)

1.2.3.1 Hotspot identification

In this section, the conclusions regarding the release hotspots for CS#3 are presented. The objective is to identify stages or operations throughout the product's life cycle—from manufacturing to end-of-life—where there is a significant potential for the release of substances that may pose a risk to workers, consumers, or users of film packaging. The CS#3 partners (IPC, WIPAK, BASF, ICT) were tasked with gathering all relevant information, including the chemical inventory of substances in the polymers used, a detailed listing of life cycle stages, and associated process parameters.

One of the main challenges for CS#3 is the lack of available information on the substances present in the polymer grades. The safety data sheets (SDS) or technical specifications of the polymers do not disclose details about their typical formulations, such as additives or fillers, due to industrial confidentiality. Only the chemical composition of the polymer (e.g., mLLDPE or PA6) is provided. Based on this study, the potential release hotspots at different life cycle stages for CS#3, including Routes 1 and 2, have been identified and are summarized in Table 10.

Table 10. Release hotspots identified for each Step of case study 3.

Life Cycle Stage	Activity / Exposure Scenario	Route	Potential Hotspot of release	Potential receptor(s) of release/ exposure	Potential exposure route(s)/ Exposed environmental compartments	Experimental test	Substance of interest
Step 1 - Material design - Row materials	Supply masterbatch	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	NO				
Step 2 - Material design (Formulation & Manufacturing) - Production MNL films	Plastic drying	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	YES - High temperature process	Workers Environment	Inhalation Soil, waters	Air monitoring and chemical composition of plastics	VOCs
	MNL Co-extrusion process	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	YES - High energy process	Workers Environment	Inhalation, dermal Soil, waters	Air monitoring and chemical composition of plastics	VOCs, NIAS, micro & nano plastics
	Rewind	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	NO				
	Cleaning/purging/repair process equipment	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	NO				
Step 3 - Use, maintenance and repair - Industrial use	Cutting	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	NO				
	Thermoforming	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	NO				
	Filling with food	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	NO				
	Sealing	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	NO				
Step 4 - EoL, reprocessing	Consumer Use	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	YES - possible direct exposure if release happen	Consumers	Oral	Migration test in food simulant according to regulation UE 10/2011	NIAS, IAS, micro & nano plastics
	Waste packaging	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	NO				
	Sorting	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	NO				
	Washing	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	YES - High energy process	Workers Environment	Dermal Soil, waters	Filtration and analysis by micro-FTIR	Micro & nano plastics
Step 4 - EoL, reprocessing	Grinding	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	NO				
	Compounding process	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	NO				
	Decontamination using supercritical CO ₂ / ultrafiltration	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	YES - High energy process	Workers Environment	Inhalation Soil, waters	Air monitoring and chemical composition of plastics	VOCs, NIAS, micro & nano plastics
	Cleaning/purging/repair process equipment	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	NO				
Plastic process	SSRbD#1 & SSRbD#2	NO					

Among all the identified release scenarios, a selection of potential hotspots was made to focus on those with the most significant release of materials throughout the life cycle. The selected hotspots are highlighted in yellow in Table 10 and are further assessed through experimental testing. The corresponding experimental plan is outlined in Table 11.

Table 11. Experimental plan for the evaluation of CS#3 release hotspots –SSbD#1 and SSbD#2 routes

Life Cycle Stage	Activity / Exposure Scenario	Potential target exposed	Test	Substances released	Technique used
Step 2: Production MNL films	Plastic drying	Workers and environment	Air measurement	VOCs	Heating material at 60°C and identification VOCs by chromatography coupled mass spectrometry
	MNL Co-extrusion process	Workers and environment	Air measurement Chemical composition of plastics	VOCs NIAS	VOCs : heating material and identification VOCs by chromatography coupled mass spectrometry NIAS : comparaison between raw materials and samples after process => identification NIAS by chromatography coupled mass spectrometry and ICP-MS
Step 4 consumer Use	Consumer Use	Consumer	Specific Migration tests according to regulation UE 10/2011	NIAS+IAS+Microplastics	NIAS +IAS : identification by chromatography coupled mass spectrometry and ICP-MS
	Washing	Workers and environment	Study of contaminant in washing water after use	Microplastics	Microplastics : Filtration and analysis by micro-FTIR
Step 5: End-of-Life	Decontamination using supercritical CO ₂ / ultrafiltration	Workers and environment	Air measurement Chemical composition of plastics	VOCs	VOCs :heating material and identification VOCs by chromatography coupled mass spectrometry

Gender dimension has been considered in CS#3 by checking if and which activities performed by workers and consumers are normally made by male or female population. Specifically, in exposure scenarios of “Step 2: production MNL films”, both during plastic drying as well as MNL co-extrusion process, males are potentially more exposed than female, as 90% of the activities are performed by male workers. Considering the use stage, as the total population can be exposed to the food packaging during daily activities, male and female are equally exposed touching the packaging on the food or through the ingestion of substances migrated from the plastic to the food. For the end-of-life stage, both washing and decontamination using supercritical CO₂ activities are male-related actions.

1.2.3.2 Transformation mechanisms and products detected

To investigate potential transformation mechanisms of the substances/materials and the corresponding transformed products for CS#3, a database from the National Institute for Research and Safety (INRS, France) was used (<https://www.inrs.fr/publications/bdd/plastiques.html>) and a bibliographic research was conducted. The research focused on the polymeric raw materials used in the production of MNL films, i.e., low density polyethylene, polyamide 6, EVOH, and maleic anhydride grafted polyethylene, and considering the works of Wiesinger, Wang, and Hellweg 2021, Aurisano, Weber, and Fantke 2021; Groh et al. 2019.

➤ PE-LD: Polyethylene Low Density

The transformation and degradation products of LDPE vary depending on processing conditions such as temperature, humidity, oxygen, and the presence of chemical agents. Below is an overview of the products that can be formed during the transformation and degradation of LDPE.

○ **Transformation Products:**

- **Monomers and oligomers:** During processes such as extrusion, moulding, or other thermal treatments, LDPE may be partially break down into its base monomer, ethylene, or into oligomers (shorter polymer chains). This can occur when the temperature is too high.
- **Free radicals:** Under heat or irradiation, free radicals can form, initiating secondary reactions that may lead to the formation of specific products, including modified or crosslinked polymer structures.
- **Copolymers:** During transformation, copolymers can be formed if other monomers, such as butylene or styrene, are added to modify the properties of LDPE.
- **Branched polymers:** Transforming LDPE at relatively high temperatures, but below its melting point, can cause branched polymer structures to form, thus altering the material mechanical properties.
- **Films and complex structures:** Through extrusion or injection moulding, LDPE can be transformed into films, bags, or other plastic products with specific structures depending on the process.

○ **Degradation Products:**

LDPE degradation, often due to extreme conditions such as temperature, humidity, or oxidation, can produce several products:

- **Free radicals:** Thermal degradation of LDPE generates free radicals, which can lead to secondary reactions, promoting the formation of specific degradation products.
- **Aldehydes and ketones:** Degradation under heat or oxidation can produce aldehydes (such as formaldehyde) and ketones (such as acetone) from the breakdown of the polymer chains.
- **Carboxylic acids:** Particularly under high temperatures or oxidation, carboxylic acids, such as acetic acid or formic acid, may form as a result of the breakdown of the polymer chain.
- **Hydroperoxides:** These products can be formed due to oxidation of LDPE, particularly under high temperatures and exposure to oxygen.
- **Monomers:** Under severe degradation conditions, polyethylene can break down into its base monomer, ethylene, especially at very high temperatures.
- **Oxidized polyethylene:** Oxidation can also lead to the formation of shorter polyethylene polymers or other oxidized products.

In summary, during both the transformation and degradation processes of LDPE, a range of products can form, including smaller monomers, reactive intermediates, and various chemical degradation by-products, depending on the specific conditions the material is exposed to.

➤ **PA6: Polyamide 6**

The transformation and degradation products of PA6, which is a widely used thermoplastic polymer, can vary depending on the processing conditions or degradation environments. Here below an overview of typical products that can be formed.

- **Transformation Products:**

During the transformation of polyamide (for example, during extrusion, injection moulding, or stretching), several intermediate products or compounds may form:

- **Intermediate amides:** During the chemical reaction between acids and amines, intermediate amides may form before polymerization takes place.
- **Oligomers:** During the polymerization of polyamide, shorter polymer chains, or oligomers, can be generated before the final polymer is formed.
- **Crosslinking compounds:** If crosslinking agents are used, crosslinked products can form, improving the polyamide's resistance to mechanical and thermal stress.

- **Degradation Products:**

Degradation products of polyamide depend heavily on processing conditions, temperature, humidity, or exposure to chemical agents. Here are some examples:

- **Caprolactam:** Caprolactam is the monomer used to produce PA6. It can be released during degradation, especially when the polymer is exposed to high temperatures or certain chemical environments. Caprolactam is a common degradation product of PA6.
- **Amines:** Under certain conditions, PA6 can break down into amines, such as Pyridine.
- **Carboxylic Acids:** Thermal or oxidative degradation can lead to the formation of carboxylic acids (e.g., hexanoic acid) as a result of the breakdown of polymer chains.
- **Aldehydes and Ketones:** When PA6 degrades under oxidative or high-temperature conditions, aldehydes (such as formaldehyde) and ketones (such as acetone) can be produced.
- **Amides:** Thermal degradation of PA6 can lead to the formation of various amide compounds due to the breaking of the polymer chains.
- **Hydroperoxides:** In the presence of oxygen and heat, hydroperoxides may form, especially during the oxidative degradation of PA6.

The factors influencing degradation include high temperature (Polyamide can decompose at temperatures above 250°C, leading to products like smaller amides or acids) and moisture, because PA is both hygroscopic and hydrolysis is possible.

- **EVOH: ethylene-(vinyl alcohol)**

EVOH is a polymer made from ethylene and vinyl alcohol, known for its excellent gas barrier properties, which makes it widely used in packaging, especially for food preservation. The transformation and degradation products of EVOH depend on the processing conditions (temperature, pressure, and chemical agents) as well as the environment in which it is exposed.

- **Transformation Products:**

- **Copolymers and Blends:** EVOH can be used to form copolymers and blends with other materials, such as polyolefins (e.g., polyethylene or polypropylene) to improve processability or enhance barrier properties. During transformation processes like extrusion or injection moulding, EVOH can form modified materials with varying chemical structures depending on the monomers used.
- **Crosslinked Structures:** Under specific conditions (e.g., exposure to high temperatures or radiation), EVOH can undergo crosslinking, where polymer chains form a three-dimensional network. This crosslinked structure can enhance its chemical, thermal, and mechanical properties.
- **Oligomers:** In some processing conditions, especially at high temperatures, EVOH may break down into oligomers, which are shorter polymer chains that may have different properties than the original polymer.

- **Degradation Products:**

The degradation of EVOH can occur under high temperature, oxidation, or in the presence of moisture. Some degradation products include:

- **Vinyl Alcohol:** The vinyl alcohol component of EVOH can hydrolyse back into vinyl alcohol under certain conditions, such as exposure to moisture. Vinyl alcohol is unstable and can further degrade into acetaldehyde.
- **Acetaldehyde:** Acetaldehyde is one of the primary degradation products of EVOH, especially under thermal degradation. It can be formed from the breakdown of vinyl alcohol or the decomposition of the polymer structure.
- **Aldehydes and Ketones:** During thermal degradation or oxidation, aldehydes (such as formaldehyde and acetaldehyde) and ketones can be formed due to the breakdown of the polymer chains or the vinyl alcohol units.
- **Carboxylic Acids:** As EVOH undergoes oxidative degradation, carboxylic acids such as acetic acid or formic acid may form, typically from the cleavage of polymer chains.
- **Hydroperoxides:** Under oxidative conditions, hydroperoxides can be formed, particularly when EVOH is exposed to high temperatures and oxygen.
- **Monomers (Ethylene and Vinyl Alcohol):** In extreme conditions, the ethylene or vinyl alcohol units may break off from the polymer chain, leading to the release of the monomers themselves.

In conclusion, the transformation and degradation of EVOH can lead to a variety of products, including copolymers, crosslinked structures, oligomers, aldehydes (especially acetaldehyde), carboxylic acids, and vinyl alcohol. The exact nature of the products depends on the specific conditions to which EVOH is exposed.

- **Maleic anhydride grafted polyethylene (compatibilizer)**

Maleic anhydride grafted polyethylene is a copolymer formed by chemically bonding maleic anhydride to the polyethylene backbone. This modification enhances the polymer's compatibility with other materials, such as polar polymers or fillers. The transformation and degradation products depend on the processing conditions (such as temperature and pressure) and exposure to chemical agents.

- **Transformation Products:**

- **Grafted Maleic Anhydride Units:** During the grafting process, maleic anhydride reacts with the polyethylene backbone, leading to the formation of grafted maleic anhydride units. These modified units improve the adhesion of the polymer to other materials and enhance its compatibility with polar substances.
- **Copolymers:** In some cases, the grafting process may lead to the formation of copolymers if other monomers are introduced during the reaction, modifying the material's properties.
- **Crosslinked Polymers:** Under specific conditions (such as high temperature or radiation), crosslinking reactions can occur, forming a three-dimensional network of polymer chains, which improves the material's mechanical and thermal properties.
- **Oligomers:** During processing, especially under high-temperature conditions, the grafted polyethylene may break down into oligomers, which are smaller chains of polymer units.

- **Degradation Products:**

Degradation of maleic anhydride grafted polyethylene can occur under high temperature, exposure to oxygen, or in the presence of moisture. The degradation products include:

- **Maleic Acid:** Upon hydrolysis, maleic anhydride grafted to polyethylene can break down into maleic acid, especially under humid or aqueous conditions.
- **Aldehydes and Ketones:** Thermal degradation or oxidation can result in the formation of aldehydes (e.g., formaldehyde) and ketones (e.g., acetone) due to the breakdown of the polymer chain or the maleic anhydride units.
- **Carboxylic Acids:** Oxidation or thermal degradation can lead to the formation of carboxylic acids, such as formic acid or acetic acid, from the cleavage of the maleic anhydride or polyethylene chains.
- **Hydroperoxides:** Under oxidation conditions, hydroperoxides may form, especially when exposed to high temperatures and oxygen.
- **Monomers (Ethylene):** If the polyethylene backbone undergoes significant degradation, ethylene (the monomer of polyethylene) may be released, especially under extreme thermal conditions.
- **Polyethylene Degradation Products:** The polyethylene part of the polymer may degrade into smaller fragments such as oligomers, hydrocarbons, or aldehydes, depending on the degradation conditions.

In conclusion, during both the transformation and degradation of maleic anhydride grafted polyethylene, a range of products can be produced, including grafted maleic anhydride units, crosslinked structures, smaller oligomers, and various degradation by-products such as aldehydes, ketones, and carboxylic acids, depending on the environmental conditions.

1.2.3.3 Experimental setup

In the experimental test plan, substances with a molecular weight of up to 600 Da are considered to have a low risk of migrating into food or being released as volatile (VOCs) or semi-volatile organic compounds (SVOCs). Therefore, the experimental work was settled to identify released substances with a maximum molecular weight of 600 Da.

The experimental tests, designed to simulate the identified and selected hotspots as well as potential transformation products for CS#3, are categorized into four main areas: VOCs, migration tests, NIAS

(Non-Intentionally Added Substances) and microplastics. IPC performed VOCs, NIAS and migration analysis and micro- and nanoplastics during the consumer use stage, while BASF performed micro- and nanoplastics spotcheck during the recycling stage.

1.2.3.3.1 Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) Emission

For drying step of raw materials, VOCs emission rates were measured using HS-GC-MS, by heating at 60°C during 1 hour. This step concerns barrier layers, EVOH and PA6. Indeed, these two raw materials are steamed at 60°C to remove residual moisture before being processed.

For MNL co extrusion process, TENAX-TA sorbent tubes were used to perform air sampling. Air sampling with adsorbent tubes was used to collect and analyze VOCs or sVOCs in the air. The process involves two key steps: sampling and analysis.

For air sampling with adsorbent tubes, air is actively drawn through a tube filled with a solid adsorbent material, TENAX. The adsorbent traps the target compounds from the air as it passes through. Active sampling is conducted using a calibrated pump to control the airflow at 200 ml/min and ensure the collection of a representative sample during a process period. Figure 64 showed the tools used for the sampling. For hazardous organic emission measurements to analyze organic compounds in air, TENAX is recommended.

Figure 64. Tools for air sampling (on the left the tube sorbent TENAX TA and on the right calibrated pump) CS#3

The tube and the pump are positioned near the heat zone of the MNL process (near the MNL block) chain to assess the emission of VOCs posing a risk to workers as described in figure 65.

Figure 65. Tubes and pumps settled along the MNL process.

A TENAX sorbent tube is dedicated for a blank test. It's an active sampling carried out using a calibrated pump and a TENAX tube without the the MNL process line running or starting up. This allows to characterize substances released in air near the process platform.

After sampling during the entire processing phase, the adsorbent tube is transported to IPC laboratory for analysis. The trapped compounds are released from the adsorbent by thermal desorption. In this step, the tube is heated in a controlled manner, causing the compounds to volatilize and transfer into the carrier gas of a gas chromatograph (GC). The desorbed compounds are separated based on their chemical and physical properties as they pass through the GC column. The separated compounds are then detected and identified by mass spectrometry (MS), which provides a detailed analysis of the molecular structure of compounds. Parameters used are summarized in table 12.

Table 12. Apparatus parameters for VOCs analysis with TENAX tube (CS#3)

Description of test	VOCs Analysis method	Apparatus parameters
VOCs Adsorption on TENAX sorbent tube	TD-GC-MS	TD TENAX desorption at 120°C for 60 min
		MS Scan mode: 33 to 620 m/z (Da)

For scCO₂ decontamination process, active carbon filters have been made and installed, by ICT.

Filter have a volume of 275 cm³, filled with active carbon of 1 mm mesh (approximately 100 to 120 g of active carbon by filter). The filters are installed at two key points along the CO₂ process line (Figure 66), on the Extraction CO₂ Outlet Stream and on the degassing stage. A filter has been placed on the outgoing CO₂ flow from the extraction process. This ensures that any impurities or undesired substances are captured before further processing or release, maintaining the purity of the CO₂ stream.

Another filter is installed at the degassing stage, located at the outlet of the treated polymer. This filter captures residual volatile compounds or contaminants released during the degassing process, ensuring the quality of the treated polymer and minimizing emissions.

Figure 66. Active carbon filters and scheme of implementation on the scCO₂ process (CS#3)

After use, active carbon is analyzed, by IPC, to extract and identify the substances that may have been trapped during the filtration process. A thermal desorption is performed where the active carbon is subjected to thermal desorption to release the adsorbed substances. Extracted compounds are then analyzed using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) to identify the trapped substances.

This analysis helps evaluate the efficiency of the active carbon in capturing contaminants and provides insights into the nature of the released substances during the scCO₂ process.

Table 13 indicates the applied apparatus parameters.

Table 13. Apparatus parameters for VOCs analysis with active carbon (CS#3)

Description of test	VOCs Analysis method	Apparatus parameters
VOCs Adsorption on active carbon	HS-GC-MS	Active carbon sampling method 0.5 g
		HS Active carbon desorption at 150°C for 60 min
		MS Scan mode: 33 to 620 m/z (Da)

1.2.3.3.2 NIAS

This part is managed by IPC partner.

The concept of NIAS was introduced through regulations related to food contact applications. For example, the Regulation EU 10/2011 for plastics food contact materials, the following NIAS definition is provided as “Non-intentionally added substance” means an impurity in the substances used or a reaction intermediate formed during the production process or a decomposition or reaction product.

The (United Nations Environment programme 2023) reported the subcategories of NIAS (Figure 67). NIAS can originate from different sources, and they can include breakdown products of polymers, impurities in starting materials, unwanted side-products, and various contaminants from recycling processes.

Figure 67. Sources and categories of NIAS (United Nations Environment programme 2023).

The strategy associated with this objective involves three steps (Nerín et al. 2022):

- Step 1: Detect unknown substance (non-exhaustive list).
- Step 2: Identify unknown substance (non-exhaustive list).
- Step 3: Formulate a hypothesis on the NIAS or IAS category of the identified substance of interest (Groh et al. 2019).

Currently, this strategy is not exhaustive due to the limitations of existing analytical techniques (detection limits, identification limits, etc.).

Screening analysis can be conducted for unpredicted compounds but also detects predicted compounds as well as IAS. The objective is to compare raw materials and MNL films in order to identify IAS and NIAS, then MNL films with decontaminated product.

For the SURPASS project, the following methodology is applied for the analysis of a material (raw material or MNL film or recycled/decontaminated product):

- Simulant/solvent or thermal extraction (Head Space (HS) or Thermal desorption (TD)) followed by analysis using gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS). HS-GC-MS is used to detect volatile substances and TD-GC-MS for semi-volatile substances.
- Acid mineralization under microwave fields followed by analysis of the mineralized sample using ICP-MS (Inductively Coupled Plasma - mass spectrometry) for trace elements like heavy metals.

All these analytical methods may be useful for the analysis of NIAS. Table 14 indicates the applied apparatus parameters.

Table 14. Analytical methods and parameters used for NIAS/IAS identification.

Type of release target	NIAS/IAS analysis method	Apparatus parameters
NIAS/IAS	HS-GC-MS	Sampling method 0.5 g
		HS Desorption at 110°C for 60 min
		MS Scan mode : 33 to 620 m/z (Da)
	TD-GC-MS	Sampling method 0.1 g
		TD Desorption at 250°C for 15 min
	Solvent extraction GC-MS	Solvent extraction 5g in 200ml dichloromethan Soxhlet extraction
		MS Scan mode: 33 to 620 m/z (Da)
	Acid mineralisation IPC-MS	Sampling method 0.2 g
		Microwave Acid mineralisation Acids: HNO ₃ + HF + HCl
		ICP-MS Acquisition method: Semi quantification by screening

1.2.3.3.3 Migration tests: consumer use step

Migration tests are performed on films in order to ensure that the developed finished products meet the applied regulation N° 10/2011/EC.

Two levels of migration were considered: overall and specific migrations.

The aim is to compare the results of global and specific migrations of SSbD solutions and Reference for CS#3 and the Reference finished products intended to be exposed to food based on the regulations (European Commission (EC) 2004) and (European Union (EU) 2011) and associated amendments.

Food simulants are intended to simulate the interactions between the food contact materials and food and are used in migration experiments to simplify the analysis.

A simulant should be selected as worst case according to the food to be packaged. It should not cause swelling of the tested material or any other physical change that does not occur in contact with the intended foods. Furthermore, artefacts can be formed when aqueous or ethanolic simulants lead to hydrolysis and ethanolsis products, respectively. Some NIAS may also be lost through sample preparation.

For this study, two simulants worst case have been selected:

- 95% ethanol (v/v): it covers most of the food categories and is suitable for most of the polyolefin-based food contact materials showing only little interaction with the polymer (swelling).
- 3% Acid acetic (w/v): it covers the materials containing acid-soluble components (e.g. primary aromatic amines, heavy metals, etc.).

Overall migration (OM) is determined in accordance with standards NF EN 1186-1, NF EN 1186-3 and NF EN 1186-14. The regulatory threshold for overall migration is 10 mg/dm² of plastic in contact or 10 mg/kg of foodstuffs (Figure 68).

The contact conditions chosen are the following:

- Contact type: direct with the films (SSbD solutions or Reference) in dedicated migration cells like on Figure 68 (contact surface of the cut film 1 dm² with 200 ml - only one surface of the film is in contact with the simulant.).
- Contact conditions: 10 days in contact at 40°C (MG2 condition of regulation 10/2011/EC applies to materials in long-term contact with food).

Figure 68- Migration cell compliance with regulation 10/2011/EC

For specific migration (SM), a contact is performed between simulant and films and after a chemical screening is performed on the simulant in order to identify the substances that have migrated into the simulant and could therefore present a risk to the consumer.

The contact conditions chosen are the following:

- Contact type: direct with the films (SSbD solutions or Reference) by immersion in glass bottle like on Figure (contact surface of the cut film 1 dm² with 200 ml). The type of contact is the worst case for specific migration with all areas in contact with the simulant.
- Contact conditions: 10 days in contact at 60°C (applies to materials in long-term contact with food according to regulation 10/2011/EC).

Figure 69. Glass bottle for immersion contact compliance with regulation 10/2011/EC

The 95% ethanol simulants resulting from the contacts mentioned are analysed by gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry. A preliminary concentration step (by 67 times) was carried out to increase our chances of detecting substances. The 3 % acetic acid simulants resulting from the contacts mentioned are analysed by ICP-MS.

1.2.3.3.4 Micro- and nanoplastic spot-checks

Consumer use step: migration tests

For each film, a 10-day contact period with 95% ethanol is conducted in a migration cell at 40°C, following the global migration test conditions outlined in §3.2.3.2.3 (1 dm² film with 200ml 95% ethanol). After this period, the 95% ethanol simulant is filtered to quantify microplastics.

In parallel, one control sample is performed with only 95% ethanol without contact with film. This allows for the assessment of microplastic presence in the test protocol without a tested film sample.

Prior to contact, the simulant is filtered through an Al₂O₃ filter (Anodisc 47 mm, 0.2 µm) and stored until use. All laboratory glassware is rinsed accordingly, and only glass or stainless steel equipment is used. To minimize microplastic contamination, glassware is covered with aluminum foil.

Following contact, the 95% ethanol is collected and processed under a Class ISO 3 laminar flow hood (ISO 14644-1 standard) equipped with an ULPA (Ultra Low Penetration Air) filter. The ethanol is then vacuum-filtered using a vacuum flask and sintered glass with a 13 mm Ag filter.

Both the filter and the containers that previously held the 95% ethanol are rinsed multiple times with ultra-pure water. The filter is subsequently analyzed using a Micro-IRTF imager, Spotlight 400 (Perkin Elmer), to characterize the microplastics present. The infrared image is processed using the software “siMPle”.

Recycling process: washing water

Due to sample availability, the method testing was first done on a washing water sample for a PE/Aluminium laminate. Afterwards the washing water sample of a different recipe of mLLDPE/EVOH MNL films (made in the SURPASS project) was analyzed with the previously tested Raman method. A washing water blank was measured to detect any background contamination.

The received samples of 500 mL (from IPC) were stirred continuously while a 100 mL subsample was taken. In the case of the blank, the whole 100 mL volume was filtered through a polycarbonate filter with a diameter of 47 mm and a pore size of 0.2 μm . In the case of the washing water sample, the 100 mL subsample was stirred again, and a further 10 mL subsample of the washing water containing released particles from the mLLDPE/EVOH MNL films was filtered through a polycarbonate filter with a diameter of 47 mm and a pore size of 0.2 μm . Filters were slightly dried (room temperature, 30 min) and fixed on a sheet metal using double-sided adhesive tape. The filters were then transferred to a confocal Raman microscope (WITec alpha 300R) equipped with a 785 nm laser and a 20x objective. Raman Image acquisition and analysis was performed using WITec’s Suite FIVE and Particle Scout software. The fragment diameter was determined by Equivalent Circle Diameter. Using a laser wavelength of 785 nm has the advantage of reducing disturbing fluorescence in the Raman spectra (as compared to e.g., lasers at 532 nm). Particle sizes from 5-1000 μm were measured.

1.2.3.4 Results

1.2.3.4.1 *VOCs emissions*

Plastic drying activity

Only PA6 and EVOH are analyzed. No VOCs were detected by heating the samples at 60°C during 1 hour.

MNL co extrusion process

The list of analyzed samples is presented in Table 15. It includes two TENAX sorbent tubes from a single MNL process campaign, which involved the production of a 129-layer MNL film (PE/PA) with 7.5 wt% compatibilizer.

Table 15. List of analysed samples for the VOCs release test during the MNL process (CS#3)

Sample Reference	Description of test	Type of processed material (process conditions)
Air monitoring TENAX N°1	Blank	No processed materials
Air monitoring TENAX N°2	PE/PA MNL films 129 layers with 7.5% compatibilizer	MNL process

No products were detected in the TENAX analysis for the blank.

For MNL process, detected products are presented below, see Table 16.

Table 16. Detected substances in TENAX sorbent tubes CS#3

CAS number	Name of detected substance
/	Unknown (number = 3)
5055-74-3	1,5-Diphenyl-2H-1,2,4-triazoline-3-thione

In the analysis of potentially released chemicals during the MNL transformation process, only 4 substances were detected, of which 3 were unidentified.

The substance with CAS Number 5055-74-3 is not listed on the European Chemicals Agency website. Additionally, this substance is not a known transformation or degradation product for the mLLDPE, PA, and compatibilizer matrices. It may have formed through a reaction between two substances.

scCO₂ decontamination process

The list of analysed samples is presented in Table 17. They are 4 active carbons used during two scCO₂ process campaigns corresponding to 2 recipes of barrier layers.

Table 17. List of analysed samples for the VOCs release test during the CO₂sc process (CS#3)

Sample Reference	Localisation on the process line	Type of material processed (process conditions)
Active Carbon N°1	Degassing Stage (vacuum)	mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH weight ratio : 82/12/6 (80 bars, 130 minutes)
Active Carbon N°2	Extraction CO ₂ Outlet Stream	
Active Carbon N°3	Extraction CO ₂ Outlet Stream	mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio : 77.5/7.5/15 (80 bars, 125 minutes)
Active Carbon N°4	Degassing Stage (vacuum)	

The total VOC emission is estimated through an analysis by GC-MS of the activated carbon, by integrating the entire area of the chromatogram. The concentration is proportional to the area in the GC. The results are presented in Table 18 and Figure 70.

Table 18. Materials, process and area of VOC emission.

Materials	Sample	Process zone	Total aera of sVOC emission (in $\mu\text{V.s}$)	
mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH weight ratio : 82/12/6 (80 bars, 130 minutes)	Active Carbon N°1	Degassing Stage (vacuum)	1 405 791 525	1 609 120 396
	Active Carbon N°2	Extraction CO ₂ Outlet Stream	203 328 871	
mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio : 77.5/7.5/15 (80 bars, 125 minutes)	Active Carbon N°3	Extraction CO ₂ Outlet Stream	1 380 162 388	1 505 105 894
	Active Carbon N°4	Degassing Stage (vacuum)	124 943 506	

Figure 70. Total VOCs emission (in $\mu\text{V.s}$) in scCO₂ process (CS#3)

The level of total VOCs emissions is similar between the two formulations (mLLDPE/PA and mLLDPE/EVOH with compatibilizer). It is worth noting a difference in the quantity of VOCs released between the two areas of the process (degassing stage and CO₂ extraction).

A suspicion of sample inversion has been reported between the two sampling areas. To remove this doubt, additional tests were carried out and the results do not allow to confirm or rule out the sample inversion.

A summary of the chemical families detected, and the associated substances has been established in Table 19.

Table 19. Chemicals detected on active carbon during scCO₂ process of CS#3

Materials	Detected chemical families	Detected substances	Number CAS
mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH weight ratio: 82/12/6 (80 bars, 130 minutes)	Acid	Acetic acid	64-19-7
	Alcohol	Isopropyl Alcohol	67-63-0
	Alkyl oxirane/silane	Oxirane, trimethyl-	5076-19-7
	Acetate derivative	Isopropyl acetate	108-21-4
mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio: 77.5/7.5/15 (80 bars, 125 minutes)	Alcohol	Isopropyl Alcohol	67-63-0
	Alkyl oxirane/silane	Oxirane, trimethyl-	5076-19-7

VOCs are released during the decontamination process of MNL films using scCO₂. Indeed, the films are heated and treated to remove substances. These results confirm that this process is promising for decontaminating packaging films and even for eliminating volatile compounds originating from polymer formulation or degradation. This result is both useful for the SSbD assessment and for the advancement of the scCO₂ decontamination process.

1.2.3.4.2 NIAS

The list of analyzed samples for the screening of NIAS/IAS is presented in Table 20. These samples correspond to SSbD#1, SSbD#2 routes and Reference route of CS#3. For routes 1 and 2, formulations with or without compatibilizer, with a barrier layer made of PA or EVOH, and varying numbers of layers are compared.

Detected NIAS in simulant after migration test are presented in following paragraph 0.

Table 20. List of analyzed samples for NIAS/IAS release test of CS#3

Sample Reference	Type of analysis	Relevant Route of CS#3	Description of tested material
NIAS/IAS N°1	HS-GC-MS TD-GC-MS Solvent extraction – GC-MS ICP-MS	0 → Reference WIPAK ML packaging film	11 layers film PO/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio (%) 61/7/3
NIAS/IAS N°2	HS-GC-MS TD-GC-MS Solvent extraction – GC-MS ICP-MS	1&2 → SsbD Solutions MNL packaging film	129 layers film mLLDPE/EVOH weight ratio (%) 95/5
NIAS/IAS N°3	HS-GC-MS TD-GC-MS Solvent extraction – GC-MS ICP-MS		129 layers film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH weight ratio (%) 91/3/6
NIAS/IAS N°4	HS-GC-MS TD-GC-MS Solvent extraction – GC-MS ICP-MS		1025 layers film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH weight ratio (%) 91/3/6
NIAS/IAS N°5	HS-GC-MS TD-GC-MS Solvent extraction – GC-MS ICP-MS		129 layers film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio (%) 77.5/7.5/15
NIAS/IAS N°6	HS-GC-MS TD-GC-MS Solvent extraction – GC-MS ICP-MS		129 layers film mLLDPE/PA weight ratio (%) 85/15
NIAS/IAS N°7	HS-GC-MS TD-GC-MS Solvent extraction – GC-MS ICP-MS		1&2 → SsbD Solutions Raw materials
NIAS/IAS N°8	HS-GC-MS TD-GC-MS Solvent extraction – GC-MS ICP-MS		Pellets EVOH
NIAS/IAS N°9	HS-GC-MS TD-GC-MS Solvent extraction – GC-MS ICP-MS		Pellets PA
NIAS/IAS N°10	HS-GC-MS TD-GC-MS Solvent extraction – GC-MS ICP-MS		Pellets compatibilizer

The analyses written in red are those that will be included in the updated version of the deliverable.

The detailed results are available on Annex.

The objective is to identify new substances in MNL films by comparing them with raw materials. These new substances are NIAS (degradation products, contaminants of process, etc.). The limit of the methodology is the fact that it is not exhaustive.

The following Table 21 indicates the detected organics NIAS with the results of analysis by HS-GC-MS, TD-GC-MS and solvent extraction GC-MS.

Table 21: Identified organics NIAS by comparing raw materials and MNL films by GC-MS

Type of MNL film	NIAS	CAS Number
mLLDPE/PA with/without compatibilizer	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	96-76-4
	Acetone	67-64-1
	Diethyl Phthalate	84-66-2
	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	95906-11-9
	Alkane	/
	Caprolactam	105-60-2
	n-Hexadecanoic acid	57-10-3
	No identified	/
mLLDPE/EVOH with/without compatibilizer	2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	96-76-4
	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	95906-11-9
	Acetone	67-64-1
	Diethyl Phthalate	84-66-2
	Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	95906-11-9
	Alkane	/
	Octanal	124-13-0
	Nonanal	124-19-6
	Decanal	112-31-2
	Acetaldehyde	75-07-0
No identified	/	

Among all the identified NIAS, some are common to the MNL mLLDPE/PA and mLLDPE/EVOH film configurations (with or without compatibilizer). These are the ones written in red in Table 21.

The origin of these red substances is therefore the material mLLDPE or the MNL process:

- Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate (CAS N° 95906-11-9): It is a degradation product of the antioxidant **Irgafos 168**, which is commonly used in the composition of polyolefins such as polyethylene.
- Acetone (CAS N° 67-64-1): It is a degradation product of LDPE or a residual solvent used in the process.
- Diethyl phthalate (CAS N° 84-66-2) and 2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol (CAS N° 96-76-4): these substances can be degradation products of PE or contaminants introduced during the process due to prior production with materials containing these substances.

Some NIAS are degradation products of PA6 or EVOH. Specifically:

- For PA: n-Hexadecanoic acid (CAS N° 57-10-3) and caprolactam (CAS N° 105-60-2).
- For EVOH: acetaldehyde (CAS N° 75-07-0) and aldehydes (decanal, nonanal, octanal).

This result is consistent with the bibliographic data on the transformation products mentioned in the chapter 1.2.3.2.

The following Table 21 bis indicates the detected inorganics NIAS with the results of analysis by ICP-MS.

Table 21 bis : Identified inorganic NIAS by comparing raw materials and MNL films by ICP-MS

Type of MNL film	NIAS
mLLDPE/PA with/without compatibilizer	Lithium (Li)
	Sodium (Na)
	Cobalt (Co)
	Antimony (Sb)
mLLDPE/EVOH with/without compatibilizer	Magnesium (Mg)

All the identified inorganics NIAS are present in the MNL films in a low concentration level (maximum 200 ppm).

1.2.3.4.3 Migration tests: consumer use step

The list of analysed samples for overall migration tests is presented in Table 21. They correspond to routes 0, 1, and 2 of CS#3. For routes 1 and 2, formulations with or without a compatibilizer, are compared, along with barrier layers made of either PA or EVOH.

Table 21. List of analysed samples for overall migration tests – consumer use step of CS#3

Sample Reference	Relevant Route of CS#3	Description of tested material
OM N°1	0 → Reference – WIPAK ML packaging film	11 layers film PO/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio (%) 61/7/3
OM N°2	1&2 → SSbD Solution – MNL packaging film	65 layers film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio (%) 70/15/15
OM N°3	1&2 → SSbD Solution – MNL packaging film	129 layers film mLLDPE/EVOH weight ratio (%) 95/5
OM N°4	1&2 → SSbD Solution – MNL packaging film	129 layers film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH weight ratio (%) 91/3/6
OM N°5	1&2 → SSbD Solution – MNL packaging film	129 layers film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio (%) 77.5/7.5/15
OM N°6	1&2 → SSbD Solutions – MNL packaging film	129 layers film mLLDPE/PA weight ratio (%) 85/15

The results of overall migration (mean value ± standard deviation) in the two simulants (3% acid acetic and 95% ethanol) are presented in the Table 22.

Each simulant is representative of a type of food: 3% acetic acid for food products with a pH lower than 4.5 and 95% ethanol for food products containing fats or having an alcohol content.

Table 22. Results of overall migration tests for CS#3 according to regulation 10/2011/EC

Sample Reference	Route and description of tested material	3 % acetic acid		95% ethanol	
		mg/dm ² film	mg/kg food	mg/dm ² film	mg/kg food
OM N°1	0 → Reference 11 layers ML film	16 ± 5	96 ± 32	3,3 ± 0,7	20 ± 4
OM N°2	1&2 → SSbD solution 65 layers film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio (%) 70/15/15	10 ± 7	59 ± 39	< 1.0	< 1.0
OM N°5	1&2 → SSbD solution 129 layers film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio (%) 77.5/7.5/15	5.4 ± 0.3	33 ± 2	3.3 ± 1.3	20 ± 8
OM N°6	1&2 → SSbD solution 129 layers film mLLDPE/PA weight ratio (%) 85/15	11 ± 1	68 ± 8	3,0 ± 4,6	18 ± 27
OM N°3	1&2 → SSbD solution 129 layers film mLLDPE/EVOH weight ratio (%) 95/5	5 ± 6	31 ± 37	< 1.0	< 1.0
OM N°4	1&2 → SSbD solution 129 layers film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH weight ratio (%) 91/3/6	8 ± 5	45 ± 32	4 ± 12	22 ± 75
10/2011/EC Regulatory requirement		10	60	10	60

The values in green are those compliant with Regulation 10/2011/EC and the values in red are those not compliant with Regulation 10/2011/EC.

The Reference route is not intended to be used for contact with acidic foods. Indeed, the migration test in the 3% acetic acid simulant was carried out for comparison with the SSbD solutions. For this reason, this film did not comply with the overall migration requirements of Regulation 10/2011/EC for acidic food products.

Impact of compatibilizer on overall migration for SSbD solutions:

- For the mLLDPE/EVOH configuration, with the same number of layers (129 layers), the presence of a compatibilizer increases the overall migration value for the two simulants.
- For the mLLDPE/PA configuration, with the same number of layers (129 layers), the presence of a compatibilizer decreases or stabilizes the overall migration value for the two simulants.

Impact of number of layers on overall migration for SSbD solutions:

- For the mLLDPE/PA configuration with compatibilizer, by increasing the number of layers from 65 to 129 layers, a decrease in the overall migration value for the 3% acetic acid simulant and an increase for the 95% Ethanol simulant was observed.

It should be noted that these are preliminary results. These trends would need to be confirmed by testing different configurations in terms of compatibilizer percentage, number of layers, and conducting more repetitions.

Screening of specific migration tests

The list of analysed samples for the screening of specific migration tests is presented in Table 23. Each of them was analysed after contact with 3% acetic acid by IPC-MS and after contact with 95% ethanol by GC-MS. These samples correspond to routes 0, 1, and 2 of CS#3. For routes 1 and 2, formulations with or without compatibilizer, with a barrier layer made of PA or EVOH, and different numbers of layers were compared.

Table 23. List of analysed samples for screening of specific migration tests – consumer use step of CS#3

Sample Reference	Relevant Route of CS#3	Description of tested material
Screening SM N°1	0 → Reference – WIPAK ML packaging film	11 layers film PO/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio (%) 61/7/3
Screening SM N°2	1&2 → SSbD Solution – MNL packaging film	65 layers film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio (%) 70/15/15
Screening SM N°3	1&2 → SSbD Solution – MNL packaging film	129 layers film mLLDPE/EVOH weight ratio (%) 95/5
Screening SM N°4	1&2 → SSbD Solution – MNL packaging film	129 layers film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH weight ratio (%) 91/3/6
Screening SM N°5	1&2 → SSbD Solution – MNL packaging film	129 layers film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio (%) 77.5/7.5/15
Screening SM N°6	1&2 → SSbD Solution – MNL packaging film	129 layers film mLLDPE/PA weight ratio (%) 85/15
Screening SM N°7	1&2 → SSbD Solution – MNL packaging film	1025 layers film mLLDPE/EVOH weight ratio (%) 95/5
Screening SM N°8	1&2 → SSbD Solution – MNL packaging film	1025 layers film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH weight ratio (%) 91/3/6

95% ethanol simulant – GC-MS

Only qualitative analysis is performed on simulant, on organic compounds. The release level of substances in each simulant is assessed by considering the total area of the chromatogram obtained by GC-MS. In GC-MS, a detected substance is represented by a peak on the chromatogram, with an associated area proportional to the substance concentration. The total area of the chromatogram corresponds to the sum of the areas of all peaks. The graph on Figure 71 represents the evaluation of the level of substance release during a specific migration test (risk to the consumer) based on the total area of the chromatogram.

Figure 71. Graph of total area of chromatogram for specific migration screening on 95% ethanol CS#3

The Reference shows a lower release level than the SSbD solution versions, MNL film with 129 or 1025 layers. The trends are not similar between the mLLDPE/PA and mLLDPE/EVOH systems.

Impact of compatibilizer on organic specific migration level for SSbD solutions:

- For the mLLDPE/EVOH configuration, with the same number of layers, the presence of a compatibilizer slightly decreases the level of specific migration in the 95% ethanol simulant for system with 129 layers and increases the level for system with 1025 layers.
- For the mLLDPE/PA configuration, with the same number of layers (129 layers), the presence of a compatibilizer decreases the level of specific migration in the 95% ethanol simulant.

Impact of number of layers on organic specific migration level for SSbD solutions:

- For the mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH and mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA configurations, the increase in the number of layers leads to a higher level of specific migration in 95% ethanol.
- For the mLLDPE/EVOH configuration, the increase in the number of layers leads to a lower level of specific migration in 95% ethanol.

Several substances are detected on the 95% ethanol after contact. They are listed in the tables below: Table 24 for formulation mLLDPE/EVOH and Table 25 for formulation mLLDPE/PA.

If no specific substance could be identified but a chemical family was revealed, the latter is indicated. In this case, no CAS number is mentioned.

Table 24. Screening specific migration on 95% ethanol after contact with mLLDPE/EVOH MNL films

Identification substance	CAS number	SM N°3 GC	SM N°7 GC	SM N°4 GC	SM N°8 GC
		<i>MNL film mLLDPE/EVOH 129 layers</i>	<i>MNL film mLLDPE/EVOH 1025 layers</i>	<i>MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH 129 layers 3wt% compatibilizer</i>	<i>MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH 1025 layers 3wt% compatibilizer</i>
		Detected substance (X)			
Alkane	/	X	X	X	X
Alkene	/	X			
Not identified	/	X	X	X	X
Irgafos 168	31570-04-4	X	X	X	X
Irganox 1076	2082-79-3	X	X	X	X
Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	95906-11-9	X	X	X	X
Total area of the chromatogram		887 847 309	584 439 509	805 028 543	957 732 596

Table 25. Specific migration screening on 95% ethanol after contact with mLLDPE/PA MNL films

		SM N°1 GC	SM N°2 GC	SM N°5 GC	SM N°6 GC
		Reference PO/compatibilizer /PA 11 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA 65 layers 15wt% compatibilizer	MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA 129 layers 7,5wt% compatibilizer	MNL film mLLDPE/PA 129 layers
Identification substance	CAS number	Detected substance (X)			
Caprolactam	105-60-2	X	X	X	X
Alkane	/	X	X	X	X
Undecanoic acid	112-37-8	X			
Amide	/	X			
Oleamide	301-02-0	X			
Erucamide	112-84-5	X			
2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	96-76-4			X	X
No identified	/	X	X	X	X
Irgafos 168	31570-04-4	X	X	X	X
Irganox 1076	2082-79-3	X	X	X	X
Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	95906-11-9	X	X	X	X
Total area of the chromatogram		507 483 942	349 676 482	1 187 175 544	1 525 264 997
Reduction of NIAS between SSbD solutions and Reference (KPI >10% NIAS)			+51%	+69%	+87%

The identification results demonstrate the presence of organic NIAS in 95% ethanol simulants after contact with MNL films.

The NIAS are determined based on existing bibliographic data and are the substances in **green cells** on table 25. These are substances that are not usually intentionally added to PE, PA, and EVOH matrices or that are not authorized under EU Regulation 10/2011/EC (the polymer grades used are food-grade and therefore comply with the requirements of this regulation).

For example:

- The substance with CAS No. 95906-11-9 is a degradation product of the antioxidant Irgafos 168. This antioxidant is commonly used in the composition of polyolefins such as polyethylene.
- The substance with CAS No. 96-76-4 is not compliant with Regulation 10/2011/EC. It is a degradation or transformation product. It is detected in configurations with a high number of layers (>129 layers).

A Key Indicator Performance (KPI) for CS#3 focuses on the reduction of >10% of NIAS release from MNL films during realistic life cycle simulation, in particular for migration to food in comparison with conventional films.

This KPI can be studied with the screening on specific migration by comparing Reference and SSbD solutions.

Target KPI isn't obtained with an increase of NIAS release during realistic life cycle in comparison with the reference route.

3% acetic acid – ICP/MS

A semi-quantitative analysis is performed on the simulant via a semi-quantification of 64 chemical elements. A bias of +/- 30% should be considered between the semi-quantification value and the actual quantification value. Like for 95% ethanol, the release level of substances in each simulant is assessed by considering the total value of semi-quantification (sum of semi-quantification of each element in ppm) obtained by IPC-MS. The graph on Figure 72 represents the evaluation of the level of substance release during a specific migration test on 3% acetic acid (risk to the consumer) based on the total semi quantification value.

	SM N°1 ICP	SM N°2 ICP	SM N°6 ICP	SM N°5 ICP	SM N°3 ICP	SM N°4 ICP	SM N°7 ICP	SM N°8 ICP
	Reference PO/compatibilizer/PA 11 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA 65 layers 15wt% compatibilizer	MNL film mLLDPE/PA 129 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA 129 layers 7,5wt% compatibilizer	MNL film mLLDPE/EVOH 129 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH 129 layers 3wt% compatibilizer	MNL film mLLDPE/EVOH 1025 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH 1025 layers 3wt% compatibilizer
Total semi quantification (ppm)	1177	101	17	5	268	766	634	225

Figure 72. Graph of total semi-quantification (ppm) for specific migration screening on 3% acetic acid CS#3

The SSbD solutions, film MNL (SM N°2 to SM N°8), have a level of release of inorganics substances lower than the Reference (SM N°1). This can be related to the formulation of raw materials (inorganic fillers, dyes, etc.).

Impact of compatibilizer on inorganic specific migration level for SSbD solutions:

There is no single trend regarding the level of release of inorganic compounds in the presence or absence of compatibilization. The latter can either increase or decrease this release level for mLLDPE/PA and mLLDPE/EVOH with the same number of layers.

Impact of number of layers on inorganic specific migration level for SSbD solutions:

There is no single trend regarding the level of release of inorganic compounds with the number of layers. The latter can either increase or decrease this release level for mLLDPE/PA and mLLDPE/EVOH with the same number of layers.

The details of the semi-quantification in ppm obtained for each chemical element are provided in the following Table 26. It is the average of two measurements.

Out of 64 analysable chemical elements, 10 were semi-quantified (with values above the quantification limit QL). These elements are boron (B), sodium (Na), magnesium (Mg), Aluminium (Al), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), calcium (Ca), iron (Fe), cobalt (Co), and lanthanum (La).

The other elements have a quantification limit (QL) between 0.00005 ppm and 0.01 ppm.

	SM N°1 ICP	SM N°2 ICP	SM N°6 ICP	SM N°5 ICP	SM N°3 ICP	SM N°4 ICP	SM N°7 ICP	SM N°8 ICP	QL (mg/kg)
Chemical element	Reference PO/compatibilizer/PA 11 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA 65 layers 15wt% compatibilizer	MNL film mLLDPE/PA 129 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA 129 layers 7,5wt% compatibilizer	MNL film mLLDPE/EVOH 129 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH 129 layers 3wt% compatibilizer	MNL film mLLDPE/EVOH 1025 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH 1025 layers 3wt% compatibilizer	
B	205,3	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	304,2	266,6	91,2	0,0005
Na	241,8	98,3	<LQ	<LQ	268,4	410,2	367,1	128,7	0,05
Mg	14,0	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	0,0005
Al	9,7	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	52,1	<LQ	4,9	0,0005
P	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	4,0	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	0,05
K	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	0,5
Ca	706,3	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	0,1
Fe	<LQ	2,3	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	0,0005
Co	<LQ	<LQ	16,9	0,9	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	0,0005
La	<LQ	0,0	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	<LQ	0,000005
Total semi quantification	1177	101	17	5	268	766	634	225	

Table 26. Specific migration screening on 3% acetic acid after contact with films of CS#3 (QL : quantification limit)

For the SSbD solutions (SM ICP No. 2 to 8), compared to the mLLDPE/EVOH formulation, the mLLDPE/PA formulations contain Phosphorus, Cobalt, and Lanthanides. Compared to the mLLDPE/PA formulation, the mLLDPE/EVOH formulations contain Boron and Aluminium.

Compared to the SSbD Solutions, the Reference contains Calcium and Magnesium. Calcium is the predominant element, significantly impacting the total semi-quantification value. Calcium-based compound is employed as a filler in plastics.

1.2.3.4.4 Micro- and nanoplastic spot-checks

Consumer use step: migration tests

The list of analysed samples for the study of microplastics release on 95% ethanol after migration tests are presented in Table 27. Two replicates are performed by sample.

Table 27. List of analysed samples for study of microplastics on migration tests – consumer use step of CS#3

Sample Reference	Relevant Route of CS#3	Description of tested material
Microplastics on Migration test N°1	0 → Reference – WIPAK ML packaging film	11 layers film PO/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio (%) 61/7/3
Microplastics on Migration test N°2	1&2 → SSbD Solutions – MNL packaging film	65 layers film mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio (%) 70/15/15

The objective is to compare a commercial Reference of CS#3 (Route N° 1) with one MNL film with compatibilizer (Routes N°1&2) in terms of microplastic release into a simulant after a migration test. This test simulates film-food contact conditions. These samples are made with PE, PA, PP.

The results are presented in Figure 74. They correspond to the number of detected microplastics, averaged over two replicates. The sample control is detailed to monitor microplastic release in the test protocol, without contact with a film. The detection limit for microplastic size is 25 µm.

	Sample control	Reference (route N°0)	SSbD solution MNL film (routes N°1&2)
PE	2	1	0
PP	1	3	3
PMMA	39	82	23
PVC	0	5	4
PA	0	1	0
PS	0	2	1
Silicone	0	3	1
PU	0	2	2
Bio-based	0	0	2
EVA	0	0	1
PET	0	0	1
POB	0	0	1
ALL	42	96	37

Figure 74. Microplastics release in count by nature of polymer (μ -IRTF measurement of the 95% ethanol simulant after migration test).

The polymer most commonly found in the three samples subjected to testing is PMMA:

- 92% by count of PMMA for the control sample.
- 59% by count of PMMA for the MNL film.
- 83% by count of PMMA for the Reference sample.

PMMA is a widely used plastic in chemical analysis laboratory equipment. This polymer may originate from consumables or devices used throughout the testing strategy that can contaminate the test. The origin of other polymers such as PVC, PS, PU, and PET should be examined more closely. However, they do not come from the formulation of the Reference films or MNL.

It should be noted that the total microplastic release level under the applied conditions is similar for Reference film (Route No. 1) and MNL film selected for the study (Routes No. 1&2).

This evaluation indicates that the risk of microplastic release into food is the same for both the MNL film (SSbD route) and the Reference film. However, only a single MNL film configuration was tested (65 layers with an mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA weight ratio of 70/15/15). To confirm this preliminary finding, further tests with different MNL and Reference film configurations should be performed.

Recycling process: washing water

In the washing water after recycling of the mLLDPE/EVOH SURPASS laminate, several types of particles were found and quantified (Figure 75). While the primary counts of particles identified did not exhibit a Raman spectrum – indicating the presence of components lacking characteristic peaks, such as organic residue – a significant number of PE particles was also detected, which can be traced back to the original PE laminates. Based on the processing parameters and the measured volume of the subsample, the total number of PE fragments released from 1 kg of laminate can be calculated to around 2.000.000 PE microplastic counts/kg_{sample}. In contrast to the previously measured PE/Aluminum washing water (where no 65 µm sieving step was applied), all PE particles detected were < 200 µm in size, demonstrating the efficiency of the sieving step for the removal of larger fragments. Besides PE, microplastics from PET, PS and PP were also found, which cannot be traced back to the PE/EVOH laminates. In the blank sample no PE particles were found, but instead 1 PET and 4 PP particles per 100 mL could be detected, explaining some of the background contamination in the washing water sample.

Figure 75. µ-Raman measurement of the washing water sample after the recycling of mLLDPE/EVOH SURPASS MNL films. Based on the processing parameters, the microplastic release in counts per kg sample can be calculated.

In deliverable D4.4 'Report on link between phys/chem properties of (N)IAS, their functionality, and human and environmental toxicity', due at month 36, certain NIAS will be quantified, and an evaluation of consumer exposure will be studied using the ConsExpo tool in collaboration with RIVM partners.

1.2.3.5 Main findings in Case Study 3

Release investigations of substances in **CS#3** and the comparison between the Reference material and SSbD#2 Route have led to several observations. However, these are based on a limited number of replicates and different TRL levels. These factors should be considered when interpreting the trends below.

During MNL process and scCO₂ decontamination process, VOCs emissions were investigated. The data for the Reference Route is not available at the moment from the partner WIPAK. For this reason, during these activities, it was not possible to make a comparison between the VOCs emissions of the Reference and the SSbD solutions. In general, a higher release of VOCs is observed during the CO₂ decontamination process compared to the MNL process, as volatilization and stripping is intended in this step for removal, and emissions are captured by process design in activated carbon filters. During **drying of raw materials**, no VOCs emissions were detected.

Different NIAS have been identified for the SSbD solutions of CS#3, mLLDPE/PA and mLLDPE/EVOH MNL films with or without compatibilizer. Some examples are the Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate as degradation product of the antioxidant Irgafos 168, or the n-Hexadecanoic acid and caprolactam for PA systems, or acetaldehyde and aldehydes (decanal, nonanal, octanal) for EVOH systems.

For simulating the use stage, the screening specific migration tests were performed, where the release of organic substances from the SSbD solution in 95% ethanol simulant is higher than from the Reference material. However, for inorganic substances in 3% acetic acid simulant, the release is higher for the Reference than for the SSbD solutions.

The KPI “Reduction of >10% of release of NIAS from MNL films during realistic life cycle simulation, in particular for migration to food in comparison with conventional films” is obtained for inorganic compounds for all MNL films and for organic compounds for MNL films mLLDPE/compatibilier/PA with 65 layers and 15 wt% of compatibilizer.

To investigate potential release **during the washing activity**, the microplastics spot-check was conducted. It is possible to conclude that the washing water of recycling process contains a high level of microplastics after treatment of materials. The microplastic spot-check was also conducted during the migration test **to simulate the use scenario**. In this case, the release of microplastics is similar between Reference and SSbD solutions.

1.3 Scoring System for release assessment

Release refers to the liberation of a material/product during a natural or technical process at any stage of its life cycle and serves as the first step toward the assessment of potential exposure for workers, consumers, or the environment. Comprehensive qualitative and quantitative information on potential release is a crucial prerequisite for assessing exposure to released materials. However, the occurrence of a release does not necessarily imply exposure for various targets, including workers, the environment, consumers, or the general population. For exposure to occur, the released materials must be emitted into an environmental compartment where they can undergo fate and transformation processes (transmission) before coming into contact with, and potentially entering, the body of the receptor(s) through a specific exposure route.

For this reason, the identification of potential materials released along the life cycle of a material/product can be considered as initial step to investigate exposure of workers, consumers and environmental targets. Once a release hotspot is identified, additional investigations are conducted to identify and quantify the material released. With this aim, four sequential levels of assessment are proposed for the release scoring system and presented in figure 1.

It should be highlighted that several factors are contributing to passing from a level to another one:

- Data availability on performance evaluations of the tested product: more the product is close to the final product, less unintentional releases of materials are expected.
- Type of analytical techniques: more advanced analytical/coupled techniques are used, a more in-depth investigation and quantification of each substance released is possible to reach.
- Knowledge related to the investigated ES, technical knowledge related to release and hazard evaluations.
- Costs and time: more advanced analytical techniques also required higher costs and time-consuming analysis.

Exp. Target	Life Cycle Stage	Assesam. Scenario	Pot. Hotspot	Release test	Type of measur.	Total release		DiP (%)	Substance release	Type of measurement	Release of each substance		DiP (%)	Hazardous pattern/concern	
						Ref	SSbD				Ref	SSbD		Ref	SSbD
0 level				1 st level					2 nd level					3 rd level	

Figure 1. The four sequential levels of the scoring system for the release assessment.

Level 0: at this level, hotspots of release are identified based on the release hotspot questionnaire explained in paragraph 1.1. Hotspots of materials released are considered for each potential exposed target, life cycle stage and assessment scenario. If a potential release of material is identified following the rules established in paragraph 1.1, the assessment continues to the first level. Otherwise, exposure can be excluded for the specific exposure scenario (ES).

1st level: Once potential release hotspots of substances/materials are identified, a release test is conducted to mimic as much as possible the activities and use conditions of the ES. From this test, a quantification of the total release of material is expected to be obtained both for the Reference and

the SSbD products. The units of the total material released can change depending on the product investigated (e.g., mg powder/mg weight of the sample, or for VOC in µg/g). The DiP value is obtained in % and it is calculated using the equation presented below:

$$DiP (release) (\%) = \frac{[R]_{Ref} - [R]_{SSbD}}{[R]_{Ref}} * 100$$

where $[R]_{Ref}$ represents the concentration of the material released from the reference product and $[R]_{SSbD}$ represents the concentration of the material released from the SSbD alternative, obtaining the DiP as a single value using the total amount of release material from the reference product and from the SSbD alternative.

2nd level: Whenever is possible, the quantification of the different substances released is requested in this second level. The second level can be considered as a step forward of the one of the first level as it implies a quantification of each substance released from the total release quantification obtained (e.g., a quantification of a specific substance from the total release of the previous level). In the second level, different DiP values are obtained, one for each individual substance released from the reference product respect to the SSbD alternative.

3rd level: once a quantification of a substance will be obtained from the 2nd level, hazard considerations can be taken into account based on the identification of the substance released and/or morphological investigations. For example, in case of fibers released from the material, aspect/ratio and rigidity can be key parameters to take into account to establish if the fibers released can be classified as “critical fibers” following the fibers pathogenicity paradigm developed by WHO (‘NANoREG D2.12 -’ 2017).

Once the DiP is/ are obtained, a score can be assigned to a specific DiP range (Table 2).

Table 2. Current ranges of DiP (%) and associated score.

DiP (%)	Score
≤-20%	0
-20%<DiP≤+20%	1
20%<DiP≤+50%	2
>+50%	3

Nevertheless, these ranges are meant to be modified to better represent how much the SSbD alternative is better (or worst) than the reference product in terms of release performances. To be aligned with the scoring for hazard, LCA and LCC evaluations, the obtained score will range from 0 (the SSbD alternative is releasing more than the reference material), to 1 (the two tested materials have similar amount of material released) and 2 or 3 (the SSbD alternative released less materials than the reference).

In the 2nd level of scoring for release, for each ES and Hotspot, different DiP% and “2nd level scores” are obtained. The “2nd level scores” are integrated between them to provide a “ES Score” using a weighted average. The weighing should avoid that a small release amount (e.g., milligram) will be counted like as a relatively high release amount (e.g., grams).

Few considerations were made to help in the comprehension of the release scoring system:

- The total amount of release obtained in the first level of the assessment is not always equal to the sum of the substances released in the second level (as more accurate analytical techniques would give a more precise quantification).
- The % DiP and associated score of both levels will be shown to the final user in a table, to be transparent on how a certain score was obtained, and to track back which substance released was the cause of a low scoring.
- The scoring system developed can be used both for release and exposure estimations. However, as in the project we were not able to reach exposure estimations, release values are reported just to give indications on potential exposure of each receptor. In the worst-case scenario, it could be assumed that the release corresponds to the exposure.

How the scoring system was tuned and applied for each case study is reported in the following paragraphs.

Scoring system for CS1

Different alternative for SSRbD routes and reference routes (SSRbD#1 vs. Ref; SSRbD#2 vs. SSRbD#0; and SSRbD#0 vs. Ref) were considered in CS1, as presented in Fig. 1. Various release hotspots were identified for these routes, including cutting/milling, the thermal compression process, and the use stage (see Fig. 3). Due to the large volume of experimental data, the scoring implementation is illustrated using the example of the “use stage” for the vitrimerized bio-based material (SSRbD#2 route) in comparison with the bio-based material from Indresmat (SSRbD#0 route). The scoring tables for other routes and life cycle stages are fully reported in Annex.

At the Level 0 (Figure 38), the window settings in indoor and outdoor conditions were analyzed. This analysis revealed the potential release of organic compounds over time through both airborne outgassing and water leaching scenarios. These scenarios enable potential exposure for consumers (via inhalation) or for the environment (water and soil pollution).

For the level 1 evaluation, release tests were conducted to assess the total organic compounds release through TVOC outgassing at 40°C using TD-GC-MS/FID characterization and TOC release in water using UPLC-tofMS analysis as explained in paragraph 1.2.1.3. Both fresh materials and aged samples (subjected to an accelerated weathering protocol adapted from EN ISO 4892-2 method A), were evaluated to assess the total VOC release behavior over the materials' lifespan. The results obtained for the SSRbD#2 route are presented in the final scoring (Figure 38). For instance, in the case of fresh materials, the data show no significant difference in organic release in air but a strong decrease in water between the bio-based material and its vitrimer form (SSRbD#2), leading to score notations of 1 and 3, respectively. For aged materials, the results were mainly modified by lower released amounts and degradation of the DiP%, resulting in a scoring degradation (scores of 0 and 1).

For the second level assessment of organic compounds release, the main individual organic compounds or groups of compounds (e.g., C₁₈ carboxylic esters and propylene glycol family compounds) composing the TVOC or TOC were identified, quantified and the corresponding DiP was associated for each substance released (Figure 38).

Some species may be released only by the reference material or the SSbD material, leading automatically to scores of 3 and 0, respectively. As a result, the scoring of the different substances can be quite different from level 1, as illustrated below for the airborne release of fresh materials. Then, second level scores are integrated using a weighted average to obtain a total level 2 score based on more detailed release data.

Finally, based on the identification and quantification of substances detailed in the level 2 scoring, hazard considerations can be considered to establish the third level scoring. Further information can be found in D4.3.

0 level				1st level		2nd level					integrated 2nd level score		
Life Cycle Stage	Assessment Scenario	Potential Release Hotspot	Main potential receptor of release and route	Release test	Type of measurement / class of substance of interest	Score	Substance release	Type of measurement	Substance release			Score	
									Ref. mat. (bio-based)	S Sbd altern.	DiP (%)		
									S Sbd#0	S Sbd#2			
use	Airborne organic compounds release/exposure before/after weathering	long-term use in indoor/outdoors setting	consumers (inhalation, dermal) environment (air)	airborne organic compounds release rate @ 40°C	TVOC - TD-GC-MS/FID (ng/g/h)	1	ethylene sulfide (cas 420-12-2)	TD-GC-MS/FID (ng/g/h)	n.d.	0,16	<< -100%	0	0
							chlorobenzene (cas 108-90-7)		0,3	0,5	-67%	0	
							glycerin (cas 56-81-5)		3,66	0,17	95%	3	
							HEDS (cas 1892-29-1)		n.d.	0,96	<< -100%	0	
							Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester (cas 111-39-0)		0,37	0,76	-105%	0	
							C18-carboxylic acid ester compounds		0,27	0,81	-200%	0	
	airborne organic compounds release rate @ 40°C after 1000h-aging	TVOC - TD-GC-MS/FID (ng/g/h)	0	C2-oxidation compounds (acetone, acetic acid)	0,36	0,58	-61%	0					
				alkanes (C3, C5, C6, C8)	3,66	5,54	-51%	0					
				C6-C8 oxidation compounds (ketone, acids)	0,4	0,87	-118%	0					
	Organic compounds release by water leaching before/after weathering	long-term use in outdoors setting	environment (water, soil)	organic compounds release in water at 50°C	TOC (µg/g) by UPLC-tofMS	3	benzeneamine, 4-4'-methylene-bis- (cas 101-77-9)	UPLC-T ofMS (µg/g)	41,5	n.d.	>>100%	3	
propyleneglycols family							56,1		n.d.	>>100%	3		
organic compounds release in water at 50°C after 1000h-aging				TOC (µg/g) by UPLC-tofMS	1	benzeneamine, 4-4'-methylene-bis- (cas 101-77-9)	UPLC-T ofMS (µg/g)	38,5	n.d.	>>100%	3		
						propyleneglycols family		12	n.d.	>>100%	3		

Figure 38. Final scoring system for CS1.

Scoring system for CS2

As reported in paragraph 1.2.2.1, for case study 2, a hotspot of release during manufacturing stage was identified: the handling and cutting of carbon-fibers to produce the final composite can release micro and nanofibers in air, with a potential occupational exposure during this activity. However, as no differences in terms of particle size were observed from the fibers released during cutting in Route 0 and Route 1 (i.e., the Reference and the SSbD alternative), these results were not reported in the final scoring. Concerning the use stage, potential release of material into the environment can occur once the composite is applied on the exterior part of the train (Paragraph 1.2.2.1), activating the 0 level of the scoring (Figure 39). For simulating the effect of the outdoor weathering and the strong abrasion occurring during the use stage, the experimental test reported in paragraph 1.2.2.3 were performed and results were reported in the first level of the scoring. The DiP obtained for the total release for outdoor weathering and strong abrasion was 2, suggesting that the SSbD alternative has better performances compared to the reference material in terms of release. A different DiP score was obtained of 1 once releases of fibers and hardener were tracked, suggesting that no differences were noticed once these substances were analysed.

Different results were obtained from the microplastic spotcheck. Indeed, in this case, in the first level, a score of 3 was obtained, suggesting the good performances of the SSbD alternative compared to the reference material in terms of weight loss (to VOCs only) after 2000h of aging. The lower weight loss to VOCs indicates higher resistance against aging and presumably lower micro- and nanoplastic release. In the 2nd level for the DiP the same score was obtained for the nanoplastics released, while for DOC, no differences can be noticed from the SSbD alternative and the reference material obtaining a DiP of 1, and for microplastics a score of 0 was obtained suggesting that the SSbD alternative does not present better performances compared to the reference material in terms of release of microplastics after 2000h of aging.

Hazard considerations can be made once 0 or 1 DiP are obtained from each substance investigated in the second level. In this case study, hazard considerations related to the hardener are reported in D4.3. The aspect/ratio and rigidity of the released fibers suggested that they are “critical fibers” following the fibers pathogenicity paradigm developed by WHO (‘NANoREG D2.12 -’ 2017), leading to an hazardous concern. For micro- and nanoparticles, further investigations should be made considering the composition of these complex release products.

0 level				1st level					2nd level						
Life Cycle Stage	Assessment Scenario	Potential Release Hotspot	Main potential receptor of release and route	Release test	Type of measurement / class of substance of interest	Total release		DiP (%)	Score	Substance release	Type of measurement	Substance release		DiP (%)	Score
						Ref. mat.	SSbD altern.					Ref. mat.	SSbD altern.		
Use	Use as lightweight structural part of the train	Yes-abrasion and weathering	Environment	Weathering and strong abrasion tests (500h)	powder	0.43125	0.2675	37.97%	2	Hardener (AFD)	S (% released/tot); ICP-MS	26.40%	22.79%	13.67%	1
										Fibers	Fibers (% elongated particles with A/R>3); SEM	60.00%	53.00%	11.70%	1
				Weathering and strong abrasion tests (750h)	powder	0.548	0.41635	24.02%	2	Hardener (AFD)	S (% released/tot); ICP-MS	26.40%	11.60%	56.06%	3
										Fibers	Fibers (% elongated particles with A/R>3); SEM	73%	67%	8.22%	1
				mass loss (to VOCs) after aging 2000h	weight loss (mg/cm2)	0.81	0.49	65.31%	3	MPs	Microparticles, particle counter (mg/cm2)	0.037	0.048	-29.73%	0
										NPs	Nanoparticles, AUC (mg/cm2)	0.031	0.007	77.42%	3
DOC	DOC (mg/cm2)	0.155	0.135	12.90%	1										

Figure 39. Final scoring system for CS2.

Scoring system for CS3

For case study 3, as reported in paragraph 1.2.3.1, and specifically in table 11, several hotspots of release were identified during manufacturing, use and end-of-life. Many experimental tests were performed to simulate the different exposure scenarios identified in the 0 level. To demonstrate the application of the scoring system for CS3, the use phase was presented which is the most critical in terms of consumer exposure with potential ingestion of chemicals (**level 0**).

For **1st level** the performed test is a migration test according to regulation 10/2011/EU with three kinds of measurement:

- Overall migration in 95% Ethanol simulant.
- Total level of organic compounds migration.
- Total semi quantification of inorganic compounds migration.

For CS3, only one reference and 4 SSRbD alternatives solutions were taken into account, resulting in several DiP(%) and score by comparing each SSRbD alternative solution with the reference route.

The result of scoring system for 1st level is detailed below (Figure 40).

Due to the huge amount of experimental data obtained for each substance and each SSbD alternative material, in **2nd and 3rd levels**, results were reported for one alternative solution (PE-PA with compatibilizer). The result of scoring system for 2nd and 3rd levels is detailed in Figure 40.

0 level				1st level													2nd level										
Life Cycle Stage	Assessment Scenario	Potential Release Hotspot	Main potential receptor of release and route	Release test	Type of measurement/class of substance of interest	Total release					DIP (%) R-1	Score R-1	DIP (%) R-2	Score R-2	DIP (%) R-3	Score R-3	DIP (%) R-4	DIP (%) EVOH 2-4	Score R-4	Substance release	Type of measurement	Substance release			Score R-1		
						R Ref. mat. (PE-PA)	1 SSbD PE-PA with compatib.	2 SSbD PE-PA without compatib.	3 SSbD PE-EvOH with compat	4 SSbD PE-EvOH without compat												R Ref. mat. (PE-PA)	1 SSbD PE-PA with compati b.	DIP (%) R-1			
Step 3 : use	Consumer use : food contact matériel	Yes	Consumer - ingestion of food in contact with plastic	Migration test (according regulation 10/2011/EU)	Overall migration in 95% ethanol (mg/dm ²)	4	4.6	7.6	1	16	-15%	1	-90%	0	75%	3	-300%	No	0	No applicable							
					Total level of organic compounds migration (total area of chromatogram)	507,483,942	1,187,175,544	1,525,264,997	805,028,543	887,847,309	-134%	0	-201%	0	-59%	0	-75%	No	0	Caprolactam (CAS N° 105-60-2)	Quantification in ppm by GC-MS	3.4	1.4	59%	3		
																					2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol (CAS N° 96-76-4)	Quantification in ppm by GC-MS	0.07	0.33	-371%	0	
																						Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate (CAS N° 95906-11-9)	Quantification in ppm by GC-MS	1.5	9.3	-520%	0
					Total semi quantification of inorganic compounds migration (ppm)	1,177	5	17	766	268	100%	3	99%	3	35%	2	77%	No	3	Sodium	semi quantification in ppm by ICP-MS	242	98.3	59%	3		
																		Cobalt	semi quantification in ppm by ICP-MS	0.0005	16.9	-3379900%	0				

Figure 40. Final scoring system for CS3.

Possible improvements

Here below is presented a list of future improvements that can be applied for future improvement and use of the release scoring:

- **When possible, use release data to estimate the exposure of the target populations** by using exposure models. A proper model can be chosen based on the JRC recommendations on the SSbD Framework methodology.
- **Assign a weight to the release tests** performed to give more importance to tests that better simulate realistic release conditions. This would require a high level of knowledge on release/exposure scenarios as probably literature references are missing on how to assign these weights. This weighing will allow to integrate properly the different scores in level 2, to provide a unique score for each of the release pillars (=receptors of release: workers, consumers or environment).
- **Revise the threshold values associate to each score** depending on the obtained experimental data , to better represent the scoring categories to be aligned with the other scoring systems (hazard, LCA, LCC).
- **Develop a list of recommendations to deal with potential data gaps.** This would require to test the developed scoring system for other case studies and thus identify where data gaps can be identified (i.e., 1) a substance is added in the reference material and not in the SSRbD alternative – how can we make a % of improvement if a substance is not included in the 2 materials?; 2) the 2 tested materials have the same composition but the SSRbD alternative was manufactured in a different manner which does not permit the release of the substances as the reference material – how can we make a % of improvement in this case if the substances released are not the same?).
- Consider **the uncertainty and the TRL** of the case study in the scoring system. This would permit to show how the uncertainty of the obtained values is decreasing with higher TRL.

Considerations and limitations

How to face potential data gaps was also discussed along the development of the scoring system for release/exposure assessment, as many of the selected experimental tests are material-specific. For example, it would be not always possible to reach the 2nd level of the assessment for both the reference and SSRbD materials tested because of technical limitations (e.g., very low amount of release of material which is not possible to quantify with the available analytical technique). Moreover, the experimental design settled for one case study can be not completely suitable for another material. Some possible alternatives were considered in case of data gaps:

- Assign a score (e.g., default or expert judgment) just to make the comparison.
- Calculate the % of improvement only for the level in which data are available for both the materials.
- Associate the score with an uncertainty value.

Regarding the type of experimental tests that can be performed to obtain a scoring based on the DiP %, only experimental results which can give the type/quantity of substances released are needed. Additional tests which do not permit quantifying the material released (e.g., morphology evaluations of the material) can be considered as physico-chemical characterization of the released material to support the assessment, and sometimes the assignment of a score.

Regarding the third level of the release scoring system, as mentioned in 3.3.3.2, the release of a material may be of particular concern when the release is associated to a likely exposure and when the released material is a hazardous substance. However, this level is difficult to achieve as only in few scenarios pure substances are released from a product which cannot permits to integrate the release/exposure with hazard data.

Deviations from the workplan

To start with release experiments, T4.2 requested the “best samples available” concerning the later performance in the application from CS leaders at month M24. For this reason, in some cases, the materials tested were not the final developed materials. However, this situation may reflect the fact that SSRbD and related assessments should be applied early in the value chain (i.e., at the development stage), in which the materials available are still under their finalization.

Conclusions and perspectives

Deliverable 4.2 summarises the release assessment methodology developed in the context of WP4 as part of the SSRbD process. The theoretical part performed on the identification of release hotspots along the life cycle of each case study was considered as a first step in the release assessment. Then, once release hotspots were detected, experimental tests allowed us to verify if the substance(s) release occurred in agreement with the identified hotspot through quantitative and semi-quantitative analyses.

For CS1, experimental data for 3 different identified hotspots (namely milling/cutting process & thermo-compression process to investigate a potential workers exposure and the consumer stage with a potential exposure of consumer and environmental targets) determined contrasting conclusions. In case of the milling/cutting activity, potential airborne particles exposure was examined through dustiness and particles morphology & size, and it may be concluded that SSbD#1 route leads to lower potential release than the Reference. For the thermo-compression activity, the SSbD#1 route generates higher VOC outgassing than the benchmark case, detected a release mainly composed of TCPP flame retardant and cystamine by-products. Regarding the use stage, release measurements of micro/nanoplastics and organic compounds were performed by following weathering and leaching protocols. The main conclusions are listed below:

- *Release of micro/nanoplastics and abrasion resistance over ageing lead to no significant differences between the SSbD alternatives (i.e. SSbD #1 and #2) and their References (Ref. and SSbD#0)*
- *For airborne organic compounds release: SSbD routes show more VOC emissions than their non-vitrimer counterparts while fossil-based non-vitrimer route (Ref) appears very slightly less emissive than bio-based non vitrimer (SSbD#1). Fossil-based SSbD#1 releases lower TCPP than Reference route but additional compounds linked to the vitrimerization process are released: TCPP by-products (1-chloro-1-propene; 1-chloro-2-propanol; 1,2-dichloropropane...), anisole (impregnation solvent) and cystamine by-products. Bio-based materials (SSbD#0 and #2) release characteristic bio-compounds, namely C₁₆- & C₁₈- alkanolic & alkenolic acids esters and glycerin. Additionally, SSbD#2 PU releases the hydroxyethylthioisocyanate (HEDS) and the ethylenethioisocyanate. VOC release from all polymers is strongly reduced with ageing due to their depletion in the materials. However, low outgassing of oxygenated compounds (acetone, acetic acid) and alkanes (propane, pentane, hexane) may occur with weathering without significant difference between SSbD and References routes.*
- *Organic compounds release in water. Fossil-based PU (Ref. and SSbD#1 routes) may release significant TCPP and triethylenediamine and in addition the SSbD#1 PU emits polypropylene glycols (PPG) residues. Bio-based SSbD#2 material shows no significant release in water while the Reference route (SSbD#0) leads to low release of PPG residues and 4,4'-methylene-bis-benzamine.*

For CS2, all the experimental data collected during the simulation of the exposure scenario representing the use stage (i.e., weathering and abrasion to simulate when composite is applied on the exterior part of the train) permits to conclude that no significant difference is detected between the SSbD alternatives (i.e., SP1.1 RTM5 and SP3 RTM6) compared to the benchmark material (i.e., TCPP RTM). Indeed, measurements of the weight loss, characterization of the morphology and size of particles generated, and concentration of hardener released after abrasion showed similar results between the tested

samples. This is an important achievement in terms of the final SSbD assessment of this case study. Indeed, it is possible to conclude that the most promising SSbD alternative (i.e., SP3 RTM6) achieved the SSbD objectives, as compared to the Reference materials (i.e., metal product, TCPP RTM1.1) is i) less hazardous through the replacement of the halogen-based FR with the halogen-free FR, ii) more sustainable through the decrease of weight of the composite used, iii) more recyclable, and also iv) with the same release performances.

For CS3, the experimental data collected during the simulation of the exposure scenario representing the different life cycle stages of the packaging material. The most important scenario in terms of release is the use stage, as potential risk for the consumer can be detected when toxic substances can migrate from the packaging to the food, with the consequent ingestion of harmful substances by the consumer. For this reason, migration tests were performed to assess consumer exposure by simulating food/packaging contact. In this regard, SSbD solutions demonstrate compliance with global migration requirements according to Regulation 10/2011/EC. For specific migrations, lower releases for inorganic NIAS and higher releases for organic NIAS were observed when comparing SSbD solutions to the Reference route. Additional NIAS will be quantified and added in deliverable D4.4 'Report on link between phys/chem properties (of (N)IAS), their functionality, and human and environmental toxicity', due in month 36, and an evaluation of consumer exposure will be conducted using the ConsExpo tool from RIVM. In term of microplastics, the quantity of micro/nanoplastics detected during the use stage was similar between the Reference route and SSbD solution.

To conclude, this whole methodology was structured to compare a Reference material (e.g., a product already on the market with similar functionality) with the SSbD alternative(s) (i.e., the products developed in the project) for each case study. However, due to the differences on the materials/products selected, not all the release tests were possible for both the Reference and the SSbD alternative (e.g., in CS2, the Reference material is a metal product, while the SSbD alternative is a polymer one) that can reflect potential issues in implementing the SSbD Framework in real case studies. Moreover, it should be noted that, especially for CS3, the different TRL stage of SSbD solution and the Reference material can lead to a potential unbalance result when the release results of the SSbD and the Reference materials are compared among them.

Furthermore, collaborations between product developers and researchers performing release/exposure analysis offer the opportunity to share knowledge in a bidirectional way: product designers gave feedback on the identification of the most relevant release tests to be conducted based on the technical function of the product, but in the same way, results on the release assessment can also give indications on the functionality of the product to the product designers at the very early stage of the product development.

2 Annex

CS#1 – Focus on *feSEM* images of foam materials (SSbD#0 and SSbD#2 route) – cross-section

CS#2 – SEM images analysed with ImageJ software to obtain particle size measurements of 15 fibers for each sample.

Different images of the same specimen SP1 RTM at 0h (a-b-c-d) and 500h (e-f-g-h) selected to quantify fibers size.

Different images of SP3 RTM at 0h (a-b-c-d) and 500h (e-f-g-h) selected to quantify fibers size.

Different images of TCPP RTM at 0h (a-b-c-d) and 500h (e-f-g-h) selected to quantify fibers size.

CS#2- Size measurements of the fibres and Aspect Ratio (A/R) released after abrasion of SP1, SP3 and TCPP.

Sample	Aging	Length	Diameter	A/R	% elongated particles with A/R>3
TCPP	0h	15.21	6.59	2.31	82
		21.94	6.49	3.38	
		16.23	4.28	3.79	
		23.54	4.64	5.07	
		13.46	6.32	2.13	
		25.18	6.62	3.80	
		12.80	4.01	3.20	
		17.59	5.61	3.14	
		17.42	6.52	2.67	
		26.08	6.26	4.16	
		57.01	6.37	8.95	
		36.42	7.76	4.69	
		45.99	6.47	7.11	
		31.91	6.49	4.92	
		22.14	6.16	3.59	
		36.76	8.07	4.55	
		42.33	6.22	6.81	
		500h	29.17	6.49	
	63.53		8.33	7.63	
	24.77		6.52	3.80	
	38.30		6.80	5.63	
	28.34		6.80	4.17	
	16.16		6.79	2.38	
	52.02		6.67	7.80	

		19.49	6.53	2.99	
SP3	0h	12.73	7.03	1.81	0
		13.25	6.58	2.02	
		12.58	5.28	2.38	
		10.38	6.33	1.64	
		13.68	6.53	2.10	
		17.55	6.65	2.64	
		17.65	6.58	2.68	
		8.38	7.03	1.19	
	500h	22.18	7.28	3.05	60
		14.65	6.85	2.14	
		44.73	6.80	6.58	
		17.50	7.20	2.43	
		34.84	6.87	5.07	
	SP1	0h	25.31	6.55	3.87
22.98			6.04	3.81	
15.48			6.21	2.49	
24.32			6.35	3.83	
30.37			6.67	4.56	
30.16			5.75	5.25	
19.82			5.74	3.45	
12.87			5.75	2.24	
27.86			6.30	4.42	
40.20			6.45	6.23	
18.89			7.04	2.68	
13.79			5.36	2.57	
41.94			6.62	6.34	

		8.63	3.18	2.72	
		6.85	3.85	1.78	
		9.55	5.16	1.85	
		7.54	4.10	1.84	
		6.28	1.88	3.34	
		9.51	3.32	2.87	
		8.87	3.09	2.87	
		4.69	1.53	3.06	
		10.79	6.74	1.60	
		5.64	2.24	2.51	
		3.48	1.35	2.58	
		4.82	1.76	2.74	
	500h	5.56	4.21	1.32	
		4.97	1.43	3.48	
		3.14	0.92	3.41	
		6.03	1.34	4.51	
		6.08	3.08	1.97	
		4.50	1.50	3.00	
		4.86	1.43	3.41	
		4.56	1.99	2.29	
		16.73	6.44	2.60	
		5.52	3.84	1.44	
		6.08	2.99	2.03	
		6.02	3.34	1.80	
					29

CS#3-detailed results for identification of substances in MNL films, Reference and raw materials in order to identify NIAS (HS-GS-MS, TD-GC-MS and solvent extraction)

Solvent extraction- GC- MS		NIAS/IAS N°1	NIAS/IAS N°7	NIAS/IAS N°9	NIAS/IAS N°8	NIAS/IAS N°6	NIAS/IAS N°5	NIAS/IAS N°2	NIAS/IAS N°3	NIAS/IAS N°4
		Reference MNL film PO/compatbilizer/PA 11 layers	Raw material mLLDPE	Raw material PA6	Raw material EVOH	MNL film mLLDPE/PA 129 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatbilizer/PA 129 layers 7,5% compatbilizer	MNL film mLLDPE/EVOH 129 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatbilizer/EVOH 129 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatbilizer/EVOH 1025 layers
identified substance	CAS No.	Area of peak								
Caprolactam	105-60-2	108 751 360				116 961 616	218 347 504			
Alkane	/						5 762 758			
2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	96-76-4					4 813 482	11 049 932		4 092 942	
Alkane	/		6 402 734			5 503 413	7 224 709		7 954 823	16 570 456
Alkane	/	7 954 364	6 233 807			10 377 290	12 337 446	4 920 900	12 486 819	29 681 832
Alkane	/	6 369 030	8 666 992			18 106 078	255 001 430	8 360 371	15 571 515	42 247 460
Alkane	/	6 863 162	3 534 034			10 290 987	11 142 712		7 864 767	25 617 022
Alkane	/	5 066 170	2 256 330			8 449 577	8 856 261		5 767 889	18 558 406
Alkane	/	3 219 828								
Alkane	/		1 814 296			7 031 130	7 398 499		4 648 358	13 564 739
Alkane	/		2 037 555							
Alkane	/					31 887 212	37 232 388			
Not identified	/					5 888 736	19 075 532		13 937 688	15 903 383
Alkane	/									9 626 395
Oleamide	301-02-0	83 936 448								
Alkane	/									6 354 259
Antioxidant Irgafos 168	31570-04-4	56 205 192	26 392 316			63 310 128	714 258 304	63 350 128	191 080 352	1 007 551 424
Antioxidant Irganox 1076	2082-79-3	73 671 160	391 484 960			507 105 312	941 938 192	283 848 736	537 884 544	1 035 802 944
Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphate	95906-11-9	53 326 924	471 262 336			880 210 752	715 672 576	359 520 000	673 884 992	718 987 136
TOTAL		405 363 638	920 085 360	0	0	1 669 935 713	2 965 298 243	720 000 135	1 475 174 689	2 940 465 456

HS-GC-MS		NIAS/IAS N°1	NIAS/IAS N°7	NIAS/IAS N°9	NIAS/IAS N°8	NIAS/IAS N°6	NIAS/IAS N°5	NIAS/IAS N°2	NIAS/IAS N°3	NIAS/IAS N°4
		Reference MNL film PO/compatbilizer/PA 11 layers	Raw material mLLDPE	Raw material PA6	Raw material EVOH	MNL film mLLDPE/PA 129 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatbilizer/PA 129 layers 7,5% compatbilizer	MNL film mLLDPE/EVOH 129 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatbilizer/EVOH 129 layers	MNL film mLLDPE/compatbilizer/EVOH 1025 layers
identified substance	CAS No.	Area of peak								
Not identified	/		7 335 877							
Alkane	/	422 396								226 569
Alkane	/					657 390	1 391 688	956 132	601 499	100 066
Alkene	/	372 237								
Alkane	/	213 380								69 290
Octa/l	124-13-0							203 568	137 310	189 989
Alkane	/	427 429				1 112 303	1 848 429	1 276 965	980 826	235 517
No//l	124-19-6	1 940 273						473 635	238 364	428 587
Alkane	/		39 192 352							
Deca/l	112-31-2							328 952	188 491	380 408
Caprolactam	105-60-2	5 450 450				7 931 092	4 790 923			
Alkane	/	1 263 162				1 399 336	1 766 585	1 804 198	1 347 385	760 411
Alkane	/		14 802 416		1 191 035					
Alkane	/	615 713				310 448	624 327	470 199	530 146	588 422
Alkane	/	261 382	7 452 427	3 567 935	2 912 827	86 973	182 244	196 756	274 178	255 318
TOTAL		10 966 422	68 783 072	3 567 935	4 103 862	11 497 542	10 604 196	5 710 405	4 298 199	3 234 577

TD-GC-MS	NIAS/IAS N°1	NIAS/IAS N°7	NIAS/IAS N°9	NIAS/IAS N°8	NIAS/IAS N°6	NIAS/IAS N°5	NIAS/IAS N°2	NIAS/IAS N°3	NIAS/IAS N°4	
	Reference	Raw material	Raw material	Raw material	MNL film	MNL film	MNL film	MNL film	MNL film	
	Ml.film PO/compatibilizer/PA 11 layers	mLLDPE	PA6	EVOH	mLLDPE/PA 129 layers	mLLDPE/compatibilizer/PA 129 layers	mLLDPE/EVOH 129 layers	mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH 129 layers	mLLDPE/compatibilizer/EVOH 1025 layers	
Identified substance	CAS No.	Area of peak								
2-Butene	107-01-7		53 879 972							
2-Propanol, 2-methyl-	75-65-0		9 407 722							
Acetic acid	64-19-7			38 960 600						
Maleic anhydride	108-31-6		119 223 856							
Acetic acid	64-19-7			110 808 416						
Alcane	/		23 789 160							
Non identifié	/			233 163 040						
Carbon dioxide	124-38-9	71 285 456				91 294 576	28 310 954	28 741 838	37 537 588	
Acetaldehyde	75-07-0						50 231 240	27 631 984	20 465 096	
Sorbic Acid	110-44-1			13 281 317						
Acetone	67-64-1					1 475 518 080	23 425 662	18 841 158	18 588 488	
Alcane	/			2 600 898						
3,4-Dimethylidihydrofuran-2,5-dione	7475-92-5		63 013 640							
Octanoic acid, methyl ester	111-11-5			2 717 045						
Alcane	/	207 355 424	274 311 712							
Not identified	/						62 864 216			
3,4,5-Trimethylidihydrofuran-2-one	/		53 684 596							
E-Hex-2-en-1,2-dicarboxylic acid	132631-27-7		117 668 112							
Non identifié	/		121 621 120							
Alcane	/	206 351 072	774 554 880							
2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	96-76-4	49 700 220	424 303 968							
Alcane	/	244 795 008	1 023 953 536							
Diethyl Phthalate	84-66-2			13 684 268						
Alcane	/	237 572 368	954 541 888							
n-Hexadecanoic acid	57-10-3		180 988 304	16 984 636						
Alcane	/	259 183 200	851 884 288			66 169 376				
1-Eicosanol	629-96-9	65 225 348								
Caprolactam	105-60-2	18 681 042 944				126 593 920				
Alcane	/	233 055 232	596 909 760							
Alcane	/					106 680 048	94 521 800	75 949 304	83 050 216	
Non identifié	/	26 999 212								
Phenol, 4-(1,1-dimethylpropyl)-	80-46-6	251 220 928								
Dimethyl phthalate	131-11-3	98 985 888					29 530 802			
Not identified	/		183 370 464						33 099 558	
Alkane	/		509 526 880							
2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol	96-76-4	70 941 800				100 465 312	49 894 412	50 130 732	45 658 300	
Alcane	/			4 371 511			91 771 624	90 942 632	99 411 760	
Alcane	/					50 505 928				
Diethyl Phthalate	84-66-2	289 673 728				67 714 336	39 085 148		40 108 680	
Not identified	/		131 489 912	372 567 552			144 678 688		131 641 680	
Not identified	/								114 488 392	
Alcane	/						701 668 288	566 196 032	601 438 720	
Not identified	/						38 280 980			
Alcane	/	83 729 336	262 904 672			144 759 952			35 872 628	
Not identified	/			7 716 931			258 106 880	336 297 410	554 777 984	
Not identified	/						77 919 168			
Alcane	/	159 269 120					193 977 344	185 100 544		
Not identified	/								371 694 528	
n-Hexadecanoic acid	57-10-3					255 299 952				
Alcane	/	247 803 424	52 445 896	155 569 248		424 870 208	1 581 118 080	1 392 984 192	1 844 558 592	
Alcane	/	174 677 952				189 341 328	635 620 544	547 982 144	739 467 008	
Not identified	/							328 139 616	374 690 560	
Alcane	/	394 609 536	29 710 796	75 814 152		510 784 096	2 027 586 560	1 545 689 728	1 790 284 160	
Not identified	/	108 434 912					175 278 416	485 990 080		
Alcane	/	889 502 400	15 181 931	44 573 608		3 204 152 832	1 641 891 712	1 473 457 536	3 180 714 240	
Not identified	/	250 570 240		509 912 896		3 595 196 672	304 908 672	582 916 416	636 816 576	
TOTAL		21 688 018 328	2 232 466 129	7 601 467 852	211 125 622	3 595 196 672	6 814 149 944	8 250 671 190	7 736 991 346	10 754 364 754

CS#1- Scoring results for release assessment at the hotspot release identified over the lifecycle of the SSbD#1 route (vitrimized fossil-based PU) versus the Ref. route (fossil-based PU)

Life Cycle Stage	0 level				1st level				Score	2nd level				Score	integrated 2nd level score	
	Assessment Scenario	Potential Release Hotspot	Main potential receptor of release and route	Release test	Type of measurement / class of substance of interest	Total release		DiP (%)		Substance release	Type of measurement	Substance release				DiP (%)
						Ref. mat.	SSbD altern.					Ref. mat.	SSbD altern.			
					Fossil PU	SSbD#1			Fossil PU	SSbD#1						
cutting / milling	airborne particles release / exposure	high energy mechanical activity	Workers (Inhalation, Dermal)	powder analysis	D ₅₀ (respirable dustiness index in mass; µg/kg)	1407	121	91%	3							
				powder analysis	D ₅₀ (respirable dustiness index in number; #/mg)	29577	4948	83%								
Thermal compression	airborne VOC release / exposure	powder material, high pressure and temperature process	Workers (Inhalation)	Mass loss	ATG @ 200°C (%w.)	6,80%	9,80%	-44%	0			n.d.	0,18	<< -100%	0	
				TVOC release	d-TD-GC-MS/FID (mg/g) @ 200°C	25,00	42,50	-70%	0	ethylene sulfide (cas 428-12-2)	d-TD-GC-MS/FID (mg/g) @ 200°C	n.d.	0,18	<< -100%	0	
										thiazolidine, 2-methyl (cas 24050-16-6)		n.d.	1	<< -100%	0	
										2 unidentified cystamine by-products		n.d.	1,38	<< -100%	0	
										anisole (cas 100-66-3)		n.d.	16,3	<< -100%	0	
										TCPP (cas 13674-84-5)		17,1	17,6	-2,92%	1	
										DOP (cas 117-81-7)		1,7	0,05	97,06%	3	
										DBP (cas 84-74-2)		0,02	0,09	-350,00%	0	
				use	Airborne organic compounds release/exposure before/after weathering	long-term use in indoor/outdoors setting	consumers (inhalation, dermal) environment (air)	airborne organic compounds release rate @ 40°C	TVOC - TD-GC-MS/FID (ng/g/h)	1,7	369	-2160%	0	TVOC - TD-GC-MS/FID (ng/g/h)	propylene glycol (cas 57-55-6)	n.d.
airborne organic compounds release rate @ 40°C after 1000h-aging	TVOC - TD-GC-MS/FID (ng/g/h)	45	197					-338%	0	anisole (cas 100-66-3)	n.d.	132	<< -100%		0	
										propylene carbonate (cas 2108-32-7)	n.d.	2,4	<< -100%		0	
										2 unidentified cystamine by-products	n.d.	2,63	<< -100%		0	
										TCPP (cas 13674-84-5)	0,19	0,03	84%		3	
										1-chloro-2-propanol (cas 127-00-4)	n.d.	2,4	<< -100%		0	
										1,2-dichloropropane (cas 78-87-5)	n.d.	3,8	<< -100%		0	
										1-chloro-1-propene (cas 590-21-6)	n.d.	1,4	<< -100%		0	
										C2-oxidation compounds (acetone, acetaldehyde)	9,3	5,4	42%		2	
										anisole (cas 100-66-3)	n.d.	41	<< -100%		0	
propylene carbonate (cas 2108-32-7)	n.d.	0,24	<< -100%		0											
2 unidentified cystamine by-products	n.d.	0,43	<< -100%		0											
TCPP (cas 13674-84-5)	0,03	0,03	0%		1											
1-chloro-2-propanol (cas 127-00-4)	n.d.	0,37	<< -100%		0											
1,2-dichloropropane (cas 78-87-5)	n.d.	1,7	<< -100%		0											
1-chloro-1-propene (cas 590-21-6)	n.d.	0,07	<< -100%		0											
Organic compounds release by water leaching before/after weathering	long-term use in outdoors setting	environment (water, soil)	organic compounds release in water at 50°C		TOC (µg/g) by UPLC-toIMS	363	1906	-425%	0	TOC (µg/g) by UPLC-toIMS	TCPP (cas 13674-84-5)	165	110	33%	2	
			organic compounds release in water at 50°C after 1000h-aging		TOC (µg/g) by UPLC-toIMS	314	1774	-465%	0		triethylenediamine (TEDA, cas 280-57-9)	172	201	-17%	1	
											benzeneamine, 4-(4'-methylene-bis-(cas 101-77-9))propyleneglycols family	nd	46	<< -100%	0	
											propyleneglycols family	nd	703	<< -100%	0	
				trimethylolpropane (TMP, cas 77-99-6)							nd	25	<< -100%	0		
				TCPP (cas 13674-84-5)							217	91	58%	3		
				triethylenediamine (TEDA, cas 280-57-9)							86	232	-170%	0		
				benzeneamine, 4-(4'-methylene-bis-(cas 101-77-9))propyleneglycols family							nd	37	<< -100%	0		
				propyleneglycols family							nd	762	<< -100%	0		
				trimethylolpropane (TMP, cas 77-99-6)							nd	29	<< -100%	0		

CS#1- Scoring results for release assessment at the hotspot release identified over the lifecycle of the SSbD#2 route (vitrimized bio-based PU) versus SSbD#0 route (bio-based PU)

0 level				1st level				2nd level				Score	Integrated 2nd level score									
Life Cycle Stage	Assessment Scenario	Potential Release Hotspot	Main potential receptor of release and route	Release test	Type of measurement / class of substance of interest	Total release	DIP (%)	Substance release	Type of measurement	Substance release	DIP (%)											
						Ref. mat.	SSbD altern.			Ref. mat.	SSbD altern.											
use	Airborne organic compounds release/exposure before/after weathering	long-term use in indoor/outdoors setting	consumers (inhalation, dermal) environment (air)	airborne organic compounds release rate @ 40°C	TVOC - TD-GC-MS/FID (ng/g/h)	SSbD#0 (Bio-based PU)	SSbD#2	160	169	-6%	1	ethylene sulfide (cas 420-12-2)	TD-GC-MS/FID (ng/g/h)	n.d.	0,16	<< -100%	0	0				
																	chlorobenzene (cas 108-90-7)		0,3	0,5	-67%	0
																	glycerin (cas 56-81-5)		3,66	0,17	95%	3
																	HEDS (cas 1892-29-1)		n.d.	0,96	<< -100%	0
																	Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester (cas 111-39-0)		0,37	0,76	-105%	0
																	C18-carboxylic acid ester compounds		0,27	0,81	-200%	0
		Organic compounds release by water leaching before/after weathering	long-term use in outdoors setting	environment (water, soil)	airborne organic compounds release rate @ 40°C after 1000h-aging	TVOC - TD-GC-MS/FID (ng/g/h)	3	21	-600%	0	0	C2-oxidation compounds (acetone, acetic acid)	TD-GC-MS/FID (ng/g/h)	0,36	0,58	-61%	0					
																alkanes (C3, C5, C6, C8)	3,66		5,54	-51%	0	
																	C6-C8 oxidation compounds (ketone, acids)		0,4	0,87	-118%	0
				organic compounds release in water at 50°C	TOC (µg/g) by UPLC-toMS	144,5	26,6	82%	3	benzeneamine, 4-4'-methylene-bis-(cas 101-77-9) propylene glycols family	UPLC-toMS (µg/g)	41,5	n.d.	>>100%	3							
				organic compounds release in water at 50°C after 1000h-aging	TOC (µg/g) by UPLC-toMS	62,9	70,7	-12%	1	benzeneamine, 4-4'-methylene-bis-(cas 101-77-9) propylene glycols family		56,1	n.d.	>>100%	3							
																		3				

CS#1- Scoring results for release assessment at the hotspot release identified over the lifecycle of the SSbD#0 route (bio-based PU) versus Ref. route (fossil-based PU)

0 level				1st level				2nd level				Score	Integrated 2nd level score									
Life Cycle Stage	Assessment Scenario	Potential Release Hotspot	Main potential receptor of release and route	Release test	Type of measurement / class of substance of interest	Total release	DIP (%)	Substance release	Type of measurement	Substance release	DIP (%)											
						Ref. mat.	SSbD altern.			Ref. mat.	SSbD altern.											
use	Airborne organic compounds release/exposure before/after weathering	long-term use in indoor/outdoors setting	consumers (inhalation, dermal) environment (air)	airborne organic compounds release rate @ 40°C	TVOC - TD-GC-MS/FID (ng/g/h)	Fossil PU (foam)	SSbD#0	188	169	10%	1	ethylene sulfide (cas 420-12-2)	TVOC - TD-GC-MS/FID (ng/g/h)	n.d.	n.d.	<< -100%	0	1				
																	chlorobenzene (cas 108-90-7)		0,22	0,3	-36%	0
																	glycerin (cas 56-81-5)		n.d.	3,66	<< -100%	0
																	HEDS (cas 1892-29-1)		n.d.	n.d.	<< -100%	0
																	Hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester (cas 111-39-0)		n.d.	0,37	<< -100%	0
																	C18-carboxylic acid ester compounds		n.d.	0,27	<< -100%	0
		Organic compounds release by water leaching before/after weathering	long-term use in outdoors setting	environment (water, soil)	airborne organic compounds release rate @ 40°C after 1000h-aging	TVOC - TD-GC-MS/FID (ng/g/h)	4,6	21	-357%	0	0	propylene carbonate (cas 2108-32-7)	TVOC - TD-GC-MS/FID (ng/g/h)	4	n.d.	>>100%	3					
																TCP (cas 13674-84-5)	0,54		n.d.	>>100%	3	
																	C2-oxidation compounds (acetone, acetic acid)		5,19	0,58	89%	3
																	alkanes (C3, C5, C6, C8)		n.d.	5,54	<< -100%	0
				organic compounds release in water at 50°C	TOC (µg/g) by UPLC-toMS	363	144,5	60%	3	benzeneamine, 4-4'-methylene-bis-(cas 101-77-9) propylene glycols family	UPLC-toMS (µg/g)	165	n.d.	<< -100%	3							
				organic compounds release in water at 50°C after 1000h-aging	TOC (µg/g) by UPLC-toMS	314	62,9	80%	3	benzeneamine, 4-4'-methylene-bis-(cas 101-77-9) propylene glycols family		172	n.d.	<< -100%	3							
																		2				
																		0				
																		0				
																		0				
																		0				

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